

To my parents, Esad and Nadija

and

To those who inspired my endeavours

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Edib Smolo
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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Acknowledgements	ii
Table of Contents	iii
List of Tables	vi
List of Cases	vii
List of Abbreviations	viii
CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION	1
1.0 Background of the Study	1
1.1 Problem Statement	4
1.2 Justification of Problem	5
1.2.1 General Point of View	6
1.2.2 Religious Point of View	7
1.2.3 Economic Point of View	9
1.3 Infrastructure of Islamic Banks	11
1.4 Objectives of the Study	12
1.5 Methods of the Study	12
1.6 Outline of the Study	13
CHAPTER 2: <i>BAY' BITHAMAN 'AJIL</i>	14
2.0 Introduction	14
2.1 Definition	14
2.2 Basic Features of BBA	16
2.3 Determination of the Price	17
2.4 Overdependence of Islamic Banks on BBA Financing	19
2.5 Sharī'ah Rulings on BBA	21
2.6 How Does It Work? – Mechanism of BBA	23
2.7 Risks Related to BBA	26
2.8 Maqāsid Al-Sharī'ah, Qawā'id Al-Fiqh and BBA	26
2.9 Objections Related to the BBA	31
2.10 Vulnerability of the BBA Contract	32
2.10.1 Rising Interest Rate	33
2.10.2 Falling Interest Rate	35
2.10.3 Inflation	36
2.11 Conclusion	37
CHAPTER 3 <i>MUSHĀRAKAH MUTANĀQISAH PARTNERSHIP</i>	40
3.0 Introduction	40
3.1 Literature Review	41
3.2 Overview of Mushāraakah	44
3.2.1 Definition	44
3.2.2 Legality of Mushāraakah Mutanāqisah	44
3.2.3 Profit and Loss Sharing under MMP	45
3.2.4 Termination of Mushāraakah Mutanāqisah	45
3.3 Mechanism of Mushāraakah Mutanāqisah Partnership	46
3.4 Basic Conditions for Valid Mushāraakah Mutanāqisah Partnership	49
3.5 Salient Features of the Mushāraakah Mutanāqisah Partnership	51
3.6 Advantages and Disadvantages of MMP	51
3.6.1 Advantages of the MMP	51
3.6.2 Disadvantages of the MMP	53

3.7	Examples of MMP Being Practiced	53
3.8	Comparison Between Conventional Loan, BBA and MMP	56
3.9	Necessary Legal Amendments	58
3.9.1	Income Tax Act 1967	59
3.10	Conclusion	60
CHAPTER 4 <i>IJĀRAH SUKŪK</i>		62
4.0	Introduction	62
4.1	Literature Review	63
4.2	Nature of Ijārah Sukūk	65
4.2.1	Definition of Ijārah Sukūk	65
4.2.2	Conditions for Issuance of Sukūk	65
4.2.3	Structure and Mechanism of Ijārah Sukūk	66
4.2.4	Sale of the Leased Asset	67
4.2.5	Characteristics of Ijārah Sukūk	68
4.2.6	Application of Ijārah Sukūk	71
4.3	Evolution of Ijārah Sukūk: A Historical Overview	72
i)	Bahrain	72
ii)	Malaysia	73
iii)	Qatar	74
iv)	Saudi Arabia	75
v)	United Arabic Emirates (UAE)	75
vi)	The Rest of the World	76
4.4	Securitization	78
4.5	Advantages and Disadvantages of Ijārah Sukūk	81
4.5.1	Advantages of Ijārah Sukūk	81
4.5.2	Disadvantages of Ijārah Sukūk	81
4.6	Challenges Related to Ijārah Sukūk	82
4.7	Practical Issues	84
4.8	Comparison Between BBA, MMP and Ijārah Sukūk	84
4.9	Conclusion	87
CHAPTER 5 RESEARCH FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS		88
5.0	Introduction	88
5.1	Research Methodology	88
5.2	Data Collection	89
5.3	Findings and Analysis	90
5.3.1	Profile Analysis	90
5.3.2	BBA Analysis	91
5.3.3	MMP Analysis	95
5.3.4	Comparative Analysis between BBA and MMP	98
5.3.5	Ijārah Sukūk Analysis	100
5.3.5	General Comments by the Participants	101
5.4	Conclusion	103
CHAPTER 6 CONCLUSION		105
6.0	Introduction	105
6.1	Findings and Contributions	106
6.2	Limitation and Further Research	109
BIBLIOGRAPHY		111
APPENDIX A: A Mathematical Derivation Model		120

APPENDIX B: Survey 124
APPENDIX C: Frequency Tables 129

LIST OF TABLES

<u>Table No.</u>		<u>Page No.</u>
1.1	Islamic Banking System: Financing concepts as at end of 2005	6
2.1	Modes of Islamic Finance in Malaysia	20
3.1	Comparison between conventional loan, BBA and MMP	57
4.1	Features of <i>Ijārah Sukūk</i>	71
4.2	<i>Ijārah Sukūk</i> Ratings History	78
4.3	Comparison between BBA, MMP and <i>Ijārah Sukūk</i> contract arrangements	85
5.1	Distribution of Questionnaires and Response Rate	90
5.2	Distribution of Respondents by Gender, Age, and Marital Status	90
5.3	Distribution of Respondents by Education, Occupation and Knowledge about Islamic Products	91
5.4	Respondents' Perception of BBA	92
5.5	Familiarity with MMP	95
5.6	Respondents' Perception of MMP	96
5.7	Preference: BBA, MMP and Conventional Loan	98
5.8	True Representative of IFS	99
5.9	Development of IFS	99
5.10	Familiarity with <i>Ijārah Sukūk</i>	100
5.11	Participants' perception on <i>Ijārah Sukūk</i>	100
5.12	Occupation vs. Familiar with MMP	103
5.13	Occupation vs. <i>Ijārah Sukūk</i>	103

LIST OF FIGURES

<u>Figure No.</u>		<u>Page No.</u>
2.1	Real <i>al-bay^c bithaman ājil</i>	24
2.2	Actual <i>al- bay^c bithaman ājil</i>	25
3.1	<i>Mushārah mutanāqisah</i> structure in home financing	47
3.2	<i>Mushārah mutanāqisah</i> structure in corporate financing	49
4.1	Malaysian Global <i>Sukūk</i>	67

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AAOIFI	Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions
ACHC	Ansar Co-operative Housing Corporation
AFHL	American Finance House LARIBA
AHL	Ansar House Limited
AIBs	Assets Ijārah Bonds
APR	Annual Profit Rate
BAFIA	Banking and Financial Institutions Act 1989
<i>BBA</i>	<i>Bay^c Bithaman Ājil</i>
DJCSI	Dow Jones Citigroup Sukuk Index
GNP	Gross National Product
IDB	Islamic Development Bank
IBA	Islamic Banking Act 1983
IBF	Islamic Banking and Finance
ICHC	Islamic Co-operative Housing Corporation
IUM	International Islamic University Malaysia
IRTI	Islamic Research and Training Institute
KFH	Kuwait Finance House (M) Berhad
LIBOR	London Inter-Bank Offer Rate
LTP	Lease-To-Purchase
MCCA	Muslim Community Cooperative Australia
MMP	<i>Mushāraka Mutanāqisah</i> Partnership
M-M	<i>Mudhārabah</i> and <i>Mushārah</i>
PBUH	Peace Be Upon Him
PLS	Profit and Loss Sharing
PPA	Property Purchase Agreement
PSA	Property Sale Agreement
RA	<i>Radiyallāhu ^cAnhu</i>
S.O.S	Shared Ownership Scheme
SPV	Special Purpose Vehicle
swt	<i>Subhānahū wa ta^cālā</i>
S&P	Sales and Purchase Agreement

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.0 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Islamic economics, banking and finance started breathing some forty years ago. The emergence of the Islamic banks is considered as “the most remarkable and revolutionary development”¹ within the banking system today, it has engraved itself into the world of economic and financial systems. Many scholars have written on Islamic economics in general and Islamic banking and finance in particular. Many workshops, seminars and conferences are being held all over the world discussing the issues pertaining to Islamic economics and finance. Nevertheless, this discipline is very young one and it is in the process of development.

Since the Islamic economics follows the teachings of Islam, it is governed by the Laws of Allah (swt) (i.e. *Sharī‘ah*). This implies that the interest (*ribā*) and other illegal acts (e.g. *gharar* and exploitation) are strictly prohibited, and trade with mutual consent is encouraged. Allah (swt) says in this regard:

الَّذِينَ يَأْكُلُونَ الرِّبَا لَا يَقُومُونَ إِلَّا كَمَا يَقُومُ الَّذِي يَتَخَبَّطُهُ الشَّيْطَانُ مِنَ الْمَسِّ ذَلِكَ بِأَنَّهُمْ قَالُوا إِنَّمَا
الْبَيْعُ مِثْلُ الرِّبَا وَأَحَلَّ اللَّهُ الْبَيْعَ وَحَرَّمَ الرِّبَا فَمَنْ جَاءَهُ مَوْعِظَةٌ مِنْ رَبِّهِ فَانْتَهَى فَلَهُ مَا سَلَفَ وَأَمْرُهُ
إِلَى اللَّهِ وَمَنْ عَادَ فَأُولَئِكَ أَصْحَابُ النَّارِ هُمْ فِيهَا خَالِدُونَ (البقرة, 275)

“Those who devour usury will not stand except as stands one whom the Evil One by his touch hath driven to madness. That is because they say: "Trade is like usury but Allah hath permitted trade and forbidden usury. Those who after receiving direction from their Lord desist shall be pardoned for the past; their case is for Allah (to judge); but those who repeat (the offence) are companions of the fire: they will abide therein (for ever)”, (Al-Qur’an, al-Baqarah: 275)

يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا لَا تَأْكُلُوا أَمْوَالَكُمْ بَيْنَكُمْ بِالْبَاطِلِ إِلَّا أَنْ تَكُونَ تِجَارَةً عَنْ تَرَاضٍ مِّنْكُمْ وَلَا تَقْتُلُوا
أَنْفُسَكُمْ إِنَّ اللَّهَ كَانَ بِكُمْ رَحِيمًا (النساء, 29)

“O ye who believe! eat not up your property among yourselves in vanities: but let there be amongst you traffic and trade by mutual good-will: nor kill (or destroy)

¹ M. Azizul Hoque, “Islamic Banking and Some of Its Possible Impacts” in *Islamic Banking: How Far Have We Gone?*, edited by A.H. Pramanik (IIUM: Research Centre, 2006), 107.

yourselves: for verily Allah hath been to you Most Merciful"² (Al-Qur'an, an-Nisa': 29).

Having these verses in mind, many Muslim scholars have tried, and are still trying, to come up with modes of financing³ that are *Shari'ah based*⁴ and in line with *maqāsid al- Shari'ah*. Usually Islamic scholars refer to Islamic modes of finance as *Shari'ah compliant* products while here we would like to promote *Shari'ah based* and not *Shari'ah compliant* modes of financing. This thesis focuses on some of the financial instruments, namely *mushārah mutanāqisah* partnership, *ijārah* and *ijārah sukūk*, which are used to finance acquisition of assets and which, if implemented properly would be *Shari'ah-based*.⁵

This is not an easy job when we are trying to combine two things that are mutually exclusive; Islamic banking and finance based on *Shari'ah* which prohibited *ribā* and other illegal acts and conventional banking and finance that is solely based on *ribā*. Ziauddin Sardar raises the question of whether or not we need banks in an Islamic economic system.⁶ He further goes on saying that by inheriting western-made banks we are inheriting the western culture and values. By accepting the banks we accept "the entire exploitative and theoretical framework that comes with it."⁷ It is that system itself that is bad – according to him - and therefore should be addressed with caution. Another scholar, Muhammad Anwar, also questions banking system as well as the operations of Islamic banks. He opines that both are of doubtful validity due to the problem of seigniorage.⁸ However, we believe that without banks it would be very difficult to meet the needs of all economic agents in today's world. It is necessary for us to have banks and financial institutions, but these banks and institutions should be fully in line with the *Shari'ah* teachings. These banks and

² Translation by A.Yusuf Ali.

³ Note: Mode, product and instrument of financing will be used interchangeably throughout this paper.

⁴ What do we mean here by *Shari'ah-based* is that Islamic financial products should be in line with *maqāsid al- Shari'ah* and *al-qawā'id al-fiqhiyyah*. In other words, it should incorporate *Shari'ah* as whole. Here, the author acknowledges indebtedness to Prof. Dr. Mahmood Sanusi for the introduction of *Shari'ah-based* term during the consultation with the author. Mahmood Sanusi (personal communication, December 29, 2006), International Islamic University Malaysia, Malaysia.

⁵ According to Muhammad Anwar, there are 21 operational modes which are interest free and can be used by Islamic banks. They are: *mudarabah*, *musharakah*, *musharakah mutnaqisah*, *ijārah*, *ijārah wa iqtina*, *murābahah*, *bai' al-salam*, *bai' al-mu'ajjal* (*bai' bi al-thaman al-ajil*), *bai' istisna*, *bai' eena*, *muzara'ah*, *musaqah*, *qard al-hasan*, *wakalah*, service charge, sale on installments, development charges, equity participation, sale and purchase of shares, purchase of trade bills, and financing through *awqaf*. See Muhammad Anwar, "Islamicity of Islamic Banking Practices" in *Islamic Banking: How Far Have We Gone?*, edited by A.H. Pramanik (IIUM: Research Centre, 2006), 355.

⁶ Ziauddin Sardar, *Islamic Futures: The Shape of Ideas to Come*, (Kuala Lumpur: Pelanduk Publications, 1988), 203-206.

⁷ *Ibid.*, 204.

⁸ This is due to the fact that Islamic banks are operating under fractional reserve system. It means that even Islamic banks create fiat money using Islamic modes of finance. See Muhammad Anwar (2000, 2006). Regarding the socio-economic effects of the creation of fiat money and seigniorage see also Ahamed Kameel Mydin Meera (2002, 2004) as well as Meera and Larbani (2005).

institutions may not necessarily be like ordinary banks and financial institutions but rather investment banks and institutions (i.e. PLS-based banks and institutions).

Today's Islamic banking and finance, though still young, have not reached its horizons yet. The main reason, I would say, is that Islamic economics is a subordinate to the conventional economic system. It is functioning under some kind of supervision of the latter. More and more time is spent for justification of Islamic economics and promoting it to Western world. This led Islamic economics to become "variation of Western economic thought."⁹ Its scope of products or derivatives is very limited and *ribā* of conventional banks is, more or less, a benchmark for the rate of return in Islamic banks. Due to these reasons many Muslims are reluctant to use facilities offered by Islamic banks.¹⁰ Furthermore, standards and requirements with regard to operating and running of Islamic banking and finance (IBF) differ from a country to a country.

How much "Islamic" is an Islamic bank? Can they survive in this increasingly volatile market and tough competition? Did they fulfil the necessary criteria and accomplish the mission bestowed upon them? – are only some of the questions that can be raised in this regard. Islamic banks are rotating around one or two products with which they are trying to meet all needs of the people. In Malaysia, they are mostly using *bay' bithaman ājil (BBA)* or instalment sale mode of finance. Their practice is very similar to their conventional counterparts. It seems that they are only carrying Islamic name,¹¹ while everything else is more or less the same as in conventional banks. According to *New Horizon*,¹² Islamic banks are operating using modes of Capitalist system. This overdependence on few instruments and mainly short-term financing is worrisome since it cannot address all needs of the Muslim society. Long term projects are rarely financed due to the mismatch between the short-term deposits and long-term financing of those projects. There are two reasons why we should be concerned about this situation of Islamic banks. Firstly, overemphasis of Islamic banks on short-term financing will marginalize them since there are serving only a part of public needs and this will push them into shadows of the financial system. Secondly, this practice does not create new capital, thus it does not contribute to Gross National Product (GNP) growth.¹³ In most cases these funds from Islamic banks are used for consumer goods which are not adding to the economic growth and development. Very little is used to meet investment needs and finance

⁹ See Seyyed Vali Reza Nasr, *Islamization of Knowledge: A Critical Overview*, (Islamabad: International Institute of Islamic Thought, 1992), 3.

¹⁰ For example, *bay' bithaman ājil* or *BBA* mode of financing is widely used in countries such as Malaysia, Indonesia, Brunei, etc. while this mode of finance is disapproved by Middle Eastern scholars.

¹¹ See Muazzam Ali, "Islamic Banking: The Challenge From Within," *New Horizon*, no. 101, August 2000, 3.

¹² "Islamic Banking: A Long Journey Ahead," *New Horizon*, no. 104, November 2000, 2.

¹³ Ismail Bacha Obiyathullah, "Conventional versus Mudaraba Financing: An Agency Cost Perspective" in *Islamic Banking: How Far Have We Gone?*, edited by A.H. Pramanik (IIUM: Research Centre, 2006), 177-178.

development and growth projects. It is therefore believed that *mudārabah* and *mushārah* financing instruments should be used by Islamic banks and financial institutions. Obiyathullah is of opinion that these two modes of financing are “the *raison d’etre* of Islamic banks.”¹⁴ Muhammad Taqi Usmani stated that the *mushārah* is “the ideal instrument of financing according to *Sharī‘ah*”¹⁵ since it allows the share of the profit and loss by both parties according to their invested capital.

It is in a human nature to strive for a better life and to live more comfortably. One of the basic goals, that every individual is trying to get throughout his lifetime, is the comfort of a home and the necessity of a car. However, meeting these ends requires one to have funds. In most cases personal income and saving are not enough to buy a house or a car on cash terms. Therefore, these individuals, wishing to meet their life dreams, have no other option but to apply for a loan from a bank or financial institution. If they do not have Islamic scheme of finance available for them they will be trapped into the web of *ribā* (interest). Because of all of this, Muslim *Ummah* in general and Islamic economists in particular are responsible for protecting these individuals from harm of *ribā* by providing them with Islamic modes of finance. Implementing *MMP* and *ijārah* financing will enable them to get what they want while at the same time avoiding *ribā* payment.

1.1 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Islamic banks have passed the test of the time. Throughout the years of its existence, the activities and services have improved leading to great results. Besides all of this, current status and development of Islamic banks and financial institutions are far from being bright. Stella Cox is reported saying:

Whilst we can begin this new millennium on a very positive note, there are ongoing inefficiencies that need to be addressed. We must nurture all that has been achieved to date whilst avoiding complacency and finding solutions to existing problems that will continue to strengthen Islamic economic and financial practice and maintain its growth curve. This can be achieved, In sha Allah, through sharing of ideas and experiences so that the levels of education and depth of knowledge are broadened throughout the industry.¹⁶

This paper is of the view that Islamic banks and financial institutions, due to the limited modes of finance and services, and primarily short-term financing, are not at their optimum

¹⁴ Ibid., 178.

¹⁵ Muhammad Taqi Usmani, *An Introduction to Islamic Finance*, (The Hague: Kluwer Law International, 2002), 113.

¹⁶ Cited in “Islamic Banking: A Long Journey Ahead,” *New Horizon*, no. 104, November 2000, 2.

performance. In other words, there is a lot more to be done. This paper attempts to offer more *Shari'ah* compliant ways for these institutions to reach their optimum goals.

The purpose of this study is to analyze the characteristics and operational procedures used by Islamic banks and financial institutions with special focus on *MMP*, *ijārah* and *ijārah sukūk*. This paper will try to answer following questions:

1. What is the current *status quo* of Islamic banks and financial institutions?
2. Which modes of finance are used the most by Islamic banks?
3. How can *MMP*, *ijārah* and *ijārah sukūk* modes of finance be implemented into Islamic banking and finance?
4. Why these products?
5. How can these modes of finance promote profit-sharing financing and help both, Islamic banks as well as customers?
6. What are the problems and challenges faced by Islamic banks in today's world?
7. What are possible obstacles for implementing these modes of finance and how can these problems be avoided?

1.2 JUSTIFICATION OF PROBLEM

So far, Islamic banks and financial institutions have been overwhelmed by few products/services, among which one is more predominant than the others. This one is known as *Bay' Bithaman Ājil* (BBA) or differed payment (on instalment). The minimum and maximum percentage of banking finance under each mode, shown as average for ten leading Islamic banks – according to Muhammad Anwar – are as follows: “*murābahah-cum-bai' al-mu'ajjal* 45%-93%, *mushārahah* 1%-20%, *mudarabah* 1%-17%, *ijārah* (leasing) 0%-14% and other modes 0%-30%”.¹⁷ He also cites the mode of financing of Bank Islam Malaysia Berhad for the year ended on 30 June 1999. In this case the proportions are: *murābahah-cum-bai' bi al-thaman al-ājil* 91.55%, *ijārah* 3.41%, *mushārahah* 0.52%, *mudārahah* 0.47%, and *qard al-hasan* 2.63%.¹⁸ Another set of data showing proportions of each mode of financing is presented in Table 1 below. It is due to this reason, among others, that Islamic banks failed to reach their zenith. They failed on these levels: Firstly, they were not able to capture bigger share of the market size and to attract new customers due to the limited modes of financing. Secondly, they were not able to meet unlimited needs and wants of the clients with limited modes of financing (using mainly BBA). Thirdly, they were not able to fulfil the role of the Islamic banks, i.e. to promote just, profit sharing approach and to set the path for Islamic economic order.

¹⁷ Anwar, “Islamicity of Islamic Banking Practices”, 356.

¹⁸ Ibid.

Table 1.1
Islamic Banking System: Financing concepts as
at end of 2005

<i>Mode of Finance</i>	<i>2005</i>
Al-Bay ^c Bithaman Ajil	40.70%
Al-Ijāra	31.60%
Al-Istisna'	0.90%
Mudharaba & Mushāraka	0.30%
Murābahah	6.90%
Other Islamic Contracts	19.60%

Source: Bank Negara Malaysia, Annual Report 05.

This proposal will be justified from three points of view, namely from general point of view, religious point of view and economic point of view.

1.2.1 General Point of View

The solutions, offered by this paper to the under-developed Islamic banks and financial institutions, will be beneficial for both, Islamic banks as supplier of the funds and clients as the customers of Islamic banks and users of these funds. From the perspective of the clients, these services will result in following:

- i) It will be more affordable for the clients to meet their needs through these new products by reducing the cost of the financing these needs and wants;¹⁹
- ii) These services will be more in line with *Shari'ah*, which is one of the most important concerns for Muslim clients. Validity of the current modes of financing used by the Islamic banks has been questioned by many.²⁰

As for Islamic banks, these services will bring to the Islamic banks:

- i) Diversification of their modes of financing;

¹⁹ For more information on the advantages of *mushārahah mutanāqisah partnership* see, Ahamad Kameel M.M. and Dzuljastri A.R., "Islamic Home Financing Through *Mushāraka Mutanāqisah* and *al-Bay' Bithaman Ajil* Contracts: A Comparative Analysis," *Review of Islamic Economics*, vol. 9, no. 2 (2005): 5-30.

²⁰ For more details on validity of Islamic modes of financing see, Muhammad Anwar, "Islamicity of Islamic Banking Practices" in *Islamic Banking: How Far Have We Gone?*, edited by A.H. Pramanik (Kuala Lumpur: IIUM Research Centre, 2006), 353-368.

- ii) This will leave them more options to meet the client's needs and wants by having more products and services for financing them; and
- iii) By offering more products and, therefore, attracting more clients, Islamic banks will be able to acquire more shares in the market and with this more profit.

1.2.2 Religious Point of View

Islamic banks are supposed to be different from their conventional counterparts in its very nature. However, their performance is very much similar to the performance of the conventional banks. They are using same tools for evaluation and even the mode(s) of finance is to a great extent similar to the *ribā*-based financing techniques used by conventional banks and financial institutions. *BBA* is criticized by many authors writing on Islamic economics because of its similarity to the *ribā*-based modes of finance. Vogel and Hayes concluded that *BBA* “is the closest Islamic analogue to interest finance, and accordingly has been universally employed as a vehicle of finance throughout Islamic history.”²¹ The very reason why *BBA* contracts should be avoided and why *MMP*, *ijārah* and *ijārah sukūk* should be implemented throughout Islamic banks and financial institutions is that *BBA*, as stated above, is the closest to the interest based financing. In other words, *BBA* is some kind of replica to the interest which should not be the case. Legality of *murābaha* is based on the evidences from *Qur'an* and *Sunnah*. Allah (swt) says: “*Those who devour usury will not stand except as stands one whom the Evil One by his touch hath driven to madness. That is because they say: "Trade is like usury but Allah hath permitted trade and forbidden usury. Those who after receiving direction from their Lord desist shall be pardoned for the past; their case is for Allah (to judge); but those who repeat (the offence) are companions of the fire: they will abide therein (for ever)"*”, (Qur'an, *al-Baqarah*: 275). This contract is also supported by *ahādith* from the Prophet Muhammad (pbuh). One such *hadīth* is the one narrated by Muslim, “If the two kinds (of commodities) differ, sell as you wish (whichever price) so long as they are (exchanged) hand in hand (on the spot)”.²²

Legality of *mushāraka* in general has been found in *Qur'an*, *Sunnah*, and consensus of Muslim scholars. Allah (swt) said: “*In what your wives leave your share is a half if they leave no child; but if they leave a child ye get a fourth; after payment of legacies and debts. In what ye leave their share is a fourth if ye leave no child; but if ye leave a child they get an eighth; after payment of legacies and debts. If the man or woman whose inheritance is in question has left neither ascendants nor descendants but has left a brother or a sister each one of the two gets a sixth; but if more than two they share in a third; after payment of legacies and debts; so that no loss is caused*

²¹ Frank E. Vogel and Samuel L. Hayes, *Islamic Law and Finance: Religion, Risk and Return*, (The Hague, London and Boston: Kluwer Law International, 1998), 139.

²² Cited in Mustafa Omar Mohamed, *Islamic Financial Contracts (Module 2)*, Fiqh Muamalat Course Material, (International Islamic University Malaysia, 2005), 3.

(to anyone). Thus is it ordained by Allah and Allah is All-Knowing Most Forbearing.” (an-Nisa’: 12). In *sūrah Sad*, Allah (swt) said: “(David) said: “He has undoubtedly wronged thee in demanding thy (single) ewe to be added to his (flock of) ewes: truly many are the Partners (in business) who wrong each other: not so do those who believe and work deeds of righteousness and how few are they?”... And David gathered that We had tried him: he asked forgiveness of his Lord fell down bowing (in prostration) and turned (to Allah in repentance)” (as-Sad: 24).

Abu Hurayrah r.a. narrated from Prophet Muhammad (pbuh) that Allah (swt) said in *Hadīth Qudsi*: “I am the third of every two partners as long as neither one betrays the other. However, if one betrays the other, I leave their partnership”.²³ The Prophet (pbuh) found some people using partnership contract and approve it with several *hadīths*, such as: “Allah supports the partners as long as they do not betray one another”.²⁴ Furthermore, Muslim scholars are unanimous on the legality of *mushārah* while there is difference of opinions among them on the legality of *BBA*. To be more precise, there is no problem with *BBA* as described by Muslim scholars in the literature, as we will see in the next chapter. The problem lies in the *modus operandi* which is used for operation of *BBA* contract in case of Islamic banks in Malaysia. Therefore, the contract is legal but the mechanism of implementing it is suspicious.

On the other hand, when it comes to *mushārah mutanaqisah* partnership (MMP) contract, its legality is based on the following:²⁵

(a) *Scholars’ unanimous agreement*

Al-Masālih Al-Mursalah or *Al-Istislāh* (public interest) is guiding rule when it comes to this contract. Since, this mode of finance is serving the interests of people in general it is considered as legal and lawful from *Sharī’ah* point of view.

(b) *Islamic legal maxims*

Since there is no legal ruling within the *Sharī’ah* that prohibits this type of financial contract it is deemed as lawful based on legal maxims such as the following:

- (i) What is not prohibited is permissible;
- (ii) The initial state of things is permissible, unless it is clearly prohibited - **الأصل في الأشياء الإباحة**; and
- (iii) There can be neither danger nor any endangerment –

لا ضرر ولا ضرار.

²³ This hadith is recorded by Abu Dawud and Al-Hakim who validated its chain of narration. Cited in Wahbah Al-Zuhayli, *Financial Transactions in Islamic Jurisprudence*, translated from Arabic by Mahmoud A. El-Galam, (Damascus: Dar Al-Fikr, 2003), 1:448. See also: Nik Norzrul Thani et al., *Law and Practice*, 54 and Mustafa Omar, *Islamic Financial Contracts*, 28.

²⁴ Ibid.

²⁵ The following points are cited in Nik Norzrul Thani et al., *Law and Practice*, 56-57.

(c) *Avoidance of Ribā and Gharar*²⁶ (ambiguity)

Under this contract there is no violation of any principles of *Shari'ah*, i.e. it does not involve *ribā* or *gharar* with the regard to the goods being traded.

(d) *Fatwa*

During the First Conference of Islamic Banks, held in Dubai 1979, a fatwa was issued on the permissibility of *MMP* contract.

1.2.3 Economic Point of View

From economic point of view we have several issues arising on the topic. One is related to the demand for Islamic modes of finance and the other is related to the risk involved in these transactions that will be dealt on few levels.

As already stated above, Islamic banks may not be willing to transform their way of running the business since it creates less profit for them and is, therefore, less attractive from their point of view. This argument is misconceived. By implementing these new modes of finance (i.e. *MMP*, *ijārah* and *ijārah sukūk*) and gradually transferring their operations from credit-based to equity-based financing, Islamic banks and financial institutions will have a comparative advantage with regard to conventional banks. Since the financing through these modes is relatively cheaper for customers, it will lead to greater demand by them. This is simply the *Law of Demand* which says that once the price of a good/product goes down the quantity demanded for that good/product will increase and vice-versa. Therefore, by implementing these modes of finance Islamic banks will face increased demand for their financing which will, undoubtedly, lead to more profits to the Islamic banks. This extra profit earned through increased demand for the products of Islamic banks will offset some of the loss incurred by transferring funds from *BBA* mode of financing to the new ones.

When dealing with the banks in general and Islamic banks in particular the question of *ghurm* (risk, liability) is one of the main issues. Here we will address the risk of default and/or loss and the market risk.

(a) Risk of default and/or loss

This risk could be also classified under the credit risk, which is defined as “the potential that counterparty fails to meet its obligations in accordance with agreed terms.”²⁷ Some

²⁶ *Gharar* is defined as activities that have elements of uncertainty, ambiguity or deception. It is an element of deception either through ignorance of the goods, the price, or through faulty description of the goods, in which one or both parties stand to be deceived through ignorance of an essential element of exchange. As an example, gambling is a form of *gharar* because the gambler is ignorant of the result of the gamble. See International Organization of Securities Commission, *Islamic Capital Market Fact Finding Report*, Securities Commission, <http://www.sc.com.my/eng/html/icm/ICM-IOSCO_Fact%20finding%20Report.pdf> (accessed 15 January, 2007).

²⁷ Islamic Financial Services Board, *Exposure Draft No. 1: Guiding Principles of Risk Management for Institutions (Other Than Insurance Institutions) Offering Only Islamic Financial Services*, (n.p., 2005), 11.

would say that in case of *mushārah* it is more likely that the losses will be passed to the financier, i.e. banks or institutions. This loss will be further passed on to depositors, who, after being exposed constantly to the risk, will be reluctant to place their savings with the Islamic banks. This will result in funds to remain idle and could be used for the transactions outside the banking system.

This argument is also not valid. Before the financing takes place, the banks will study the feasibility and viability of the proposed projects. In addition to that, these banks will not constrain themselves to one *mushārah* contract only. They will have a lot of *mushārah* contracts and hence their portfolio will be diversified. For example, if a bank has 1,000 *mushārah* projects financed, after studying their feasibility, it is hard to believe that majority or all of these projects will result in a loss.

Furthermore, even if there is default, this risk of default is more manageable in case of *MMP* but it is hard to manage in case of *BBA*. The reason for that is simple. Under *MMP* contract, there are shares of both parties (i.e. Islamic bank and a client) which can be sold to third party at any time without breaching *Shari'ah* teachings. It is lawful since we are selling equities. However, in case of *BBA*, we are facing a problem. Here we cannot sell this contract since it would lead to the trading of debts, which is, if not prohibited, at least questionable practice on which scholars have different opinions.

(b) Market risk

This type of risk is defined as “the risk that arises from fluctuations in values in tradable, marketable or leaseable assets (including *sukūk*) and in off-balance sheet individual portfolios (for example restricted investment accounts).”²⁸ Again, we can see that this risk is more manageable with regard to *MMP*, but is difficult (if not possible) to manage under *BBA*. Volatility of *BBA* towards the movements of interest rate and inflation is well discussed by Saiful Azhar Rosly.²⁹ In order for *BBA* contract to be valid, the price has to be set at the time of sale and cannot be changed. Therefore, if there is change in the market conditions, interest rate or inflation this will affect the *BBA*. However, there is no mechanism that can help avoid this problem, unless we make floating-rate available for *BBA* contract. Unfortunately, it will not be viable since it would affect the underlying conditions for *BBA* contract such as predetermined price, and make that contract void. It is for this reason that we propose in this study the use of *mushārah mutanāqisah* and *ijārah* financial instruments whose structure is flexible

²⁸ Ibid., 20.

²⁹ For detailed discussion on interest rate and inflation volatility of *BBA* see: Saiful Azhar Rosly, *Critical Issues on Islamic Banking and Financial Markets*, (Kuala Lumpur: Dinamas, 2005), 121-123, 249-252, 265-268, 277-279, 309-312, 325-328, and 591-593.

and can address this problem effectively. These models could avoid the above-mentioned problem since their rates could be determined from time to time. This practice will not invalidate these contracts. In conclusion it can be said that market risk can be controlled more under the models offered in this paper and this will be helpful to the Islamic banks and financial institutions.

Therefore, it is believed that by implementing and using these new modes of financing, Islamic banks will for sure improve their market position and meet the needs of the customers as well as the goals of the Islamic banking and finance.

1.3 INFRASTRUCTURE OF ISLAMIC BANKS AND FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS

Infrastructure refers to roads, bridges, railways, water-ways, airways, and other forms of transportation and communications as well as water supplies, electricity and telephone. Financial institutions, health services and educations are also part of that infrastructure. All these things are prerequisites for both efficient market to function properly and development of that market in particular and society in general.

The same applies to Islamic banking and finance (IBF). It has its own infrastructure consisting of manpower, legal issues, banks and financial institutions, products and services rendered by these institutions, just to name a few.

“Experience of the last few decades has shown the inefficiency of creating an Islamic financial system by fiat without preparing the ground for its effective implementation. The fact is that without (i) an Islamic legal and administrative institutional infrastructure that protects investors’ rights, (ii) an effective institutional framework that ensures the validity and enforcement of contracts, (iii) a well-developed financial market that allows clear transmission of signals from the real sector of the economy to its financial system, and (iv) an efficient policy infrastructure that minimizes financial repression-keeping the rate of return administratively and artificially low-introduction of an Islamic financial system by fiat creates inefficiencies and imposes costs on the economy that nullify the beneficial effects of the financial system envisioned by Islam.”³⁰

In order for IBF to develop further we need to improve its infrastructure. This implies that: Firstly, we have to educate new experts in the field of IBF. Secondly, we have to support the development of new banks that are interested in implementing *Shari‘ah* based banking and finance.

³⁰ Abbas Mirakhor, “Vision of Islamic Finance,” *New Horizon*, no. 145, February 2005, 7.

This will bring more competition to the existing market, which will I believe, lead to the improvement of IBF. Thirdly, new products and services have to be invented which will meet the challenges of the modern world. This goal will be met only if due attention is paid to the Research and Development (R&D) activities related to the IMF.³¹ This study is meant to be one such research focusing on the last issue i.e. development of new products and services.

1.4 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of this study are manifolds. It is believed that this study will meet the following objectives:

- (i) Improving the position of the Islamic banks and financial institutions by providing them with new products/modes of finance.
- (ii) Islamic banks and financial institutions will gain a comparative advantage over their counterparts by implementing these new modes of finance.
- (iii) Borrowers of the funds, Muslims or non-Muslims, by using these modes of finance will be able to finance their asset acquisitions for relatively cheaper price and shorter time period.
- (iv) These products are more in line with *Shari'ah* than predominantly *bay' bithaman ājil* (BBA) mode of financing since they are based on profit-sharing and not instalment.
- (v) Finding out how much banking officials, academicians and students are aware of these relatively new products available for Islamic banks.

1.5 METHODS OF THE STUDY

In this paper, the author is trying to review the existing written material on the topic of asset acquisition in Islam using equity-based modes of finance. Throughout the paper attempt is made to compare these modes with BBA and conventional modes of finance. This paper is trying to develop theoretical platform for the implementation of these three models into current Islamic banks' operations. Materials related to the topic in particular and IBF in general will be collected from the available sources at the library of International Islamic University Malaysia (IIUM) and online databases that are available within the campus of IIUM. Moreover, the available articles from the daily newspapers, magazines, seminar/conference proceedings, unpublished works, research papers, theses and dissertations will also be used when available and appropriate. Besides that, the survey will be conducted by the author. The purpose of the survey is to find out how do the people, who are directly involved in the Islamic banking and finance industry, perceive these products. The findings of this survey will be used to support our theoretical foundations of this

³¹ "A progressive and Sustainable Islamic Financial System," *New Horizon*, no. 148, June 2005, 4.

study. Finally, the author will consult and interview people who are knowledgeable on the issues at focus and who are actively involved in developing financial derivatives for IBF.

1.6 OUTLINE OF THE STUDY

This study is divided into six chapters. This chapter, Chapter One, deals with introduction and gives the background of the study. Chapter Two will briefly discuss *bay' bithaman ājil (BBA)* mode of finance. Since our focus is on *mushārah mutanāqisah partnership (MMP)*, *ijārah* and *ijārah sukūk* and not on *BBA*, we will not dwell too much on the subject of *BBA*. However, for the sake of readers and for comparison purposes between *BBA* and other modes of finance it is necessary to give some highlights on *BBA* mode of finance.

Chapter Three elaborates *MMP* financing mode. Besides giving literature review³² at the beginning of the chapter, it will discuss characteristics and necessary conditions of *MMP* as well as theoretical explanation of the model. Chapter Four focuses on *ijārah sukūk* mode of financing. It will show how *ijārah sukūk* can replace some of government's funding (usually funded through interest-based loans) and what are necessary steps in order to facilitate the issuance of new *sukūk* in the future.

Chapter Five focuses on the survey. The results will show us how bank officers in Islamic banks see the development of new products for Islamic banking and finance. Their views will be elaborated and compared with the theoretical claims of the study. Finally, Chapter Six summarizes the findings and results of the paper. It gives final remarks on the topic and suggests further studies.

³² Note that the literature review will be given at the beginning of each chapter for that specific topic. The purpose of doing so is to help reader easily get the flow of the subject.

CHAPTER TWO

AL-BAY^c BITHAMAN ĀJIL (BBA) CONTRACT: REVIEW

2.0 INTRODUCTION

Stella Cox once stated, “Whilst we can begin this new millennium on a very positive note, there are ongoing inefficiencies that need to be addressed. We must nurture all that has been achieved to date whilst avoiding complacency and finding solutions to existing problems that will continue to strengthen Islamic economic and financial practice and maintain its growth curve.”³³ *Al-Bay^c Bithaman Ajil* (BBA) also known as *Bay^c Mu'ajjal*, which means credit sale or sale with delayed payment,³⁴ is a type of sale that is the most widely used by Islamic banks and financial institutions. BBA is also known as *bay^c muajjal* and *murābahah* in Pakistan and the Middle Eastern countries. In this chapter we will try to review the BBA mode of finance, its characteristics, its vulnerability, some objections and its implications. The purpose of this chapter is only to provide readers with necessary information about this mode of finance since we are going to compare it with MMP and *ijāra* financial techniques. Therefore, this chapter is mainly informative in nature and we do not intend to bring anything new into this model.

2.1 DEFINITION

Al-Bay^c Bithaman Ājil (BBA) originates from a contract called *murābahah*. Therefore it is important for us to first define *murābahah* as a contract. *Murābahah* simply means an increase or growth from the Arabic verb *rabaha* or *rabiha* (رَبَحَ) which also may imply profit.³⁵ In other words *murābahah* is a ‘cost-plus financing’,³⁶ ‘mark-up sale’³⁷ or resale based on profit margin above the cost. This is a sale contract whereby a product is sold at a price equivalent to the cost price of that product plus profit margin. For example, if the cost price of a product is RM1,000 and the profit margin is RM200, then the price of that product, under *murābahah* principle, would be RM1,200.

³³ Cited in “Islamic Banking: A Long Journey Ahead”, *New Horizon*, no. 104, November 2000, p. 2.

³⁴ Abdul Sattar Abu Ghuddah, *Al-Bay^c Al-Mu'ajjal*, (Jeddah: Islamic Research and Training Institute, 2nd edn., 2003), Eminent Scholars' Lectures Series No. 16, 15.

³⁵ The verb رَبَحَ or رَبِحَ (*rabaha* or *rabiha*) means to gain, profit, to win while رِبْحٌ (*ribh*) pl. أَرْبَاحٌ (*arbāh*) means gain, profit, benefit, interest; pl. proceeds, returns, revenues, dividends, etc. See: Hans Wehr, *A Dictionary of Modern Written Arabic*, edited by J. Milton Cowan (3rd Printing), (Beirut: Librairie Du Liban, 1980), 321.

³⁶ Thani, Nik Norzrul, Mohamed Ridza Mohamed Abdullah & Megat Hizaini Hassan, *Law and Practice of Islamic Banking and Finance*, (Petaling Jaya: Sweet & Maxwell Asia, 2003) 57.

³⁷ Rosly, *Critical Issues*, 87.

Murābahah contract, in case of Islamic banks in Malaysia, is associated with credit sale. However, this association is not fully correct. It is worthy to note that there are two types of *murābahah*. There are as follows:³⁸

- i) Cash *murābahah* – this is a sale contract whereby a product is sold at the price equal to the cost price and a profit margin and the payment is settled on cash basis.
- ii) Credit *murābahah* – in this case it is a credit sale contract. Here, the price is equal to the price of cash *murābahah* plus premium that is added over the profit margin. This reflects time value of money.³⁹

In short, if the payment is done in lump sum and it is a short-term credit *murābahah*, then it is simply called *murābahah*. On the other hand, *al-bay^c bithaman ājil* (BBA) is used to indicate long-term credit *murābahah*. This division is applied in case of Malaysia.⁴⁰

Literal meaning of *al-bay^c bithaman ājil* is as follows: *al-bay^c* (البيع) equals sale, *thaman* (ثمن) equals price, *ājil* (آجل) equal deferment. BBA is a sale and not a loan, but this is the sale with deferred payment.⁴¹ "It is an extension of the *murābahah* (cost plus) contract, whereby the commodity exchanged is 'delivered' immediately but the sale price (with profit) is paid in instalments, over a long period (the *murābahah* itself being generally for short periods)."⁴² *Al-bay^c bithaman ājil* (BBA) means a sale with deferred payments.⁴³ Muhammad Taqi Usmani defines it as, "[a] sale in which the parties agree that the payment of price shall be deferred..."⁴⁴ According to Mustafa Omar, "BBA is a branch of *Murābahah* where the payment of *Murābahah* is deferred to a certain date agreed upon by both parties."⁴⁵ It could be also defined as "... a variant of the concept of *Murābahah*, whereby the borrower is allowed to defer settlement of the payment for the goods purchased within the period, and in the manner, determined and agreed on by both parties."⁴⁶ Even

³⁸ Ibid., 87-88.

³⁹ There are different views regarding the prohibition of time value of money. For more information on the issue of Time Value of Money from an Islamic perspective please see Saiful Azhar Rosly, *Critical Issues*, 41-43. See also Syed Hamed Abdul Rahman Alkaff, *Does Islam Assign Any Value Weight to Time Factor in Economic and Financial Transactions?*, (Karachi: Islamic Research Academy, 1986). On the issue of opportunity cost of money see, Rauf Ahmed Azhar, "A Theory of Optimal Investment Decision in an Islamic Economy", in *Lectures on Islamic Economics*, edited by Ausaf Ahmad and Kazim Raza Awan (Jeddah: Islamic Research and Training Institute, 1992), 238-239.

⁴⁰ Rosly, *Critical Issues*, 88.

⁴¹ Rosly, *Critical Issues*, 88. See also: M. Umer Chapra, *Towards a Just Monetary system: A Discussion of Money, Banking and Monetary Policy in the Light of Islamic Teachings*, (London: The Islamic Foundation, 1985) 169.

⁴² Meeera and Dzuljastri, "Islamic Home Financing," 7.

⁴³ Sattar, *Al-Bay^c Al-Mu'ajjal*, 15.

⁴⁴ M.T. Usmani, *An Introduction to Islamic Finance*, 40.

⁴⁵ M.O. Mohamed, *Islamic Financial Contracts (Module 2)*, 4. Here, *italics* are ours for emphasis.

⁴⁶ Sudin Haron, Norafifah Ahmad and Sandra L. Planisek, "Bank Patronage Factors of Muslim and Non-Muslim Customers", *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, vol. 12, no. 1 (1994): 32.

though it is not a spot sale, still it is one form of trading and commerce that is allowed by the Holy *Qur'an*:

Those who devour usury will not stand except as stands one whom the Evil One by his touch hath driven to madness. That is because they say: "Trade is like usury but Allah hath permitted trade and forbidden usury. Those who after receiving direction from their Lord desist shall be pardoned for the past; their case is for Allah (to judge); but those who repeat (the offence) are companions of the fire: they will abide therein (for ever). (Al-Baqarah, 2:275)

In this regard, BBA contract is a sub-contract of *murābahah* whereby the settlement of the price is made based on instalments. Under this contract the delivery of the goods is taking place on the spot while the price, cost plus profit margin, is paid in instalments.⁴⁷ Originally, *murābahah* as well as BBA are two particular types of sale and not modes of financing.⁴⁸ However, *murābahah* and BBA contracts can be classified as debt based modes of financing. The reason for this kind of classification lies in the fact that financing under these modes is a debt in nature and that user of the funds has to pay full amount of financing.⁴⁹ It is also considered as, "...a sort of credit sale for profit."⁵⁰

The BBA is a sale contract whereby the buyer has an option to defer the payment of the goods. This deferred price is determined based on the cost of the goods plus profit margin. The cost as well as the additional profit has to be stated in the contract. Under this contract, an Islamic bank buys a commodity, property or asset and sells it to a customer at agreed price. This price is the original price of that asset plus the profit margin that can be specific or in percentage terms. The agreed price is to be paid by the customer on a deferred basis or on instalments.

2.2 BASIC FEATURES OF BBA

Some of the basic features of BBA contract are mentioned by Muhammad Taqi Usmani in his book *An Introduction to Islamic Finance*. These features are as follows:⁵¹

- a) It is a sale with deferred payment.
- b) The due date of payment has to be fixed clearly for a BBA contract to be a valid one.

⁴⁷ Meeera and Dzuljastri, "Islamic Home Financing," 7.

⁴⁸ M.T. Usmani, *An Introduction to Islamic Finance*, 37 and 41.

⁴⁹ Boualem Bendjilali, *Assessment of the Practice of Islamic Financial Instruments*, (Jeddah: Islamic Research and Training Institute, 1996), Research Paper No. 35, 43.

⁵⁰ Tajul Islam, "Mechanics of Islamic Banking", in *Islamic Banking: How Far Have We Gone?*, edited by A.H. Pramanik, (IIUM: Research Centre, 2006), 139.

⁵¹ Muhammad Taqi Usmani, *An Introduction to Islamic Finance*, 40.

- c) The specification of the due date can be with reference to the exact future date or by specifying period, for example six months, one year, etc. If the due date is not clearly stated the sale is void.
- d) If the agreed period is fixed for, let say, three months then it will commence from the time of delivery – unless otherwise agreed.
- e) The deferred price may be higher than the original/cash price. However, this price has to be fixed at the time of sale taking place.
- f) Once fixed, price can not be either increased or decreased.
- g) To avoid the default by the buyer and in order to pressurize him to pay on time, the buyer may be asked to donate some amount for a charity in case he defaults. This will not be used as the income of the seller, but he (the seller) will use it for charitable purposes on behalf of the buyer.

The question may be raised here: Can this be justified by *Shari'ah*? Is it allowed to force someone to give charity? How different it will be from ordinary loan defaulters – from the defaulter's point of view?

- h) In case of the sale on instalments, the condition on the buyer can be put forward by the seller that the remaining instalments will be due immediately if the buyer defaults on any instalment.

This may raise some logical question as well. If a client defaulted on the instalment, how can we force him to pay the remaining of the outstanding instalments? This is especially the case if he/she defaulted due to the bankruptcy. If he was unable to pay his/her due instalment how will he/she be able to pay the rest?

- i) For security reasons, the seller may ask the buyer to provide him with collateral, mortgage or any of his existing assets.
- j) The seller can also ask the buyer to sign a promissory note or a bill of exchange. However, this note or a bill of exchange cannot be sold to a third party at a price different from its face value.

2.3 DETERMINATION OF THE PRICE

Some argue that in order to determine the price of BBA facility a seller (i.e. Islamic bank) can take into consideration whatever he/she wants, because there is no *Shari'ah* rule how the price is determined for BBA. However, Islam does not allow exploitation of others either. Hence, there should be a guiding principle for pricing a product. Article 1347⁵² of the *Majallah* reads: “*The right*

⁵² Cited in Mahmood Sanusi, “The Application of *al-Qawā'id al-Fiqhiyyah* in the Area of Islamic Economics,” paper presented at IIUM International Conference on Islamic Banking and Finance (IICiBF

to gain is obtained sometimes through the introduction of capital, sometimes through the introduction of work and sometimes, through introduction of responsibility (liability).” In the following article (Article 1348) it says that, “When there is no introduction of one of the abovementioned three things, the right to gain does not exist.”⁵³ It is for these reasons that Mahmood Sanusi claims that there is a limit to the profit in Islam. According to him, this limit is one-third and any profit that is more than one-third or one-sixth of the original price is illegitimate profit.⁵⁴

However, according to some Muslim scholars with mutual consent of both parties (i.e. seller and buyer) the profit above this is considered as legitimate profit.⁵⁵ The price can be calculated either through lump-sum or percentage profit margins. Ibn Mas'ūd (r.a.) made a ruling that it is allowed to declare lump-sum or percentage profit margins.⁵⁶ Furthermore, all schools of *fiqh*, Hanafī, Mālikī, Shāfi'ī and Hanbalī, allowed that the profit margin, in case of *murābahah*, can be expressed either in lump-sum or in percentage.⁵⁷

Nothing in Islamic law dictates how the price for such a sale is determined; it is simply whatever the parties agree upon. Therefore, nothing prevents the seller from linking the sale price to the period of time for which credit is extended, and Islamic institutions in fact do so, employing formulae using LIBOR and other economic indicators. In their actual documentation, however, banks usually avoid mentioning any such procedure for fixing the price, since it is easily mistaken for a charge of interest.⁵⁸

Using the LIBOR as benchmark is definitely something that should be avoided. Why do we need LIBOR after all? Does it mean that the interest rate indirectly affects the BBA sale? If that is the case then how can we claim its *Islamicity* and to what extent it is truly *Shari'ah* compliant. These questions have to be addressed and another benchmark, independent from the interest-based benchmarks such as LIBOR, should be used for Islamic financial instruments.

Another issue related to the BBA sale is that of time factor. Observing the operation of Islamic banks, we will find that cash sale is always lower than credit sale, i.e. cash *murābahah* and

2007): *Research and Development: The Bridges between Ideals and Realities*, organized by IIUM Institute of Islamic Banking & Finance (IICiBF), 23-25 April, 2007, Crown Plaza Mutiara Hotel, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, 12.

⁵³ Cited in *ibid.*

⁵⁴ *Ibid.*, 15.

⁵⁵ See *Ibid.*

⁵⁶ Mahmoud Amin El-Gamal, *A Basic Guide to Contemporary Islamic Banking and Finance*, (Houston: Rice University, 2000), 10. Available at: <URL: <http://www.nubank.com/islamic/primer.pdf>>.

⁵⁷ Abdul Sattar, *Al-Bay' Al-Mu'ajjal*, 26-27. See also: M. T. Usmani, *An Introduction to Islamic Finance*, 41.

⁵⁸ Vogel and Hayes, *Islamic Law and Finance*, 139.

bay^c muajjal respectively. Now, why is the price of cash *murābahah* lower than the price of credit *murābahah*? For financing purposes it is almost always that the latter is used. Many people object its price determination and link it to the interest rate charged by conventional banks. Usmani believes that as cash *murābahah* can be priced over the cost by any amount, in similar way the credit *murābahah* can be charged higher. According to all the four schools of *fiqh* and the majority of the Muslim jurists, it is allowed for seller to set the price of a credit sale higher than the price for a cash sale. However it is not allowed to set many prices, for example to set two or three or even more prices for one transaction, since it will lead to uncertainty which makes the contract void.⁵⁹

2.4 OVERDEPENDENCE OF ISLAMIC BANKS ON BBA FINANCING

Many authors are worried about the Islamic banks. The reason for this concern lies in overdependence of Islamic banks on BBA financing. "...Islamic banking has come under increasing criticism, from its own ranks and from the public, for its heavy reliance on synthetic *murābahas*."⁶⁰ The minimum and maximum proportions in Islamic banks occupied by BBA and its variants are 45% and 93%.⁶¹ This inclination of Islamic banks towards BBA financing, according to Ismail Bacha Obiyathullah, comes from necessity and not preference.⁶² He further argues that this trend is worrisome. There are two reasons for this:⁶³

- i) Firstly, this overemphasis of Islamic banks on short-term financing will push Islamic banks towards periphery of the financial system;
- ii) The second reason is related with social needs. It is used to finance the purchase of already produced goods and as such it does not create additional capital.

Why do Islamic banks mainly rely on these two trading modes, *murābahah* and *al-bay^c bithaman ājil*? Several scholars gave their reasons and opinions trying to answer this question. We will try to mention some of these answers in the following. According to Muhammad Anwar there are two explanations for that.⁶⁴ Firstly, they are complying with the commands of the Holy *Qur'an* in verses already stated above (2:275 and 4:29). Secondly, it is easy for Islamic banks to, "charge time value of money in the name of a profit margin on their financing in place of the interest charged by the conventional banks." Furthermore, Islamic banks are nothing more than small

⁵⁹ M. T. Usmani, *An Introduction to Islamic Finance*, 44-48.

⁶⁰ Vogel and Hayes, *Islamic Law and Finance*, 143.

⁶¹ Muhammad Anwar, "Islamicity of Islamic Banking Practices", 356.

⁶² Ismail Bacha Obiyathullah, "Conventional versus Mudaraba Financing", 177.

⁶³ *Ibid.*, 177. See also Rosly, *Critical Issues*, 297.

⁶⁴ Muhammad Anwar, "Islamicity of Islamic Banking Practices", 359.

islands in the sea of *ribā*-based banking. This is also one of the reasons why Islamic banks heavily rely on fixed return facilities such as *murābahah*, BBA and the like.⁶⁵

Vogel and Hayes mention some characteristics of *murābahah* which made it most popular mode of finance of Islamic banks. *Murābahah* - according to them - can be used for short-term as well as intermediate-term financing.⁶⁶ Through *murābahah* financing Islamic banks create an unconditional debt in a fixed amount that can be easily collateralized or secured. Furthermore, there is no need to monitor the client's business and honesty as is the case with *mushārakah*. Meanwhile, it mimics conventional interest-based lending, being highly liquid and bearing minimum risks.⁶⁷

Table 2.1
Modes of Islamic Finance in Malaysia
(% share of total)

<i>Mode of Finance</i>	<i>2001</i>	<i>2002</i>	<i>2003</i>	<i>2004</i>	<i>2005</i>
<i>Al-Bay^c Bithaman Ajil</i>	48.3	49.1	47.7	49.9	40.7
<i>Al-Ijāra</i>	4.3	3	1.4	24	31.6
<i>Al-Ijāra Thumma Al-Bay^c</i>	22.2	23.3	27.6	-	-
<i>Al-Istisna'</i>	0.9	1.3	0.6	1.2	0.9
<i>Mudharaba & Mushāraka</i>	1.4	0.7	0.5	0.5	0.3
<i>Murābahah</i>	7	7.3	6.2	7	6.9
Other Islamic Contracts	15.9	15.3	16	17.4	19.6
Total	100	100	100	100	100

Source: Bank Negara Annual Report (various issues)

Both *murābahah* and *al-bay^c bithaman ājil* are fixed-rate instruments used by Islamic banks mostly for short-term financing requirements of trade, industry, agriculture etc.⁶⁸ These extravagant usage of fixed-rate-short-term type of financial instruments by Islamic banks are seen by some as "'deviation' from the Islamic ideal"⁶⁹ – i.e. profit and loss sharing (PLS) instruments. Furthermore,

⁶⁵ Manzoor Ali, "Islamic Banking and Finance in Theory and Practice", in *Lectures on Islamic Economics*, edited by Ausaf Ahmad and Kazim Raza Awan (Jeddah: Islamic Research and Training Institute, 1992), 351.

⁶⁶ Vogel and Hayes, *Islamic Law and Finance*, 212 and 240.

⁶⁷ *Ibid.*, 240.

⁶⁸ Ziauddin Ahmad, "Islamic Financial Institutions and Their Contribution to Trade and Development" in *International Economic Relations from Islamic Perspectives*, edited by M.A. Mannan, Monzer Kahf and Ausaf Ahmad (Jeddah: Islamic Research and Training Institute, 1992), 268.

⁶⁹ S.N.H. Naqvi, Islamic Banking: An Evaluation, *IIUM Journal of Economics and Management*, vol. 8, no. 1 (2000): 41.

this excessive reliance of Islamic banks on fixed return modes may result in loss of their comparative advantage in the long-run. It is for these reasons that scholars have been warning us about this malady of Islamic banks, saying that Islamic banks will, "lose ground against conventional banks as they are also offering products with similar, if not the same, characteristics. In order to gain competitive advantage and product differentiation, Islamic banks had better evolve mechanisms for successful application of variable returns modes".⁷⁰ The above mentioned practice of Islamic banks will lead them to assimilation with conventional banks. In other words, if Islamic banks continue current practices it will lead to the convergence of Islamic banks into conventional ones. This is very clear from the citation mentioned above.

Until and unless Islamic banks and financial institutions change this approach, they will remain in the shadows of the conventional financial system. In this regard Muhammad Anwar says:

Proper application of the Islamic modes would have set Islamic Banks apart from the conventional banks, but this did not happen in reality because the Islamic banks manipulated the trading modes in ways that retained their identity as lenders rather than traders and entrepreneurs. Therefore, there ought to be some measures to ensure that Islamic banks are transformed from the traditional lenders to the Islamic entrepreneurs. Otherwise, the question regarding the Islamicity of their operation... would continue to confuse the Muslim mind.⁷¹

2.5 *SHARĪAH* RULINGS ON BBA

Even though, the Middle East *‘ulama* do not accept and practice BBA as a mode of financing still it is approved by majority of Muslim scholars. Although the BBA mechanism is a *Sharī‘ah* approved, still we can find some implementations of BBA and *murābahah* which are "with or without "full" *Sharī‘ah* compliance" – says Obiyathullah.⁷²

In principle, the BBA is allowed by *Sharī‘ah*.⁷³ Its permissibility is found in *Al-Qur‘an*, *Sunnah* and *Ijmā‘*. Those who support BBA contract refer to the verse in *sūrah al-Baqarah* where Allah (swt) says: "...Allah hath permitted trade and forbidden usury." (Al-Baqarah, 2:275). Ahmad, Abu Dāwūd and al-Dāraqutnī narrated *hadīth* where the Prophet (pbuh) entrusted *‘Abdullah* ibn *‘Umar* (ra) with responsibility of preparing the army for a military expedition. Accordingly, *‘Abdullah* bought mounts by offering to pay almost double the price for a single mount.

⁷⁰ Abdullah M. Noman "Imperatives of Financial Innovation for Islamic Banks", *International Journal of Islamic Financial Services*, vol. 4, no. 3 (2002). Available at <<http://islamic-finance.net/Journals/Journal15/vol4no3art1.pdf>> (accessed 16 January, 2007).

⁷¹ Muhammad Anwar, "Islamicity of Islamic Banking Practices", 357.

⁷² Mohammed Obaidullah, *Islamic Financial Services*, (Jeddah: Islamic Economics Research Center, King Abdulaziz University, 2005), 68.

⁷³ Abdul Sattar, *Al-Bay‘ Al-Mu‘ajjal*, 17.

روى عن عبدالله ابن عمروان النبي صلى الله عليه وسلم أمره ان يجهز جيشاً فكان يشتري
البعير بالبعيرين إلى أجل.⁷⁴

According to the *Mejelle*, the *instalment* sale is good.⁷⁵ It is believed that the *Shari'ah* allows this type of trade since there is need for it by people.⁷⁶ Everything is permissible in principle unless otherwise stated in sources of *Shari'ah* (i.e. the *Qur'an*, *Sunnah*, *Ijmā'* and *Qiyās*). This is based on well known legal maxim which states that everything, every contract is permissible or in Arabic,

الأصل في الأشياء الإباحة

The Council of the Islamic *Fiqh* Academy, during its sixth and seventh session held in Jeddah, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia agreed on the permissibility of instalment sale (i.e. *Al-Bay' Al-Mu'ajjal*). It says that it is allowed to have different prices for cash and instalment sale. However, once contract is signed there should be only one price whether the cash or instalment price.⁷⁷ Few scholars disagreed with the permissibility of BBA. Some of them are Zaynul 'Ābidīn 'Alī bin al-Husain, Imam Yahya, Ustaz 'Abdul Rahman 'Abdul Khaliq and Ustaz Nizam al-Dīn 'Abdul Hamīd.⁷⁸

Shaykh Ahmad Kutty, Dr. Yusuf Al-Qaradawi and Dr. Monzer Kahf,⁷⁹ among other contemporary scholars, allowed instalment sale. In their views it is a necessity for the people and without allowing the instalment sale it would put the hardship on them in performing their everyday life activities which is in contrary to the Qur'anic text where it says:

شَهْرُ رَمَضَانَ الَّذِي أُنزِلَ فِيهِ الْقُرْآنُ هُدًى لِّلنَّاسِ وَبَيِّنَاتٍ مِّنَ الْهُدَى وَالْفُرْقَانِ فَمَن شَهِدَ مِنْكُمُ الشَّهْرَ
فَلْيَصُمْهُ وَمَن كَانَ مَرِيضًا أَوْ عَلَى سَفَرٍ فَعِدَّةٌ مِّنْ أَيَّامٍ أُخَرَ يُرِيدُ اللَّهُ بِكُمُ الْيُسْرَ وَلَا يُرِيدُ بِكُمُ الْعُسْرَ
وَلِتُكْمِلُوا الْعِدَّةَ وَلِتُكَبِّرُوا اللَّهَ عَلَى مَا هَدَاكُمْ وَلَعَلَّكُمْ تَشْكُرُونَ (البقرة، 185)

Ramadan is the (month) in which was sent down the Qur'an as a guide to mankind also clear (Signs) for guidance and judgment (between right and wrong). So everyone of you who is present (at his home) during that month should spend it in fasting but if anyone is ill or on a journey the prescribed period (should be made up) by days later. Allah intends every facility for you He does not want to put you to difficulties. (He wants you) to complete the prescribed period and to glorify Him in

⁷⁴ Cited in Abdul Sattar, *Al-Bay' Al-Mu'ajjal*, 22.

⁷⁵ S.A. Rahman, *The Mejelle*, translated from Turkish by C.R. Tyser, D.G. Demetriades and Ismail Haqqi Effendi (Lahore: Law Publishing Company, 1967), 35-36.

⁷⁶ Abdul Sattar, *Al-Bay' Al-Mu'ajjal*, 18.

⁷⁷ Resolution No. (51/2/6) of Sixth Session and Resolution No. (64/2/7) of Seventh Session are held between 14-20 March, 1990 and 9-14 May, 1992 respectively. See: The OIC Islamic *Fiqh* Academy, *Resolutions and Recommendations of the Council of the Islamic Fiqh Academy: 1985-2000 – Jeddah*, (Jeddah: Islamic Economics Research Center, 2000), 103 and 135.

⁷⁸ See Abdul Sattar, *Al-Bay' Al-Mu'ajjal*, 21.

⁷⁹ Their *fatwas* on the issue of instalment sale can be found at <<http://www.islamonline.net>>.

that He has guided you; and perchance ye shall be grateful. (Al-Qur'an, al-Baqarah: 185).

وَجَاهِدُوا فِي اللَّهِ حَقَّ جِهَادِهِ هُوَ اجْتَبَاكُمْ وَمَا جَعَلَ عَلَيْكُمْ فِي الدِّينِ مِنْ حَرَجٍ مِّلَّةَ أَبِيكُمْ إِبْرَاهِيمَ هُوَ سَمَّاكُمُ الْمُسْلِمِينَ مِنْ قَبْلُ وَفِي هَذَا لِيَكُونَ الرَّسُولُ شَهِيدًا عَلَيْكُمْ وَتَكُونُوا شُهَدَاءَ عَلَى النَّاسِ فَأَقِيمُوا الصَّلَاةَ وَآتُوا الزَّكَاةَ وَاعْتَصِمُوا بِاللَّهِ هُوَ مَوْلَاكُمْ فَنِعْمَ الْمَوْلَى وَنِعْمَ النَّصِيرُ (الحج، 78)

And strive in His cause as ye ought to strive (with sincerity and under discipline): He has chosen you and has imposed no difficulties on you in religion; it is the cult of your father Abraham. It is He Who has named you Muslims both before and in this (Revelation); that the Apostle may be a witness for you and ye be witnesses for mankind! So establish regular Prayer give regular Charity and hold fast to Allah! He is your Protector the Best to protect and the Best to help! (Al-Qur'an, al-Hajj: 78).

2.6 HOW DOES IT WORK? – MECHANISM OF BBA

Since *ribā* is prohibited by the Holy *Qur'an*, Islamic banks in Malaysia have introduced *al-bay' bithaman ājil* (BBA) to cater the needs of Muslim clients. Islamic banks are not supposed to provide ordinary offering loans. Instead Islamic bank "...*theoretically* purchases the house from the developer at market price (i.e. cost price) and sells it to the customer at a mark-up price."⁸⁰ However, as the citation says, this is done only "*theoretically*" while it is in fact done using buy-back (*bay' al-inah*) transaction.

Now let us see what happens under the conventional banking. Let us assume that a customer, Ahmad, wants to buy a house which costs RM200,000. He would approach the developer and sign a sale and purchase agreement (S&P) and pay, let's say, 20 percent of the whole amount, i.e. RM40,000. Then he would approach a bank, say bank A, for the financing of the rest. If the bank A approves the loan, Ahmad would get RM160,000 loan and pay monthly instalment of RM1,146.29⁸¹ for next 20 years (i.e. 240 instalments assuming that annual interest rate is 6%) to the bank. The very same house will be used as collateral. This will be done through the contract called deeds of assignment/charge. Final amount payable to the bank would be RM275,109.60.⁸²

⁸⁰ Rosly, *Critical Issues*, 122. Here, the *italics* is ours for emphasis.

⁸¹ Computed using the standard formula for present value of annuities, i.e. $PV = \frac{Pmt}{i} \left[1 - \frac{1}{(1+i)^n} \right]$ which

gives $Pmt = \frac{i(1+i)^n PV}{(1+i)^n - 1}$.

⁸² Found by $RM1146.29 \times 240 = RM275,109.60$.

Therefore, the profit to the bank would be RM115,109.60.⁸³ In short, under the conventional banking system the financing consists of two contracts:

- a) Contract of loan between the bank and Mr. Ahmad, and
- b) Deeds of Assignment/Charge.⁸⁴

However, the case with Islamic banks is a bit complicated. Mr. Ahmad is required to buy the property from a developer, i.e. to pay down payment. By doing so he becomes a beneficiary owner of that property. Now the question arises: How can Islamic bank sell that product to Mr. Ahmad when it does not possess it at the first place? The original or the pure BBA is presented in the Figure 2.1 below. This figure shows how BBA *should be* implemented. Firstly, Mr. Ahmad identifies the property he wishes to buy. Then he approaches the bank and informs it about his intention. Secondly, the bank purchases the property from developer. Thirdly, the bank sells the property to Mr. Ahmad who gets delivery of the property on the spot. Finally, Mr. Ahmad repays the deferred price to the bank on the instalment basis throughout the agreed period.

Figure 2.1: Real *al-bay' bithaman ājil*

The figure 2.1 above shows how BBA financing should look like. However, this is not the way it is done in Malaysian Islamic banks currently. Instead, BBA financing is implemented in the following way. Mr. Ahmad, as is the case in conventional banking, will pay down payment (i.e. RM40,000 or 20 percent) and sign sales and purchase (S&P) agreement. Now, the bank, in order to secure the ownership (*milkiyyah*), will purchase that asset from Mr. Ahmad through the Property

⁸³ Found by $RM275,109.60 - RM160,000 = RM115,109.60$.

⁸⁴ Rosly, *Critical Issues*, 89.

Purchase Agreement (PPA). In fact, this purchase takes place only on the papers since there is no real transfer of the ownership as there is no evidence registration and stamp duty. Now, note that the bank will purchase that asset from Mr. Ahmad for the remaining amount of money needed to buy whole house (i.e. RM160,000). Through the introduction of PPA the bank gets the rights over the asset and becomes the legal owner of it. Once the PPA is executed, the bank will sell the asset back to Mr. Ahmad at the deferred price. This deferred price or the selling price would be the cost price plus profit margin. For calculating profit margin, Islamic banks, without mentioning it, use some interest rate benchmark such as LIBOR. Therefore, the annual profit rate (APR) of Islamic banks would be very much close (if not the same) to the annual interest rate of conventional banks. If the APR and contracting period are the same as the annual interest rate and period in the above example of conventional loan, then the monthly instalment will be the same as well, i.e. RM1,146.29. This is illustrated in the Figure 2.2 below.

Figure 2.2: Actual *al- bay' bithaman ājil*

In brief, BBA sale contract consist of the followings:

- Property Purchase Agreement (PPA): Bank purchases the asset from customer.
- Property Sale Agreement (PSA): Bank sells the asset to the customer at BBA price, i.e. cost plus profit margin.
- Deeds of Assignment/Charge: The asset is withheld as collateral by the bank.⁸⁵

⁸⁵ Rosly, *Critical Issues*, 91.

2.7 RISKS RELATED TO BBA

Since the BBA financing technique is largely used by Islamic banks it is worthy to note what are the risks related to the BBA. Deferred sale or *al-bay' bithaman ājil* is mainly faced with following risks:⁸⁶

- a. Credit risk
- b. Liquidity risk
- c. Rate of return risk

The credit risk faced by Islamic banks can be treated the same way the conventional banks threat their credit risk. This is done by taking collateral, mortgage and guarantees to protect their investments.⁸⁷ The deferred price in BBA contract represents monetary debt which cannot be sold for cash⁸⁸ except at face value.⁸⁹ Consequently, the Islamic bank can face liquidity problem. This type of risk is presently low (in fact in most cases there is excess liquidity due to the lack of financial instruments) due to non-availability of *Sharī'ah*-compatible investment opportunities – according to Chapra and Khan – but it may become a problem in the future.⁹⁰ Two solutions are available for Islamic banks dealing with liquidity risk – according to Al-Suwailem. The Islamic banks can either exchange the debt for commodity at discounted value - this is allowed according to Mālikī school and Ibn Taymiyyah – or mix the debt with real assets into one portfolio where debt will not exceed more than 50% and then securitize the portfolio.⁹¹ This type of the risk could be a great challenge to Islamic banks since there is no well developed Islamic money market from where Islamic banks can borrow the funds.⁹² When it comes to the rate of return risk, it is obvious that once determined the price cannot be changed in BBA contract. As result, both parties are exposed to this risk when market rate changes, especially in long term debt financing.⁹³

2.8 MAQĀSID AL-SHARĪ'AH, QAWĀ'ID AL-FIQH AND BBA

Maqāsid al-Sharī'ah as a topic is a wide area that goes beyond the scope of this research. Nevertheless, we would like to analyze its relevance to the BBA and the other contracts involved in this research. *Maqāsid al-Sharī'ah* or objectives of *Sharī'ah*, also known as *maslaha* (pl. *masālih* -

⁸⁶ Sami Al-Suwailem, *Hedging in Islamic Finance*, (Jeddah: Islamic Research and Training Institute (IRTI), 2006), Occasional Paper No. 10, 125.

⁸⁷ Al-Suwailem, *Hedging in Islamic Finance*, 125.

⁸⁸ Al-Suwailem, *Hedging in Islamic Finance*, 126.

⁸⁹ T. Khan and Habib Ahmed, *Risk Management: An Analysis of Issues in Islamic Financial Industry*, (Jeddah: Islamic Research and Training Institute (IRTI), 2001), Occasional Paper No. 5, 53.

⁹⁰ M.U. Chapra and T. Khan, *Regulation and Supervision of Islamic Banks*, (Jeddah: Islamic Research and Training Institute (IRTI), 2000), Occasional Paper No. 3, 56.

⁹¹ Al-Suwailem, *Hedging in Islamic Finance*, 126.

⁹² Habib Ahmed, *A Microeconomic Model of an Islamic Bank*, (Jeddah: Islamic Research and Training Institute (IRTI), 2002), Research Paper No. 59, 30.

⁹³ Al-Suwailem, *Hedging in Islamic Finance*, 126-127.

benefits), are found in Qur'an, *Sunnah* and *ijma'*. However, the due attention to this topic was given only in eleventh century by al-Ghazālī (451-505H-1055-1111) and later on by Shātībī (d.790/1388). These two scholars are the towering figures when it comes to this subject.⁹⁴ Here, we are concerned with the legal maxims that are related to the transactions or *fiqh mu'āmalāt* and which should be observed when undertaking any transaction.

The Holy Qur'an is full of references on *maslaha* (benefits).⁹⁵

إِنَّ اللَّهَ يَأْمُرُ بِالْعَدْلِ وَالْإِحْسَانِ وَإِيتَاءِ ذِي الْقُرْبَىٰ وَيَنْهَىٰ عَنِ الْفَحْشَاءِ وَالْمُنْكَرِ وَالْبَغْيِ يَعِظُكُمْ لَعَلَّكُمْ تَذَكَّرُونَ (النحل, 90)

Allah commands justice the doing of good and liberality to kith and kin and He forbids all shameful deeds and injustice and rebellion: He instructs you that ye may receive admonition. (Al-Qur'an, an-Nahl: 90).

We will also find many *āyāt* (plural of *āyah* – verse) in which Allah (swt) mentions easiness and leniency while condemning and discouraging the harshness and toughness. He (swt) says:

يُرِيدُ اللَّهُ بِكُمُ الْيُسْرَ وَلَا يُرِيدُ بِكُمُ الْعُسْرَ وَلِتُكْمِلُوا أَلْعَدَّةَ وَلِتُكَبِّرُوا اللَّهَ عَلَىٰ مَا هَدَاكُمْ وَلَعَلَّكُمْ تَشْكُرُونَ (البقرة, 185)

...Allah intends every facility for you He does not want to put you to difficulties...(Al-Qur'an, al-Baqarah: 185).

It will be suffice for us to cite the famous statement by al-Ghazālī, referring to the *maqāsid al-Sharī'ah*, when he says:

The objective of the *Sharī'ah* is to promote the welfare of human beings, which lies in safeguarding their faith, their life, their intellect, their posterity, and their wealth. Whatever ensures the safeguard of these five fundamentals serves public interest and is desirable.⁹⁶

Muslim scholars classified *maqāsid al-Sharī'ah* into three main categories: the *darūriyyāt* (the essentials), the *hājjiyyāt* (the complementary) and the *tahsīniyyāt* (the desirable or the

⁹⁴ See: M. Najtullah Siddiqi, *Riba, Bank Interest and the Rational for its Prohibition*, (Jeddah: Islamic Economics Research Center, 2004), Visiting Scholars' Research Series No. 2, 18.

⁹⁵ For example, see: (57:25), (16:90), (2:151), (3:164), (2:185), (22:78), (2:286), (4:28), (27:77).

⁹⁶ Cited in M.U. Chapra, "Relevance and Importance of Islamic Economics" in *Lessons in Islamic Economics* (Vol. 1), edited by Monzer Kahf, (Jeddah: Islamic Research and Training Institute (IRTI), 1998), Seminar Proceedings No. 41, 105.

embellishments).⁹⁷ The *maslaha*, according to *‘ulama*, refers to "the preservation of the objectives of *Sharī‘ah*"⁹⁸ which is considered to be the main objective of the *Sharī‘ah*.⁹⁹ The essential *masālih* or *darūriyyāt* are divided into five:¹⁰⁰

- a) Preservation of faith/religion (*Dīn*)
- b) Preservation of the life (*Nafs*)
- c) Preservation of lineage/descendants/procreation (*Nasl*) Here we will mention only few. Allah (Preservation of property (*Māl*)
- e) Preservation of intellect/reason (*‘Aql*)

M.F. Khan is of opinion that the objectives or *maqāsid al-Sharī‘ah* are the starting point of the foundation of Islamic economics.¹⁰¹ If this is the case, then Islamic finance and any other branch of Islamic economics is supposed to be based on the *maslaha* prescribed by *maqāsid al-Sharī‘ah*. He further goes by saying that economic agents, in an Islamic framework, "will seek *maslaha* instead of seeking utility in the conventional sense."¹⁰²

There are several definitions of legal maxims (*qawā‘id al-fiqhiyyah*). Al-Suyuti defined *al-Qawā‘id* as "a general rule which applies to all its particulars"¹⁰³ while Al-Burnu defined it "as a universal legal ruling or proposition from which are understood the particular legal rulings that are derived from it."¹⁰⁴ It could be also defined as "theoretical abstraction, usually in form of short epithetical statements, that are expressive, often in a few words, of the goals and objectives of the *Sharī‘ah*."¹⁰⁵ These statements are derived from the rules of the *fiqh*. After the detailed studying of the issues, the *‘ulama* came up with general legal maxims expressing the legal procedures in the matters concerned. There are many legal maxims mentioned by the early *‘ulama*,¹⁰⁶ but the leading

⁹⁷ Mohammed Hashim Kamali, "Al-Maqasid Al-Shari'ah: The Objectives of Islamic Law," *The Muslim Lawyer*, vol. 3, no. 1 (April-June 1998), 2, available at <<http://www.aml.org.uk/journal/3.1/Kamali%20-%20Maqasid.pdf>> (accessed 15 January, 2007).

⁹⁸ M. Fahim Khan, "*Fiqh* Foundations of the Theory of Islamic Economics: A Survey of Selected Contemporary Writings on Economics Relevant Subjects of *Fiqh*" in *Theoretical Foundations of Islamic Economics*, edited by Habib Ahmed, (Jeddah: Islamic Research and Training Institute (IRTI), 2002), Book of Readings No. 3, 64.

⁹⁹ Kamali, "Al-Maqasid Al-Shari'ah", 1.

¹⁰⁰ Following the classification given by al-Ghazālī in his book *Al-Mustasfā min ‘Ilm al-Usūl* see: Kamali, "Al-Maqasid Al-Shari'ah", 2 and M. Fahim Khan, "*Fiqh* Foundations", 64.

¹⁰¹ M. Fahim Khan, "*Fiqh* Foundations", 63.

¹⁰² M. Fahim Khan, "*Fiqh* Foundations", 65.

¹⁰³ Cited in Mahmood Sanusi, "The Application of *al-Qawā‘id al-Fiqhiyyah* in the Area of Islamic Economics," 3.

¹⁰⁴ Cited in *ibid.*, 4.

¹⁰⁵ Mohammed Hashim Kamali, "Qawa'id Al-Fiqh: The Legal Maxims of Islamic Law," *The Muslim Lawyer*, vol. 3, no. 2 (October 1998), 1, available at <<http://www.aml.org.uk/journal/3.2/Kamali%20-%20Qawaid%20al-Fiqh.pdf>> (accessed 15 January, 2007).

¹⁰⁶ In *The Mejelle* there have been recorded ninety nine legal maxims. See: S.A. Rahman, *The Mejelle*, 3-15.

five are more widely used than others as they hold the essence of the *Sharī'ah* as whole.¹⁰⁷ These legal maxims are as follows:¹⁰⁸

- i) "Harm must be eliminated" – الضرر يزال
- ii) "Acts are judged by the intention behind them" – الأمور بمقاصدها
- iii) "Certainty is not overruled by doubt" – اليقين لا يزول بالشك
- iv) "Hardship begets facility" – المشقة تجلب التيسير
- v) "Custom is authoritative" – العادة محكّمة

Why are the *maqāsid al-Sharī'ah* and *al-qawā'id al-fiqhiyyah* important for the Islamic financial system? The best answer to this question is given by Mahmood Sanusi when he said:

By downplaying the importance of the legal maxims, and by not fully implementing the principles of Islamic legal maxims of fiqh in the Islamic financial products and its legal documentation, there exists the grave risk that such financial products and their supporting legal documentation, while they embrace the requirement of Fiqh Mu'amalat on the exterior, do not fully comply with the objective of the lawgiver 'Allah (swt)' or Maqṣud al Shari' and the purpose of His Law.¹⁰⁹

Consequently, the BBA contract should be fulfilling the objectives of *Sharī'ah*, i.e. to promote public interest or *maslaha*. It should be based on the well-known legal maxim: '*Liability is an obligation accompanying gain*'.¹¹⁰ This legal maxim is directly derived from the *hadīth* of the Holy Prophet (pbuh), saying: "*Profit follows responsibility*."¹¹¹

Citing this and some other legal maxims related to the *fiqh mu'amalāt*, Mahmood Sanusi criticized the current procedures applied in Malaysia when it comes to the BBA financing. As mentioned earlier in this paper, the bank uses the Property Purchase Agreement (PPA) and the Property Sale Agreement (PSA) simultaneously. The aforementioned agreement, PPA and PSA, are 'only legal devices' since real transfer of ownership is not taking place. In addition to this artificial mechanism, the bank, as a seller, does not hold any liability to the goods sold. As result, the customer or the buyer cannot claim anything if any defects, shrinkage or faults occur. Applying this

¹⁰⁷ Kamali, "Qawa'id Al-Fiqh", 2.

¹⁰⁸ Kamali, "Qawa'id Al-Fiqh", 2. See also M. Fahim Khan, "*Fiqh Foundations*", 64.

¹⁰⁹ Mahmood Sanusi, "*Al-Qawa'id Al-Fiqhiyyah: Its Relevance to Malaysian Islamic Financial Products*", *Shariah Law Reports*, vol. 3, (July-September 2006), 1.

¹¹⁰ Cited in Sanusi, "*Al-Qawa'id Al-Fiqhiyyah*", 1.

¹¹¹ This *hadīth* is narrated by A'ishā (ra). See Abū Dāwūd, *Sunan Abū Dāwūd*, Hadīth 3508, 3509 and 3510, 661-662.

modus operandi Islamic banks deviate from the objectives of *Shari'ah* – says Mahmood Sanusi.¹¹² Some other objections mentioned by Mahmood Sanusi are as follows:¹¹³

- a) Currently the BBA is carried out through *bay' al-'inah* which is considered as legal device (*hilah*) and *harām* in *fiqh mu'āmalāt*.
- b) The BBA consists of two sales combined in one transaction.
- c) The BBA is a sale with condition which is not legal. This transaction is invalid as the promise to purchase the goods is binding on customer.
- d) This contract involves a sale prior to the possession of the object of sale. Islam does not allow the sale of the goods which are not in possession. Under the BBA contract, the role of Islamic banks is minimized to the "act of delivering the various cheques and signing the legal documents."¹¹⁴
- e) Finally, the liability for defects is waived from the banks and this is contrary to the legal maxims. A business without bearing risks and liability is forbidden.¹¹⁵

Sanusi goes step forward and declares this practice as unlawful according to *Shari'ah* by saying:

Based on the foregoing and ultimately having examined these Financial instruments and its legal documentations currently practiced in Islamic Banks, it is apparent that from the standpoint of the legal Maxims of *Fiqh Muamalat*, such Financial instruments are deemed unlawful according to *Shari'ah* rulings because, generally it is not adhering to the principles of the Islamic legal Maxims which have been developed by Muslim jurists to provide an accurate and consistent basis for ruling of the commercial transactions. Undoubtedly it conflicts with the Islamic general legal maxims and *maqāsid al- Shari'ah*. In addition, one cannot find any sound argument for its genuine validity.¹¹⁶

Now, the question can be raised: *Why do Islamic banks prefer BBA financing to other modes of finance?* The answer to this question is quite simple. Islamic banks prefer this mode of finance since this technique is relatively simple and it allows the banks to earn positive profits without really bearing the risk of loss, except in case of default and/or bankruptcy.¹¹⁷ Therefore it is

¹¹² Sanusi, "*Al-Qawa'id Al-Fiqhiyyah*", 13.

¹¹³ *Ibid.*, 14-15.

¹¹⁴ *Ibid.*, 14.

¹¹⁵ *Ibid.*, 15.

¹¹⁶ *Ibid.*, 15.

¹¹⁷ Bendjilali, *Assessment of the Practice*, 43.

important for us to mention the rule, put forward by Islamic scholars, which says that there should be no profit without risk. In this regard Saleh Kamel¹¹⁸ says:

Lack of emphasis, from the theoretical aspect, on the rule that there is no gain without risks, neglecting it totally in most operations of the Islamic banks and expanded use of guaranteed patterns of principal and return has brought confusion among the public. This loophole may provide an opportunity for skeptics to sow the seeds of confusion and deceit among people and may even pave the way for using a number of apparently logical reasons to justify and make lawful bank interest. I strongly believe that if we continue along this line, Islamic banks will lose the theoretical as well as practical basis for their establishment and continuity.

2.9 OBJECTIONS RELATED TO THE BBA

BBA as a mode of financing has been criticized for quite a long time. Its validity has been questioned throughout literature. Here we will try to summarize some of these objections related to the BBA contract. Some of the objections are:

- i) *Similarity with Interest Rate*: One of the critics linked to the BBA contract is that it is very similar to the conventional interest-based financing. It is said that, “[t]he selling price of the BBA facility is similar to nominal value of a loan plus the total interest payment.”¹¹⁹ Some would argue that it is "the closest Islamic analogue to interest finance..."¹²⁰ Comparing the characteristics of Islamic or interest-free banks and conventional banks Metwally concluded that, "[i]nterest-free banks rely heavily on the *Murābaha* method of finance which is based on the use of a mark-up which does not differ much from the interest charge."¹²¹ This again proves our previous claim that these practices would lead to the convergence of the Islamic banks into conventional banks.
- ii) As we have already explained above under the sub-topic *Determination of the Price*, we can see that the seller and buyer are at liberty to agree at any price. Therefore when performing *bayʿ*^c (sale), the seller can take into account different factors, including the time of payment. However, this can be done only at the time when the sale is taking

¹¹⁸ This citation is taken from the Lecture of Mr. Saleh Kamel at a party given in his honor as Winner of the IDB Prize in Islamic Banking, Jeddah, 20 October 1997. See: Saleh Kamel, *Development of Islamic Banking Activity: Problems and Prospects*, (Jeddah: Islamic Research and Training Institute (IRTI), 1998), IDB Prize Winners' Lecture Series No. 12, 13-14.

¹¹⁹ *Ibid.*, 122.

¹²⁰ Vogel and Hayes, *Islamic Law and Finance*, 139 and 240.

¹²¹ M.M. Metwally, "Differences Between the Financial Characteristics of Interest-free Banks and Conventional Banks", *European Business Review*, vol. 97, no. 2 (1997): 98.

place and cannot be later on extended in case of default by the buyer.¹²² However, even though the penalties should not be there in Islamic banking system, yet Islamic banks to charge penalties for the late payments and defaults.

iii) *Use of the Interest Rate as a Benchmark*: Islamic banks and financial institutions commonly use LIBOR as a benchmark, or in case of Malaysia KLIBOR, in order to determine their profit margin. Using interest rate is considered undesirable – according to Usmani – but it does not make the transaction invalid or *harām*, because the contract in itself does not contain interest. However, he thinks that this practice should be replaced with some kind of Islamic benchmark.¹²³

iv) *The Question of 'Iwad (عوض - Countervalue)*: This is one of the major objections related to the BBA facilities offered by Islamic banks. It is believed that a valid sale must meet some requirements, namely: there should be no uncertainty (*gharar*) and the equivalent countervalue (*'iwad*) should exist.¹²⁴ There are three principal components of *'iwad*, namely: risk and liability (*ghurm* and *daman*), work (*'amal*) and capital (*māl*).¹²⁵ This implies that any sale conducted by Islamic bank must contain *'iwad* for the profit to be considered legal. As stated by S.A. Rosly, "...*'iwad* is the basic trait or *conditio sine qua non* of a lawful trade."¹²⁶ In other words, a profit from a sale which does not contain *'iwad* is not a lawful profit. Islamic banks, in their financing modes, should observe *'iwad* and comprising of those three principal components mentioned above (i.e. *ghurm* and *daman*, *'amal* and *māl*). However, in the case of BBA financing there is "relatively no trace of risk-taking and value addition."¹²⁷

2.10 VULNERABILITY OF THE BBA CONTRACT

As we have already mentioned, BBA is a sale contract and therefore profit earned from BBA is *halāl*. The uniqueness of BBA facility lies in its selling price. This price (i.e. the price of goods sold through BBA) is fixed throughout the contract period and it cannot be changed since the changing of the price would make the contract null and void.¹²⁸

¹²² M. T. Usmani, *An Introduction to Islamic Finance*, 44-48.

¹²³ *Ibid.*, 48-49.

¹²⁴ Saiful Azhar Rosly, "*Iwad* as a Requirement of Lawful Sale: A Critical Analysis," *IJUM Journal of Economics and Management*, vol. 9, no. 2 (2001): 187. Any increase according to majority of jurists of four schools of *fiqh* should contain *'iwad*, see Rosly, *Issues*, 520.

¹²⁵ Rosly, "*Iwad* as a Requirement of Lawful Sale," 187 and 193.

¹²⁶ *Ibid.*, 191.

¹²⁷ *Ibid.*, 196. See also: Vogel and Hayes, *Islamic Law and Finance*, 139-143 and 240

¹²⁸ Rosly, *Critical Issues*, 122.

In case of conventional banking and finance, interest rate on loans can be adjusted at any time in line with market forces. This means that when overall interest rate is rising the borrowers will pay higher interest rates monthly and when interest rate is falling they will pay lower interest rates on monthly basis. We see that the loan price is determined by the interest rate which is further on dictated by the market forces. In other words, the loan price is flexible and can be adjusted according to the market conditions at any particular time.

However, this is not the case with BBA facility. Here, the price is fixed for whole duration of the contract. It cannot be changed even if the cost of the underlying product has changed. The price of a product under BBA is set upfront at the beginning of the contract. This price consists of the cost of that product by the bank and the profit margin. The difference between the original price (i.e. ~~marking to high high selling price~~) represents the legitimate profit the bank earns over the instalment period.

2.10.1 Rising Interest Rate

Even though the BBA contract is 'interest-free', still we observe its vulnerability¹²⁹ in case of rising and/or falling interest rate. This shows that BBA contracts are somehow linked, tied and dependent on the movement of interest rate. Here we are going to see what happens when the interest rate goes up.

If central bank announces an increase in the interest rate or if the customers expect the interest rate to go up even further then there is great possibility that the customers will opt for the BBA facilities. Because the price of BBA contracts cannot be changed, Islamic banks cannot do much about this increase in interest rate. If they do change their selling price this would violate one of the principles of *al-bay'*. This principle states that the selling price cannot be changed. Now the loans are relatively more expensive than Islamic BBA financing facilities, so increase in demand for BBA facilities is understandable.

This increase in demand for BBA is something that is desirable. However, it is a difficult situation for Islamic banks since they have locked their profit margins already. This means that Islamic banks lack necessary funds to increase BBA financing. Due to the increase in interest rate, the rate on deposits also increases in case of conventional banks. Consequently, conventional deposits are more attractive to the customers than the Islamic deposits which yield relatively less return. To increase the rate of return on new deposits, for Islamic banks, is not a wise solution. This extra *hibah*, if given, would cut the profits of the Islamic banks, since they cannot generate revenue due to the locked-in BBA financing.

¹²⁹ On this issue see illustrative example provided in Appendix 1.

Finally, Islamic banks will face a serious problem. In order to generate more deposits they will have to borrow from inter-bank money market. But the cost of these funds is higher than *hibah* given by Islamic banks.

From the above discussion we can say that Islamic banks have two (2) options¹³⁰ when interest rate is rising, namely:

- (a) To increase *hibah* and dividend in order to remain competitive in the deposit market, and
- (b) Not to increase *hibah* and dividend rates

We have to remember here that Islamic banks *cannot* change BBA profit rate. If they go for the option (a) the profit will decline and the banking performance will be adversely affected. On the other side, if they go for option (b) the profit will remain the same in the short-run. In addition, the customers would shift to conventional banks that offer higher interest rate on deposits. The deposits in Islamic banks will decrease and there will be asset-liability mismatch.¹³¹ In order to solve the problem Islamic banks will have to resort to the money market (an interest-based market) which is more expensive than bank deposits. At the end of the day, the profit of Islamic banks will fall. Islamic banks will lose, while non-Muslim, and even some Muslim, customers will gain. Here, we may ask one simple question: Having in mind the nature of Islamic banks and the prohibition of *ribā*, is it allowed to Islamic bank to resort to the money market for its financing needs?

There are also advantages of BBA over the conventional loans when the interest rate is rising. These advantages are:

- i) fixed selling price
- ii) no penalties on late payments/defaults.¹³²

Under this scenario of rising interest rate, these two advantages have made BBA contract a better alternative to the conventional loans.

In short, when interest rate is rising, the following would be the result as stated by Rosly:

¹³⁰ Ibid., 249-252.

¹³¹ When asset-liability mismatch happens there are two scenarios. First scenario is when the deposits are greater than financing. This scenario will lead to the following: (i) excess liquidity; (ii) deposit expenses greater than revenues from financing; and (iii) lower profits. Second scenario is when the deposits are lower than financing. This will lead to the following: (i) higher cost of funds; (ii) deposit expenses greater than revenues from financing; and (iii) lower profits.

¹³² Rosly, *Critical Issues*, 123. This is theoretically true, but in reality it is not true since Islamic banks do charge penalties on late payments/defaults. This is evident from several legal cases in Malaysia. There are four civil cases involving disputes between Islamic banks and their customers. These cases relate to defaults of *murābaha* or BBA facilities and its impact on the defaulting customers. These cases are: Bank Islam Malaysia v. Adnan b. Omar, Dato' Haji Nik Mahmud vs Bank Islam Malaysia, Tinta Press Sdn. Bhd vs Bank Islam Malaysia Bhd, and Affin Bank Bhd vs Zulkifli Abdullah. For the detailed discussion about these cases see: Saiful Azhar Rosly, "Consumer Rights and Protection in Islamic Banking," paper presented at *the Malaysian Institute Economic Research National Outlook Conference*, 5th – 6th December 2006, Hilton, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia. See also: Rosly, *Issues*, 354-355.

...non-Muslim customers will use BBA financing, but may place their savings in conventional deposits. By doing so, they have benefited in both worlds, namely, cheaper credit and higher returns on deposits. Muslim customers, on the other hand, don't have much choice but only to look. Islamic banks will be stuck with less deposit. To acquire funds at higher costs would cut down earnings.¹³³

The above citation indicates the process known as arbitraging. Here we see how the customers are performing arbitrage in order to gain from their investment (i.e. deposits). These examples of rising and falling interest rate also indicate the convergence that is taking place between the Islamic and conventional banks.

2.10.2 Falling Interest Rate

When this happens we could expect increase in the borrowing by the household and business sector. The increase in borrowings will increase the consumption and investment. Finally this will lead to the increase in the GDP. However, it is interesting to see what will happen to the Islamic banking once the interest rate falls. This will be discussed shortly.

Now, if the customers expect interest rate to go down, Islamic banks will again face some serious problems. This decrease in interest rate will lead to decline in demand for BBA financing, since BBA financing would be more expensive option than conventional loans. Remember that BBA price and therefore profit margin cannot be changed, while interest rate on loans can be either increased or decreased.

On the other side, the fall in interest rate will cause the interest rate on conventional deposits to go down. When this happens, the rate of return on Islamic deposit will be relatively higher than the interest rate on conventional deposits. As a result we would see some of those conventional deposits being transferred to Islamic banks. A lower demand for BBA facilities combined with higher supply of Islamic deposits will lead to the excess liquidity. Islamic banks will be overburdened by deposits that they are unable to invest. Here again we see the convergence between the Islamic and conventional banks taking place.

Once again, non-Muslim customers are going to gain from the decline in interest rate. When interest rate falls, due to the lower cost of borrowing, they will use loans instead of BBA for financing purposes. At the same time, *hibah* paid by Islamic banks is relatively higher than the interest rate on deposit in conventional banks. This will increase the supply of Islamic deposits by non-Muslims.

¹³³ Ibid., 251.

In overall, as with the case of rising interest rate, here again Islamic banks have two (2) options when interest rate is falling, namely:

- (a) To cut *hibah* and dividend in order to remain competitive in the deposit market, and
- (b) To maintain *hibah* and dividend rates.

But remember again that Islamic banks *cannot* change the profit rate under any circumstances. Why it cannot change the profit rate? The answer is relatively simple. Changing of the profit rate would bring uncertainty to the contract. This uncertainty makes a contract void. Cutting the *hibah* and dividend rates will increase the profit of Islamic banks. Islamic banks will gain, while its customers using BBA facilities will lose. They will still have to pay higher instalment and they will not be able to enjoy decrease in interest rate. As mentioned above, the profit rate cannot be changed due to the uncertainty it may bring into contract.

In the short-run, the profit will remain the same if the option (b) is applied. BBA customers will lose again as stated above. In the long-run, Islamic banks may lose. If they keep the *hibah* at the initial level it will attract new deposits. Therefore, the supply of Islamic deposits will go up while there will be a big problem to use BBA for new contracts due to relatively higher cost. Again, we will see the asset-liability mismatch. Finally, the profit will decline.

2.10.3 Inflation

The effect of inflation on BBA contract is very much similar to the case of increasing interest rate explained earlier. Once inflation occurs the cost of funds will increase reciprocally. The conventional banks will increase the interest rate on the loans. This way they will protect themselves from the adverse effect of inflation. The inflation and especially hyper inflation will have a huge impact on the rate of return charged by Islamic banks using *murābaha* and BBA modes of finance. Whether the rate of return is determined below the rate of inflation or if it caters for the inflation rate, still it will have some impacts either on the bank or on the client. In latter case, the effect on financial institution will be negative in real terms and it may face problem in meeting new commitments. In former case, when Islamic bank caters for inflation rate, the *murābaha* rate would be a burden on low income earners. The reason for this is that the rate of *murābaha* is determined on the total amount of *murābaha* financing.¹³⁴

When it comes to Islamic banks, as we have already seen that, in the case of rising interest rate, the selling price cannot be changed. In other words, Islamic banks cannot adjust their profit margin once it is been locked-in. Therefore, the end result will be the same as in the case of rising interest rate i.e. Islamic bank will have two (2) options to choose from, namely:

¹³⁴ Abdin A. Salama, "Housing Finance in Islamic Countries" in *Islamic Banking Modes For House Building Financing*, edited by Mahmoud Ahmad Mahdi,, (Jeddah: Islamic Research and Training Institute (IRTI), 1995), Seminar Proceedings Series No. 28, 31.

- (a) To increase *hibah* and dividend in order to remain competitive in the deposit market, and
- (b) Not to increase *hibah* and dividend rates

We have to remember, again here, that Islamic banks *cannot* change BBA profit rate. Implementing the first option, the profit will decline and the banking performance will be adversely affected. On the other side, going for the second option, the profit will remain the same in the short-run. Non-Muslim customers will shift to the conventional banks that offer higher interest rate on deposit. The deposits in Islamic banks will decrease and there will be asset-liability mismatch. One of the solutions for Islamic banks to address this problem would be to resort to the money market which is more expensive than bank deposits. Finally, the profit of Islamic banks will fall. Islamic banks will lose, while non-Muslim customers will gain.

2.11 CONCLUSION

Although BBA financing is permissible according to *Shari'ah*, yet many Muslim scholars have warned us not to use it extensively, due to its similarity to the conventional interest-based transactions. Even though we are not paying interest directly we are doing it indirectly. Once a bank buys a product for a customer and sell it to him at a mark-up price, the bank, without saying, takes into account all the components considered by conventional bank. Therefore, the customer pays the instalment that includes principal plus '*interest*' already paid by the bank.¹³⁵ Using BBA "widely and indiscriminately...might open a back door to "interest"."¹³⁶ This has been pointed out by the Islamic Ideology Council of Pakistan in its report to the Government in 1980:

Safeguards would, therefore, need to be designed so as to restrict its use only to inescapable cases. In addition, the range of mark-up on purchase prices would also have to be regulated strictly so as to avoid arbitrariness and possibility of recrudescence of interest in a different garb. The State Bank may, therefore, specify, and from time to time, review and vary the sub-sectors and items for which banks may provide the needed finance under *bay' muajjal* arrangements. It may also lay down the range of the profit margin in general or separately for each sub-sector or item and may impose such other restrictions as may be deemed to be necessary with a view to avoiding the emergence of unhealthy practices.¹³⁷

¹³⁵ Amilda Dymi, "Faith-Based Lending: Islamic Financing", *Broker*, August 2005, 61.

¹³⁶ D.M. Qureshi, "The Role of *Shari'ah*-Based Financial Instruments in a Muslim Country", in *Developing A System of Financial Instruments*, edited by Mohammad Ariff and M.A. Mannan (Jeddah: Islamic Research and Training Institute, 1990), 52.

¹³⁷ Cited in *Ibid.*, 52.

From everything we have said so far it can be concluded that BBA as a mode of finance, even though being allowed by *Shari'ah* scholars, is of a questionable validity because of the *modus operandi* or mechanism implemented in Malaysian Islamic banks. The extensive use of BBA contracts and overdependence of Islamic banks on this mode of finance will result in convergence of Islamic bank into conventional, interest-based, banks. Therefore, its usage as a mode of finance should be minimized as much as possible, if not eliminated from Islamic banks. By doing so, Islamic banks will move closer to the real objectives of *Shari'ah* (*maqāsid al- Shari'ah*). It is worthy to mention here M. Umer Chapra's view on the issue. Addressing the issue of *murābahah* and BBA he says:

This is a perfectly legitimate transaction according to the *Shari'ah*, provided that the risk for the transaction is borne by the financier until the possession has been passed to the customer. For such a transaction to be legal, the bank would have to sign two separate contracts, one with the supplier and the other with the customer. It would not be lawful for the bank to have only one contract with the purchaser, the only service rendered by it being the remittance of the amount to the supplier on behalf of the purchaser. In this case the transaction would not be different from an interest-based arrangement. In addition to the dual contract, the bank would have to continue to be responsible until the goods were actually delivered to the customer, not necessarily by the bank, according with specifications and other terms of the contract.¹³⁸

From the above statement it is obvious how the *murābahah* and BBA transactions should be carried out in reality. He further goes on by concluding that, "[t]he danger will, however, always remain that the *mu'ajjal* and *murābahah* forms of sales may deteriorate into purely financing arrangements with the agreed profit margin being no more than a camouflage for interest."¹³⁹

We couldn't agree more on the above. This is exactly what is happening right now in Islamic banks, at least in case of Malaysia. The real BBA, as shown in Figure 2.1, is not taking place nowadays. There are currently no two contracts implemented when financing through BBA as it suggested by Chapra in the above citation. For BBA to be valid contract it should be carried out as presented in Figure 2.1 earlier and in accordance to Chapra's description. Unfortunately, presently BBA is taking place as shown in Figure 2.2. This is the fear that was mentioned by Chapra and many others and this is the problem we have to deal with as soon as possible. Considering *murābahah* as financing instrument instead of treating it as a trading device – according to Ebrahim

¹³⁸ M. Umer Chapra, *Towards a Just Monetary system*, 170.

¹³⁹ *Ibid.*, 171.

Sidat – is one of the obstacles faced by Islamic banks in their pursuit to Islamize the banking system.¹⁴⁰

The Council of Islamic Ideology of Pakistan accepted BBA as a financial instrument, but with some reservations. This reservation is expressed in the following lines:

... this system commends itself for its relative simplicity as well as the possibility of some profit for the banks without the risk of having to share in the possible losses, except in the case of bankruptcy or default on the part of the buyer. However, although this mode of financing is understood to be permissible under the *Shari'ah*, it would not be advisable to use it widely or indiscriminately in view of the danger attached to it of opening a back door for dealing on the basis of interest.¹⁴¹

Rosly opines that over-dependence of Islamic banks on BBA financing caused Islamic banking to fall into a negative-fund gap strategy. Employing this negative-fund gap strategy is present during the period of economic boom as well as slowdown.¹⁴² It is believed Islamic banks need an innovative approach to the current situation. Without new instruments Islamic banks will face difficulties in sustaining their growth and development and coping with the increasing competition.¹⁴³ The best way out of the above mentioned problems faced by BBA financing lies in the diversification of the financing products offered by Islamic banks. Some of the products that could possibly be implemented by Islamic banks are discussed in the following sections. These offered products would grant Islamic banks some diversification power to overcome the discussed problems.

¹⁴⁰ Cited in Muhammad Anwar, "Islamicity of Islamic Banking Practices", 363.

¹⁴¹ Cited in Ausaf Ahmad, *Contemporary Practices of Islamic Financing Techniques*, (Jeddah: Islamic Research and Training Institute (IRTI), 1993), Research Paper No. 20, 40.

¹⁴² Saiful Azhar Rosly and Mohd Afandi Abu Bakar, "Performance of Islamic and Mainstream Banks in Malaysia," *International Journal of Social Economics*. vol. 30 no. 12 (2003): 1255.

¹⁴³ Noman "Imperatives of Financial Innovation".

CHAPTER THREE

MUSHĀRAKAH MUTANĀQISAH PARTNERSHIP

3.0 INTRODUCTION

Addressing the issues related to the Islamic banking and finance is almost impossible without mentioning the *Qur'anic* verse, already cited several times in this paper, where Allah s.w.t. says: "... Allah hath permitted trade and forbidden usury..." (Qur'an, *al-Baqarah*: 275). The trade is not only permitted, but rather it is encouraged by the Holy Prophet (pbuh). Al-Suyūṭī, in his book *Al-Jāmi' Al-Saghīr*, mentioned a *hadīth* on the authority of Rāfi' that: "The Prophet (pbuh) was asked: "which are the best forms of income generation?" He (pbuh) replied: "A man's labour, and every legitimate sale".¹⁴⁴ It is this *ayah* which should be guiding principle in Islamic banking and finance. Based on its meaning scholars have concluded that financial transactions should be based on the principle of profit and loss sharing (PLS - الغنم بالغرم). Therefore in Islam the trade should be carried out through PLS mechanism and not through mechanism of interest (i.e. fixed excess return for a fixed amount for a determined period of time, or any excess exchange of similar commodity).¹⁴⁵ Furthermore, *Qur'an* talks about cooperation among Muslims in good deeds and avoiding injustice by saying:

يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا لَا تَحِلُّوا شَعَائِرَ اللَّهِ وَلَا الشَّهْرَ الْحَرَامَ وَلَا الْهَدْيَ وَلَا الْقَلَائِدَ وَلَا آمِينَ الْبَيْتِ
الْحَرَامَ يَبْتَغُونَ فَضْلًا مِّن رَّبِّهِمْ وَرِضْوَانًا وَإِذَا حَلَلْتُمْ فَاصْطَادُوا وَلَا يَجْرِمَنَّكُمْ شَنَا نَ قَوْمٍ
أَصَدُّوكُمْ عَنِ الْمَسْجِدِ الْحَرَامِ أَنْ تَعْتَدُوا وَتَعَاوَنُوا عَلَى الْبِرِّ وَالتَّقْوَىٰ وَلَا تَعَاوَنُوا عَلَى الْإِ
ثْمِ وَالْعُدْوَانِ وَاتَّقُوا اللَّهَ إِنَّ اللَّهَ شَدِيدُ الْعِقَابِ (المائدة, 2)

"O ye who believe! violate not the sanctity of the Symbols of Allah nor of the Sacred Month nor of the animals brought for sacrifice nor the garlands that mark out such animals nor the people resorting to the Sacred House seeking of the bounty and good pleasure of their Lord. But when ye are clear of the Sacred Precincts and of pilgrim garb ye may hunt and let not the hatred of some people in (once) shutting you out of the Sacred Mosque lead you to transgression (and hostility on your part). Help ye one another in righteousness and piety but help ye not one another in sin and rancor: fear Allah: for Allah is strict in punishment." (Al-Qur'an, *al-Mā'idah*: 2).

¹⁴⁴ Cited in Mahmoud Amin El-Gamal, *A Basic Guide to Contemporary Islamic Banking and Finance*, (Houston: Rice University, 2000), 10. Available at: <URL: http://www.nubank.com/islamic_primer.pdf>. See also: Ibn Mājah, *Sunan Ibn Mājah*, Hadith no. 2137 and 2138.

¹⁴⁵ Tajul Islam, "Mechanics of Islamic Banking", 128.

This cooperation has been promoted and implemented by the Holy Prophet (pbuh) between *Ansārs* and *Muhājirūn* in Madīnah. *Mushārahah mutanāqisah partnership* (MMP) is a direct result and implementation of the above verses. MMP or partnership culminating in ownership is a recent innovation in Islamic banking industry. It could be considered as a derivative of original *mushārahah* and *ijārah* modes of financing. Here, these two modes of finance are combined in order to facilitate asset acquisition. MMP consists of two portions.¹⁴⁶ First one consists of *mushārahah* (partnership) between the customer and the bank. This is done through the contract of '*Shirkat-al-^oaqd*. For example, the customer and the bank buy a house with initial capital investment equals 20% and 80% by them respectively. The customer will continue to buy the shares of the bank gradually until the house is fully owned by him. Second portion is implemented through the contract of *ijārah* between the customer and bank. Here, the customer rents the house from the bank and pays the rental payment, which is shared between the two based on their percentage of shares. Slowly, the shares of the customer will increase while the shares of the bank will decrease, through the periodical redemption by the customer, until the house is fully owned by the customer.

This chapter is divided into ten sections, excluding introduction. First section is literature review. Here the main literature on the topic is reviewed and highlighted. Second section is the overview of the *mushārahah* in general and *mushārahah mutanāqisah partnership* in particular. The definitions, legality, classifications and profit and loss issues are all discussed here. Third section explains the mechanism of *mushārahah mutanāqisah partnership* and how it can be implemented in different areas of finance using appropriate examples. The following section, section four briefly explains the basic conditions for valid MMP contract. Section five lists down salient features of MMP contract. Next section, section six highlights the advantages as well as disadvantages of MMP partnership model. Section seven reviews several successful implementations of MMP model used in several countries throughout the world. Mathematical derivation that is used to calculate monthly rental payment and additional payment due by a customer is the subject matter of the section eight. Here, the mathematical model by Meera and Dzuljastri is provided. In section nine, we have compared MMP with BBA and conventional loan financing techniques. Finally, section ten is left for the concluding remarks on the MMP model presented in this chapter.

3.1 LITERATURE REVIEW

The *mushārahah mutanāqisah* or diminishing partnership is relatively a new technique that is not found in classical literature. It is formulated by contemporary Muslim scholars to facilitate investments among Muslims. It is also a financing technique that is relatively very little used by Islamic banks. Even though the mechanism of *mushārahah mutanāqisah partnership* has been

¹⁴⁶ Meera and Dzuljastri, "Islamic Home Financing," 11.

approved by the First International Conference on Islamic Banking, held in Dubai in 1979,¹⁴⁷ it has not been widely implemented throughout Islamic financial system. In this section, we will try to review available literature on *mushārahah mutanāqisah* partnership and give readers necessary background on the topic.

Many problems have been raised about the inability of Islamic banks in implementing traditional *mudhārahah* and *mushārahah* (hereinafter referred to as M-M) modes of financing with regard to their complexity,¹⁴⁸ agency problem,¹⁴⁹ trustworthiness, duration and termination of the contract etc. In that regard, Bendjilali and Khan are of opinion that termination of financier's ownership in certain economic activities is a necessity. Another paper by Khan also addresses the issue of redeemability of M-M modes of financing. It goes on by saying that pure *mudhārahah* funds are not redeemable.¹⁵⁰ Traditional modes of financing (i.e. M-M) do not offer such option. This non-terminating nature of M-M "imposes limitations on the provision of bank finance to newer projects and entrepreneurial activities."¹⁵¹ In this regard Bendjilali and Khan propose the use of *mushārahah mutanāqisah* partnership (MMP) as it enables financier to gradually terminate his/her ownership in a project. They argue that some of the problems faced by M-M could be avoided through implementation of MMP. For example, it is expected that partial ownership of the project could be a fair deterrent against moral hazards. At the same time, as the capital share of a bank gradually decreases in a given project, it will recover some of its capital, together with its share of profits that could be used for investment in new projects.¹⁵²

Rosly is of opinion that MMP is one possible solution to the volatility and uncertainty faced by Islamic banks due to their overdependence on BBA financing technique (referring to the case of Malaysia and Bank Negara's proposal for a floating rate option).¹⁵³ The objective of the MMP is to earn a profits through the investment, while the object of the investment – he says – is to own a property. Capital contribution by the partners is not fixed and can vary from contract to contract.

¹⁴⁷ See: Boualem Bendjilali and Tariqullah Khan, *Economics of Diminishing Musharakah*, (Jeddah: Islamic Research and Training Institute (IRTI), 1995), Research Paper No. 31, 16.

¹⁴⁸ In fact these modes of financing (i.e. *mudhārahah* and *mushārahah*) are not complex at all. There are complex from the point of view of the banks. There are the entities that do not want to be liable and to take responsibility. As M-M modes of finance imply liability, the banks are avoiding them. It can be also attributed to the environment in which Islamic banks are operating and the legal constraints imposed on them by entering this environment.

¹⁴⁹ Ismail Bacha Obiyathullah, "Conventional versus Mudaraba Financing: An Agency Cost Perspective" in *Islamic Banking: How Far Have We Gone?*, edited by A.H. Pramanik (IIUM: Research Centre, 2006), 177-178.

¹⁵⁰ For more details see: Tariqullah Khan, *Redeemable Islamic Financial Instruments and Capital Participation in Enterprises*, (Jeddah: Islamic Research and Training Institute (IRTI), 1995), Research Paper No. 29, 31-49.

¹⁵¹ Bendjilali and Khan, *Economics of Diminishing Musharakah*, 14.

¹⁵² Bendjilali and Khan, *Economics of Diminishing Musharakah*, 44.

¹⁵³ Rosly, *Critical Issues*, 141-142.

However, more research is necessary in order for this contract to get wide acceptance by public – according to Rosly. We hope that this research can help in this regard.

It is believed that MMP, as a mode of Islamic financing, is both efficient and equitable at the same time.¹⁵⁴ Under the MMP, the period needed for the transfer of ownership will be shorter.¹⁵⁵ Furthermore, Bendjilali and Khan opine that MMP could lead to specialization, productivity and alleviation of poverty through redistribution mechanism.¹⁵⁶ In addition to that, MMP is also proposed by Rosly as a solution to the market volatility and uncertainty.¹⁵⁷

The *mushārahah mutanāqisah* financing technique was one of the modes for house financing discussed and approved during the workshop organized by Islamic Research and Training Institute (IRTI), Jeddah, and Sudanese Estates Bank, Sudan, held in Khartoum in 1991.¹⁵⁸ Several papers have been presented in which various techniques have been explained for house financing. Application of these modes by several institutions, such as Jordan Islamic Bank and Al-Baraka International Bank London, are elaborated and explained. Participants of the workshop concluded that the *mushārahah mutanāqisah*, among other modes of financing, is allowed by *Shari'ah* and can be implemented in house financing. The main objections to this mode of finance were: firstly regarding the content or the form of the contract; and secondly the determination of the price of the shares. It is agreed that it is not allowed to have more than one transaction in a single contract where a contract may represent a condition to another contract. It is also believed that the share prices should be determined in accordance with market forces.

Meera and Dzuljastri¹⁵⁹ compared *mushārahah mutanāqisah* partnership with conventional loans and BBA financing facility. They showed that out of these three, MMP is the most efficient in terms of cost incurred by a client. In other words, MMP is relatively the most affordable mode of financing. In addition to that, the duration of financing could be substantially lowered. It is interesting to note that the balance, at any point of time, would not exceed the original amount extended by the financier.

Both, MMP and conventional loans, follow diminishing balance method and therefore the balance, at any point of time, cannot exceed the original amount. On the other hand, balance under BBA facility can be higher than initial contribution by the financier. Being less expensive for the clients compared to BBA, MMP – the authors argued – may not be attractive to the banks since this

¹⁵⁴ Bendjilali and Khan, *Economics of Diminishing Musharakah*, 55.

¹⁵⁵ Bendjilali and Khan, *Economics of Diminishing Musharakah*, 54. See also: Meera and Dzuljastri, "Islamic Home Financing," 20.

¹⁵⁶ Bendjilali and Khan, *Economics of Diminishing Musharakah*, 54.

¹⁵⁷ Rosly, *Critical Issues*, 142.

¹⁵⁸ Proceedings of this Workshop have been published by IRTI. Please see: Mahmoud Ahmad Mahdi ed., *Islamic Banking Modes for House Building Financing*, (Jeddah: Islamic Research and Training Institute (IRTI), 1995), Seminar Proceedings Series No. 28.

¹⁵⁹ Meera and Dzuljastri, "Islamic Home Financing," 5-30.

may reduce their earnings. Due to that, the authors suggested its implementation through cooperatives where the funds are provided by the members for the members. Furthermore, the advantage of cooperatives lies in the fact that there will be no money creation as is the case with fractional reserve banking. This will further promote the objectives of *Sharī'ah* (*maqāsid al-Sharī'ah*). However, MMP is far from being perfect. There are operational problems, such as determination of rental rate, taxation, land laws, etc., that need to be addressed in depth. One of the suggestions is to use Rental Index or House Price Index to avoid any linkage to interest rate.

3.2 OVERVIEW OF MUSHĀRAKAH

Mushārahah represents the partnership whereby the partners share the profit according to agreed ratio/proportion, while the loss is in proportion to the capital invested by the partners. This principle was firstly introduced by Quraishi in his work *Islam and the Theory of Interest*. However, it was formally discussed by Ahmad in *Economics of Islam*, in 1947.¹⁶⁰ Since general *mushārahah* is covered well in the literature we will avoid it here and focus more on the issues related to the *mushārahah mutanāqisah* partnership.

In this section we will discuss some issues related to the *mushārahah mutanāqisah* in particular. We will start with the definitions of *mushārahah mutanāqisah* and its legality from Islamic legal sources followed by the discussion on the profit and loss sharing in *mushārahah mutanāqisah* partnership. Finally the issue of termination of *mushārahah mutanāqisah* will be briefly discussed.

3.2.1 Definition

Bendjilali and Khan define *mushārahah mutanāqisah* partnership or *mushārahah tantahī bi al tamlik* (partnership which ends in transferring of ownership to one party - the client) as a diminishing partnership whereby a product/project becomes fully owned by a client. It is a combination of sale and sharing contracts whereby the ownership is transferred through sale and this transfer is done through profit sharing arrangement.¹⁶¹

3.2.2 Legality of Mushārahah Mutanāqisah

Sharī'ah validity of general *mushārahah* contract can be found in the *Qur'an* (for example see *an-Nisa'*: 12 and *Sād*: 23-24), the Prophet's *Sunnah* and consensus of Muslim scholars (*ijma'*).

When it comes to the legality of the *mushārahah mutanāqisah* partnership model, then we can say that it is fully in line with *Sharī'ah*. It consists of several contracts, namely *mushārahah*

¹⁶⁰ Mentioned in Monzer Kahf and Tariqullah Khan, *Principles of Islamic Financing: A Survey*, (Jeddah: Islamic Research and Training Institute (IRTI), 1992), Research Paper No. 16, 24.

¹⁶¹ Bendjilali and Khan, *Economics of Diminishing Musharakah*, 49.

(partnership), *ijārah* (leasing) and *bayʿ* (sale), whose validity is found in all sources of *Shariʿah*. There is no disagreement even among the Muslim scholars on its permissibility. The only slight differences exist with regard to the conditions related to the MMP and its implementation.

It should be also noted that the *mushārahah mutanāqisah* partnership has been discussed and agreed upon even during the first Islamic Banking conference held in Dubai 23-25 of *Jumad Thani* 1399H (1979).¹⁶²

3.2.3 Profit and Loss Sharing under *Mushārahah Mutanāqisah*

It is important to note that in a cooperative agreement such as *mushārahah*, partners mingle their capitals and make it as one that is indistinguishable. All the partners in *mushārahah* can participate in managing funds, but if a partner does not want to take a part in management it is still a valid partnership. This means that participating in management under *mushārahah* contract is not required. The same applies to the *mushārahah mutanāqisah* partnership.

Regarding the profit and loss sharing, partners must agree at the beginning of a partnership on an exact percentage (e.g. each share 40% and 60% respectively) of the profit that is due to each one of them. *Shariʿah* did not prescribe any specific percentage, rather it is up to the partners to agree on. It can be in equal proportions or in different ones. The only thing that *Shariʿah* does not allow is to prescribe a lump-sum amount of profit for any party involved in partnership or any percentage tied up with the capital.¹⁶³ However, the partners are free to agree on any percentage of the profit to be allocated between them.

On the other hand, Muslim scholars are unanimous about the sharing of the loss incurred in *mushārahah*. In this case they all agree that it *must* be according to the capital invested by each party involved. For example, if the financier's and the client's shares in *mushārahah* are in proportion 40:60 then the loss will be borne in that vary same proportion, i.e. 40:60 respectively.

3.2.4 Termination of *Mushārahah Mutanāqisah*

It is generally agreed that the *mushārahah*, in general, and therefore *mushārahah mutanāqisah*, in particular, is unilateral contract that can be terminated at any time by any party involved. In other words, this is not binding contract and every partner can quit or sell his/her shares to others. The

¹⁶² Ahmed Ali Abdallah, "Forms of Investment in Real Estates in Islamic Perspectives" in *Islamic Banking Modes For House Building Financing*, edited by Mahmoud Ahmad Mahdi,, (Jeddah: Islamic Research and Training Institute (IRTI), 1995), Seminar Proceedings Series No. 28, 48.

¹⁶³ Usmani, *An Introduction to Islamic Finance*, 14. See also: AAOIFI, *Shari'a Standards*, 214.

only situation when a partner is not allowed to sell his/her shares is in the case when it can hurt the other side, i.e. his/her partner.¹⁶⁴

3.3 MECHANISM OF *MUSHĀRAKAH MUTANĀQISAH* PARTNERSHIP

The *mushārahah mutanāqisah* model can be easily implemented for various financing purposes. It is most commonly used for home financing. The mechanism used in this case can be found in almost every article referring to MMP financing technique. Basic steps involved in the *mushārahah mutanāqisah* structure for home financing are:

i) *First Step*

- a. Customer identifies the property that he/she wants to purchase and he approaches the bank for financing facility.
- b. Customer and bank will enter into a *mushārahah mutanāqisah* arrangement where the purpose of this partnership is to acquire a property.
- c. The initial deposit/down payment made by the customer at this stage will be his contribution towards the *mushārahah mutanāqisah* Venture while the bank's contribution will equal the financing amount.

ii) *Second Step*

- a. The bank subsequently leases the acquired property to the customer.
- b. The rental paid by the customer will be distributed among partners in accordance to the prevailing shareholding at the point the rental is paid/received.
- c. The customer will use his/her portion of the rental income to purchase the bank's stake in the property. The shares of the bank will be reduced by every purchase of the shares by the customer.
- d. The bank's portion of the rental income is similar to a financing profit earned by a conventional bank.

iii) *Third Step*

- At the end of tenure of the lease, the property will be wholly owned by the customer. The *mushārahah mutanāqisah* will be terminated.

The above mentioned steps are illustrated in the Figure 3.1 below. In addition to this, some of the contemporary implementation of MMP for home financing will be discussed later on in this research.

¹⁶⁴ Muhammad Ahmad A. Hadi Siraj, "Mudharabah, Musharakah and Ijarah" in *Lessons in Islamic Economics* (Vol. 1), edited by Monzer Kahf, (Jeddah: Islamic Research and Training Institute (IRTI), 1998), Seminar Proceedings No. 41, 89.

2) Periodic rental income generated from the lease rental of the property will be distributed to Bank and Customer. Customer will use his portion from the lease rental amount to buy the Bank's stake in the property.

1) Bank and Customer enters into a *Mushārahah* Arrangement whereby Bank and Customer will provide capital towards the acquisition of the property.

Figure 3.1: *Mushārahah Mutanāqisah* Structure in Home Financing

Here, we will try to explain the MMP mechanism using another example. To illustrate how MMP financing technique could be implemented, consider the following example¹⁶⁵ for instance: Ahmad wants to start a factory that produces home furniture, but he lacks necessary funds for running that business. Let us assume that for starting this business Ahmad needs RM200,000. He approaches the bank and asks for assistance. The bank enters into joint venture with Ahmad whereby the bank finances 90% of the necessary capital (RM180,000), while the remaining 10% (RM20,000) is financed by Ahmad himself. There are two scenarios that could be implemented here:

- (i) *Profit and loss sharing*: Once Ahmad starts operating and earns income that will be divided according to agreed ratio. For example, if the agreed ratio is 80:20, then 80% of the profit would go to the bank and 20% to Ahmad respectively. It should be noted that this ratio may be in the same proportion as their capital contribution or it may be different one. However, if loss occurs then it will be shared according to capital contribution only. Islamic scholars are unanimous on this.

¹⁶⁵ This example has been presented in the paper by the author: Edib Smolo, "Utilizing *Mushārahah Mutanāqisah* Partnership for Micro and Medium Enterprises (MMEs)," paper presented at the First International Conference on Inclusive Islamic Financial Sector Development: *Enhancing Islamic Financial Services for Micro and Medium Sized Enterprises (MMEs)* held during 17-19 April, 2007 in Negara Brunei Darussalam.

The bank's share in the business will be further divided into equal units, each representing additional shares in the business. Ahmad agrees that he will buy additional unit of the shares after an agreed period of time. Consequently, Ahmad will buy additional shares of the business and his shares in the business will increase while decreasing the shares of the bank. Following this method, Ahmad will completely own the business after an agreed period (it can be any amount of years). Using this mechanism, the bank earns periodical profits generated out of the business plus it regains the original amount invested in the business through the periodical sale of its shares to Ahmad.

- (ii) *Renting the premises:* The above-mentioned example is one way of operating under MMP model. The other one would be if the bank and Ahmad enter the joint venture and Ahmed starts the business while paying the rent to the bank for using its shares in the business. If we assume that the rental in that area is RM2,000 per month, this is the amount to be shared between the parties according to their capital contribution. This means that out of RM2,000, RM1,800 and RM200 will go to the bank and Ahmad respectively. Ahmad may add up additional amount of money in order to speed up the buy-back of the shares from the bank. Once Ahmad buys additional units of shares from the bank, his shares will rise, causing the shares of the bank to decrease. In the same way the share in the rental payment will be adjusted, until the business is fully owned by Ahmad and no rental is paid to the bank. Following this scenario, the bank will earn the rent throughout the period plus it will regain its original capital invested in the joint venture. This example will be further substantiated by the mathematical model later on in this paper.

In short, the mechanism for financing business needs is illustrated in the Figure 3.2 below.

2) Customer will undertake to purchase the Bank's stake with a profit attached throughout the venture tenor via an agreed schedule of purchase.

1) Bank and Customer enters into a *Mushārah* Arrangement whereby Bank and Customer will provide capital towards the financing of the Venture

Figure 3.2: *Mushārah Mutanāqisah* Structure in Corporate Financing

3.4 BASIC CONDITIONS FOR VALID *MUSHĀRAKAH MUTANĀQISAH* PARTNERSHIP

The *mushārah mutanāqisah* or decreasing partnership represents a joint venture between the bank and the customer where they buy the house (or any other asset) together. Once acquired, the house is leased to the customer who pays the rent to the bank for using its shares in the house. Together with the rent, the customer will pay additional amount in order to redeem the shares of the financier. Consequently the financier's shares will decrease while the customer's shares will increase until the house is fully owned by the customer. This mechanism entails three contracts – according to Usmani.¹⁶⁶ These contracts are:

- i) Establishment of the joint venture;
- ii) Leasing the shares of financier to the customer; and
- iii) Selling the successive shares of the financier to the customer.

It is obvious from the above that *mushārah mutanāqisah* financing technique consists of three parts, namely: *mushārah* (partnership), *ijārah* (leasing) and *bay'c* (sale). All of these

¹⁶⁶ Usmani, "Methods of House Building Financing According to *Shari'ah*" in *Islamic Banking Modes For House Building Financing*, edited by Mahmoud Ahmad Mahdi,, (Jeddah: Islamic Research and Training Institute (IRTI), 1995), Seminar Proceedings Series No. 28, 67-68.

contracts are allowed by *Sharī'ah* and consensus of the *‘ulamā*. However, some issues arise when it comes to combining of these three contracts under one. It is general agreement of the Muslim scholars that two contracts combined into one, where one of them is conditional for another, is not allowed by *Sharī'ah*. Therefore, *‘ulamā* put forward several conditions for this mode of finance to be valid from *Sharī'ah* point of view. These conditions can be summarized as follows:

- a. The agreement of joint purchase (*mushārah*), leasing (*ijārah*), and selling (*bay‘*) the financier's shares in asset should not be combined in one single contract. However, there can be one document joining the joint purchase and the contract of leasing. In this document the financier may agree to lease his shares to the customer after they jointly purchase the asset.
- b. Whenever the sale/purchase of new shares is taking place, it must be done through the exchange of offer and acceptance between the financier and the client at that particular time.
- c. Prices of the units of the financier's shares will be determined according to the market value at the time of sale/purchase. This is more preferable – according to Usmani. However, it is also permissible for the price to be agreed in the promise signed by the client.¹⁶⁷

Apart from the conditions put forward by Usmani, the following has been suggested by Bendjilali and Khan:¹⁶⁸ a) There should be promise by the bank to put its shares on sale at specific future date; b) The purchase of the shares should not be binding on the customer; and c) The prices to be determined at the time of sale.

The only issue at question here is regarding the determination of the prices of the different units of the financier's shares. As stated above, Usmani is of the opinion that these prices can be agreed in the promise signed by the client.¹⁶⁹ However, Bendjilali and Khan opine that it should be at the market value.¹⁷⁰ This is also upheld by the AAOIFI standards. It says that to acquire the shares at their original or face value is not allowed to be stipulate (i.e. predetermined), since this would guarantee the value of the shares of one partner by the other partner and this is against *Sharī'ah*.¹⁷¹ *Shaykh* al-Darir is of the same opinion as stated earlier. Although the prices can be agreed in the promise signed by the client according to Usmani, he gives preference to the market

¹⁶⁷ For more details see: Usmani, *An Introduction to Islamic Finance*, 33-34. Here he mentions this as permissible option. However, at the end he gives preference to the market determination of the price view.

¹⁶⁸ See: Bendjilali and Khan, *Economics of Diminishing Musharakah*, 17-19.

¹⁶⁹ Usmani, *An Introduction to Islamic Finance*, 33-34.

¹⁷⁰ Bendjilali and Khan, *Economics of Diminishing Musharakah*, 17-19.

¹⁷¹ Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions (AAOIFI), *Shari'a Standards*, (Bahrain: Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions, 2004), 214-215.

determination of the price of the shares. Therefore, it can be concluded that the prices of shares should be determined through market forces.

3.5 SALIENT FEATURES OF THE *MUSHĀRAKAH MUTANĀQISAH* PARTNERSHIP¹⁷²

From what have been said above, we can list down the salient features of the *mushāraakah mutanāqisah* partnership. They are as follows:

- i) Creation of joint-venture between the client and the bank on the basis of *mushāraakah*.
- ii) Profits are to be shared in accordance to the agreed ratio, but the losses are to be shared in proportion of capital invested by each party involved.
- iii) There should be unilateral, binding promise by the financier to sell his shares of the partnership on instalments.
- iv) The client voluntarily buys the shares of the financier which are to be priced at the market value at the time of the sale.
- v) The sale component of MMP contract is binding only on the financier.

3.6 ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF THE *MUSHĀRAKAH MUTANĀQISAH* PARTNERSHIP

There are several advantages as well as disadvantages in implementing the *mushāraakah mutanāqisah* partnership. We will briefly explain some of them in the following lines.¹⁷³

3.6.1 Advantages of the *Mushāraakah Mutanāqisah* Partnership

- (a) It is a relatively cheaper or more affordable mode of finance for asset acquisition, at least from a customer's point of view, than asset financing through either BBA mode of financing or conventional loan. Furthermore, BBA financing puts extra pressure on the customer and causes hardship for him/her.
- (b) The period for financing can be also shortened which would be beneficial for both the bank and the client. The former will receive the funds invested which could be reinvested into new projects. The latter will be able to acquire the needed asset in

¹⁷² I fully acknowledge indebtedness to Bendjilali and Khan for this subtitle. See: Bendjilali and Khan, *Economics of Diminishing Musharakah*, 19-20.

¹⁷³ Some of the advantages and disadvantages are mentioned in Meera and Dzuljastri, "Islamic Home Financing," 15, 19-21.

shorter period of time. This shows that MMP is, as compared to BBA, relatively more flexible mode of financing.

- (c) The financing and the payment of the instalments as well as the rent can be adjusted periodically to reflect the market changes. This makes the *mushārah mutanāqisah* partnership less vulnerable to the outside factors such as the movements in interest rate and inflation faced by alternatives (the BBA financing). It also gives financier better option for managing liquidity risks.
- (d) It is in line with *maqāsid al-Sharī'ah* which promotes *maslahah*, the welfare of the people, by making it easier for them, the clients, to finance their asset acquisitions. It removes the hardship from the people and serves public interest which is desirable. By hardship here we mean the hardship of paying overvalued price of BBA financing compared with MMP contract that reflects the market price of a commodity.
- (e) Using the *mushārah mutanāqisah* partnership model, the interest (*ribā*) can be avoided totally which makes this model more *Islamic* than BBA which mimics debt based mode of finance.
- (f) Under this model the balance of financing, at any point of time, will never exceed the original price of the asset. This is not the case with BBA as will be shown using example later on in this paper.
- (g) If implemented through cooperatives or mutual funds, this model can have a substantial impact on economy while being non-inflationary since there will be no creation of money as is the case under fractional reserve banking system.
- (h) The selling price, under MMP, always reflects market price and the rental payments are determined through market forces, while in case of BBA the mark-up price is way above the market price (i.e. it does not reflect the true market price of the asset).
- (i) In case of defaults, under BBA financing, Islamic banks are not allowed to charge any penalty. This can be avoided in case of MMP mode of finance. Here, in case of default the financier (i.e. the bank) will be entitled to receive higher rental payment since its share in property will remain until the customer resume payments later on. It is believed that this rent may have "a deterrent impact on a customer who evades repayment as it will remain fixed as long as no repayment of the principal takes place."¹⁷⁴ In case that the customer cannot pay even rent, then the property could be leased to the third party while the profit will be shared between the bank and the customer.
- (j) We have seen that in case of inflation the BBA financing is adversely affected. *Mushārah* financing guards the financial institution from the bad effects of inflation.

¹⁷⁴ Salama, "Housing Finance in Islamic Countries" 32.

As we stated above, the selling of the shares should be carried out at the market value. This means that each share will be sold at its own value at the time of sale itself. This way the effects of inflation could be taken into account. Therefore, from the point of view of financial institutions, *mushārah* financing technique stands better than BBA, *murābaha* or conventional loan since the financial institutions can secure a percentage of the value of the asset. This way when the asset appreciates with inflation, the shares of the financial institutions appreciate as well. Furthermore, if the asset is sold, the financial institutions' share will increase as result of capital appreciation.¹⁷⁵

3.6.2 Disadvantages of the *Mushārah Mutanāqisah* Partnership

- (a) It is less attractive for the banks since the *mushārah mutanāqisah* partnership would bring lower profits to the Islamic banks. By using BBA mode of finance Islamic banks earn higher profits with less risk and efforts invested in the projects.

However, following basic economic theories, as the price of the products/services decreases (in this case MMP mode of financing) the demand for that service would increase. Therefore, while the banks may lose some profits by implementing MMP, compared to the BBA financing, it will gain some extra profits and therefore offset some of that loss, by initial increase in demand for their services (i.e. MMP).

- (b) Since the rental price do change over the time and is dictated by the location of the property (in case of home financing), keeping track of these changes may not be an easy job for the banks. At the same time, as the rental rate increase it may be difficult for the bank to convince the customer that now he/she has to pay higher rental on the property.
- (c) Legal amendments may be needed especially with regards to the tax structure. This means that the law should be there to make sure that the customer is not taxed twice for the same property.
- (d) Land laws and the laws related to the Islamic banking and finance (i.e. Islamic Banking Act [IBA] 1983 and the Banking and Financial Institutions Act 1989 [BAFIA]) may have to be amended in order to allow banks to become legal co-owners of properties.

3.7 EXAMPLES OF MMP BEING PRACTICED BY SOME INSTITUTIONS WORLDWIDE FOR HOME FINANCING

The *mushārah mutanāqisah* partnership has been implemented by many Islamic financial institutions throughout the world. Here, some of these institutions and their practices will be highlighted.

¹⁷⁵ Salama, "Housing Finance in Islamic Countries" 31-32.

There are two cooperative financial houses in Canada operating on the principle of *mushārah mutanāqisah* partnership. These are Islamic Co-operative Housing Corporation¹⁷⁶ (ICHC) and Ansar Co-operative Housing Corporation¹⁷⁷ (ACHC), both based in Toronto and established in 1981. The purpose of setting up these Co-operatives was to help Muslims in Canada to buy a home without paying interest or mortgage. To become a member of Co-operative, an individual is required to buy shares of the Co-operative. In order to be entitled to get financing from the Co-operative a member needs to have shares equal to 10% of his/her outstanding mortgage balance as an investment in the Co-operative for at least six months. Once a member meets this requirement, the Co-operative will buy a house for this member to live, while paying fair and mutually agreed occupancy charges (i.e. rent). This rent is proportionate to the Co-operative's ownership in the house. At the same time, the members are required to buy more shares in the Co-operative so that their ownership shares will increase. As the shares of members in the Co-operative increases the rent will decrease proportionally, until the house is fully owned by a member. Once this is completed, the member will surrender the shares to the Co-operative while the Co-operative will transfer the title to the member.

There are also two successful cooperative institutions in UK providing similar services to those in Canada. In fact, the model used by ICHC and ACHC in Canada is approved by Muhammad Taqi Usmani, the renowned *Sharī'ah* scholar, and implemented by these two co-operatives, Ansar House Limited¹⁷⁸ (AHL) and Alburuq¹⁷⁹. AHL was launched in February 2000 and uses a Shared Ownership Scheme (S.O.S) applying *ijārah* (rental) mechanism. The client pays the rent for the shares of AHL in the house plus additional amount used to buy additional shares. As the time passes, the shares owned by the client increase and the rent decreases respectively. AHL provides up to 80% of purchase price and contract is between 5 and 15 years long.

On the other hand, Alburuq provides financing for buying a home up to 90% while the remaining 10% is financed by a client. In this case, Alburuq uses both *ijārah* and *mushārah* modes of financing, believing that these two methods of Islamic finance are the best solution for *Sharī'ah* compliant home finance in the UK today. Over a period of up to 25 years, the client will buy-back the shares from the Bank on monthly basis. By doing so, the Bank's shares will diminish while the client's shares will increase. At the same time, the Bank will charge the client the rent for the use of its share in the property. This rent is calculated based on respective shares owned.

¹⁷⁶ Available at: <URL: <http://www.isnacanada.com/ichc.htm>>.

¹⁷⁷ Ansar Co-operative Housing Corporation Ltd. (Canada), *An Interest-free Housing Scheme and A Good Investment Opportunity for Muslims*. available at: <URL: <http://www.isnacanada.com/achc.htm>>.

¹⁷⁸ Ansar Finance Limited (UK), *Services – House Financing*, available at: <URL: <http://www.ansarfinance.com/ServicesHousing.asp>>.

¹⁷⁹ Arab Banking Corporation, *Products: Home Finance – How Does It Work?*, available at: <URL: <http://www.alburuq.co.uk/Products/home%20finance/howDoesItWork2.html>>.

Besides these two co-operatives, the home financing attracted HSBC Bank in UK as well. HSBC's established Amanah Home Finance¹⁸⁰ which is based on the diminishing *mushārah* mode of financing. Under this model, HSBC buys a property jointly with its customer and it will be held by a third party (in this case HSBC Trust Company) who will hold it on trust for both of them. During the financing term, the client will pay monthly Amanah Home Finance payments to acquire shares in the property. This will cause the client's share to increase while the Bank's shares will decrease in the same proportion. During the same period, the client will pay rent for the property leased to him/her by the bank. At the end of the term, once all payments are made, the Bank will transfer the property into the client's name.

Islamic finance is expanding in the UK with Islamic mortgage worth £164 million with average annual growth rate of 68.1 per cent, showing its great potential.¹⁸¹ Some of the institutions, besides the above-mentioned, which offer Islamic mortgage, are Ahli United Bank, West Bromwich Building Society, United National Bank and the Islamic Bank of Britain.

American Finance House LARIBA¹⁸² (AFHL) is another example of successful implementation of *Shari'ah* modes of finance in US. AFHL is based in Pasadena, California. Its home financing model is based on "Lease-To-Purchase" (LTP) (*ijārah wa iqtinā*/diminishing *mushārah*) concept. According to this model, AFHL and the client would purchase the property together. AFHL agrees to sell its shares/units to the client, while the client agrees to re-purchase these shares/units. In this regard, AFHL allows the client to buy the property directly from the vendor and register it under his/her name. The client leases the AFHL's shares in the property and gradually repurchases its shares. The property is leased at market value which is defined by the location and specification of the property and mutually agreed between the AFHL and client. This rent value is divided between two of them in accordance with their proportion of their shares/units of the purchase price of the property. The additional amount is paid by the customer as instalment for buying back the shares/units of AFHL. Gradually, the client's shares in the property increases while the AFHL's shares diminish with each instalment, until the end of the financing period when the client will own 100% of the shares in the property.¹⁸³

¹⁸⁰ HSBC Bank (UK), *How it works (Home Finance)*, available at: <URL: <http://www.hsbcamanah.co.uk/amanahuk/home-finance/how-it-works.html>>.

¹⁸¹ Datamonitor Plc. (UK), *UK Islamic Mortgages 2005*, available at: <URL: <http://www.datamonitor.com>>.

¹⁸² American Finance House LARIBA (USA), *Home Financing*, available at: <URL: <http://www.lariba.com/financing/home-mail.shtm>>.

¹⁸³ American Finance House offers Islamic products to finance homes, autos, small business, home renovation, etc. in the following states Alabama, Alaska, Arkansas, California, Colorado, Connecticut, Florida, Georgia, Hawaii, Illinois, Indiana, Iowa, Kansas, Kentucky, Louisiana, Maryland, Massachusetts, Michigan, Minnesota, Mississippi, Missouri, Nebraska, Nevada, New Jersey, New Mexico, North Carolina, Oklahoma, Ohio, Oregon, South Carolina, Tennessee, Texas, Virginia, Washington State, Wisconsin and Wyoming.

This and similar models are also available in other financial institution in US, Pakistan, Australia, etc. Another example of Muslim community, implementing Declining Balance Co-ownership Program in US, is the case of Guidance Financial Group.¹⁸⁴ In Pakistan, Meezan Bank¹⁸⁵ developed a scheme called "Easy Home" that was the first Islamic home financing facility. This scheme also follows the *mushārahah mutanāqisah* concept of financing. In Australia the similar model is applied through Muslim Community Cooperative (Australia)¹⁸⁶, better known as MCCA. It was found in 1989 with the aim of providing a practical model of Islamic finance in Australia. Their home financing is carried out through *murābaha* and *ijāra muntahia bittamlīk*.

These models are also practiced all over the world. Some of the examples are also shown in the boxes provided. It is worth noting here that this models are not applied to the house financing only, rather they are being used in order to finance other asset acquisition as well. For example, it is been used for equipment financing, auto or car financing, business financing, etc. In fact, as stated by Obaidullah, *mushārahah* in general and *mushārahah mutanāqisah* partnership in particular are suitable for financing almost every kind of business ventures, be it manufacturing, trading or any other business where the bank is willing to become a partner.¹⁸⁷

3.8 COMPARISON BETWEEN CONVENTIONAL LOAN, BBA AND MMP

Let us take the following example as illustration: Ahmad, the customer, wants to buy a house with the market price of RM200,000. The customer places 20 per cent (i.e. RM40,000) as down-payment with vendor. The remaining RM160,000 he will finance either through conventional loan, BBA or MMP facility. For simplicity, let us assume that Annual Profit Rate (APR) is 10% per annum while the duration of finance is supposed to be 20 years. Conventional bank will simply loan RM160,000 to the customer with the aforementioned interest for the period. The Islamic bank, using BBA facility, would buy the house from the customer for RM160,000 and sell it back to him for an agreed profit with payments being deferred throughout the period.

The monthly payment for this would be RM1544.03.¹⁸⁸ The total amount due by Ahmad would be RM370,567.20.¹⁸⁹ The difference between this amount and the original RM160,000, equal RM210,567.20, is the profit for Islamic bank. Under the BBA mode of financing, this profit is

¹⁸⁴ Guidance Financial Group, *A Program Tailored to Meet Your Needs*, available at: <URL: <http://www.guidancefinancialgroup.com/products/ourprogram.asp>>.

¹⁸⁵ Meezan Bank, *Easy Home*, available at: <URL: <http://www.meezanbank.com/en/HouseFinance.aspx>>.

¹⁸⁶ Muslim Community Co-operative (Australia), available at: <URL: <http://www.mcca.com.au>>.

¹⁸⁷ Obaidullah, *Islamic Financial Services*, 64.

¹⁸⁸ This amount is computed using the standard formula for present value of annuities, i.e.

$$PV = \frac{Pmt}{i} \left[1 - \frac{1}{(1+i)^n} \right] \text{ which gives } Pmt = \frac{i(1+i)^n PV}{(1+i)^n - 1}.$$

¹⁸⁹ Found by RM1544.02 multiplied by 240 months (20 years).

capitalized upfront, while in the case of conventional banking, the interest due is only recognized with elapse of time.

Using MMP facility and assuming the price and down payment to be the same, we will have the following scenario: The agreed rental payment would be RM1,000 as an average rental for similar homes at that particular location. Ahmed is willing to pay additional RM146.30¹⁹⁰ in order to buy back the financier's shares within 20 years. Therefore, the total monthly payment under MMP model is RM1,146.30 (see table 3.1 bellow).

Table 3.1¹⁹¹
Comparison between conventional loan, BBA and MMP

Price of House = RM200,000	Customer Puts in RM40,000	Financier Provides RM160,000	Monthly Rental = RM1,000
	APR = 10%	APR = 10%	APR = 6%
	Conventional Loan	BBA	MMP
Monthly Payment	RM1544.03	RM1544.03	RM1,146.30
Total Payment in 20 years	RM370,567.20	RM370,567.20	RM275,112.00
Total Interest/ Profit to Bank	RM210,567.20	RM210,567.20	RM115,112.00
APR	10%	10%	6%
Balance after 10 years	RM116,838.55	RM185,283.60	RM103,251.20

The distinguished feature of BBA when compared with MMP and conventional loan is with regard to the balance of financing before the stipulated date in the contract. For example, if Ahmad wants to settle his debt after 10 years, he would still owe the bank the remaining 120 instalment payments; in this case it is RM185,283.60. This amount represents the interest paid for a loan over the 20-year period under the conventional mortgage plan. It is also clear from this figure that the amount due by Ahmad after 10 years is still higher than the original amount borrowed by him, i.e. RM160,000. It is obvious that Islamic bank creates extra burden upon the client and has negative socio-economic consequences. It is believed that, following the fractional reserve system, Islamic

¹⁹⁰ This amount of RM146.30 is found using Equation (3) from Meera and Dzuljastri model mentioned above.

¹⁹¹ The author acknowledges the use of the format of the table provided by Meera and Dzuljastri, "Islamic Home Financing," 13.

banks are “very damaging to the economy”.¹⁹² It is also believed that under this fractional reserve banking system, a customer using Islamic facilities through BBA owes more money to the bank than by using conventional modes of finance, at any point prior to the end of the period. It is for this reason that Islamic banking attracted even conventional banks to provide Islamic financing.¹⁹³

3.9 NECESSARY LEGAL AMENDMENTS

As we have already mentioned above, one of the disadvantages for the implementation of MMP financing technique are the legal issues arising from this mechanism. The main problem faced by this technique is related to the issue of double-taxation. Since there is no special law regarding this technique, the tax on this property would be charged twice. This puts an extra burden on the customer, who is obliged now to pay the tax twice. Firstly, as the cost of the bank included in the price and secondly, once the ownership is transferred from the bank to the customer.

However, this issue has been solved in some of the countries already implementing MMP technique. For example the Government of UK made several amendments to the financial acts in order to facilitate *Sharīʿah*-compliant financing. They have introduced Finance Act 2003, which is extended by Finance Act 2005 and more is followed by Finance Bill 2006. These Acts overcome the adverse impact of double stamp duty on real estate financing. Furthermore, it is believed that these Acts will result in more *Sharīʿah*-compliant property financing in the future ahead.¹⁹⁴

Quite opposite to the case of UK, many Muslim countries did not make any attempt to amend the laws in order to facilitate Islamic banking and finance. When it comes to Malaysia, the amendments are already made. The initial proposal for the amendments was made by Kuwait Finance House (M) Berhad (KFH). KFH opened the discussion with Bank Negara on stamp duty exemption for the *mushārahah mutanāqisah* financing transaction. The following are the purposes of this discussion:

- i) To exempt the *mushārahah mutanāqisah* structure from submitting an annual partnership returns as required under the Income Tax Act – Section 86.
- ii) To reaffirm that the provisions of section 2(7) applies also to the profit/income earned by the Bank from *mushārahah mutanāqisah* financing;
- iii) To achieve tax neutrality status for the financing scheme under the Income Tax Act 1967.¹⁹⁵

¹⁹² Meera and Dzuljastri, “Islamic Home Financing,” 10.

¹⁹³ Meera and Dzuljastri, “Islamic Home Financing,” 10.

¹⁹⁴ See: Neil Miller, “Push on the Government breeds Islamic finance success,” *The Lawyer*, 3 July, 2006, 8.

¹⁹⁵ I would like to thank a member of the working committee from KFH who provided me with the hard copy of the slides used for the presentation to the Bank Negara officials. These and the following details are derived from this presentation. *Kuwait Finance House (M) Berhad*, “Working Committee on Tax & Stamp

The discussion led to the relaxation of the Hire Purchase Act 1967. In addition to that in order to promote the tax neutrality policy, the Stamp Act 1949 was amended as well. All of this took effect in October 2005.¹⁹⁶

Therefore, we can see that Malaysian business industry is on the good track to achieve its goal of becoming a hub for Islamic banking and finance. Its move to solve the issue of double-stamp duty is going to make the introduction and utilization of MMP financing technique smoother and more efficient.

3.9.1 Income Tax Act 1967

Here we would like to briefly overview the Income Tax Act (the “Act”)¹⁹⁷. The followings are the relevant sections of the Act which are related to the MMP financing technique:

i) Section 2 (7) of the Act

“Any reference in this Act to interest shall apply, *mutatis mutandis*, to gains or profits received and expenses incurred, in lieu of interest, in transactions conducted in accordance with the Syariah.”

ii) Section 2 (8) of the Act

“Subject to subsection (7), any reference in this Act to the disposal of an asset or a lease shall exclude any disposal of an asset or lease by or to a person pursuant to a scheme of financing approved by the Central Bank or the Securities Commission, as a scheme which is in accordance with the principles of Syariah where such disposal is strictly required for the purpose of complying with those principles but which will not be required in any other schemes of financing”

iii) Stamp Duty (Exemption) Order 1987 – 1st Schedule (General Exemption)

“Paragraph 6. An instrument executed pursuant to a scheme of financing approved by the Central Bank or Securities Commissions as a scheme which is in accordance with the principles of Syariah, where such instruments is an additional instrument strictly required for the purpose of compliance with those principles but which will not be required for any other schemes of financing.”

iv) Section 2, Act 53 of the Act - Definition of “Partnership”

The “partnership” means an association of any kind (including joint adventures, syndicates and cases where a party to the association is itself a partnership) between parties who have agreed to combine any of their rights, powers, property, labour, or skill

Duty Exemption: Discussion Memorandum on Stamp Duty Issues – Musyarakah Mutanaqisah Financing Transaction for Kuwait Finance House (M) Berhad,” September, 2006.

¹⁹⁶ Bank Negara Malaysia, *Annual Report 05*, (Kuala Lumpur: Bank Negara Malaysia, 2006), 162.

¹⁹⁷ For details of this Act, please refer to: <http://www.kpmg.com.my/kpmg/publications/tax/22/a0053.htm>.

for the purpose of carrying on a business and sharing the profits therefrom, but excludes a Hindu joint family although such a family may be a partner in a partnership

3.10 CONCLUSION

The *mushārahah mutanāqisah* partnership is an equity-based financing technique available for Islamic banks. The legality of MMP is found in *Qur'an* and *Sunnah* and it is further supported by the consensus of the Muslim *ʿulamā*. This model can be easily applied in various sectors such as housing projects, financing cars purchase, financing working materials and equipments, financing business projects, etc. It has been successfully implemented for home financing in Canada, United States, United Kingdom, Australia, Middle East, Sudan, Pakistan, etc.

Since the MMP consists of several modes of financing (i.e. *mushārahah*, *ijārah* and *bayʿ*), its validity lies in implementing the necessary conditions. The main conditions are: (i) these contracts should not be tied-up into a single contract, (ii) the sale of the units of the financier's shares should be carried out at the market value at the time of the sale, and (iii) it should be done through the offer and acceptance.

It has been argued throughout the paper that the MMP, if implemented widely, would have several advantages over the BBA mode of financing as well as conventional loan. It has been shown that this mode would offer cheaper financing to the customers and help them fulfil their needs in an easier way while complying with the teachings of *Sharīʿah*. This is in line with the objectives of *Sharīʿah* (*maqāsid al-Sharīʿah*) since it leads to the removal of the hardship. The period of financing will be shortened which is beneficial for both, the financier as well as the customer. In addition to that, this mode would reflect the market movement and the price will never exceed the original price at any point of time. This is not the case with BBA financial technique. The interest rate (*ribā*) can be totally avoided and the financier will be less vulnerable to the market movements.

Unfortunately, the MMP is far from being perfect. It has its own shortcomings, even though, we believe, the advantages of MMP are greater than the shortcomings. The banks may lose some of the profits by implementing MMP, as the customers will pay relatively lower price under this model as shown in the example above, but they may recover some of that loss through the increase in the demand for their services. Furthermore, if we are talking about Islamic banks and their social responsibility then this should not be an obstacle. Current laws and regulations may not be in support of the MMP. Nevertheless, the laws may be amended if there is strong will from the private sector as well as from the government. The steps have been made in order to overcome the legal obstacles, but the laws are yet to be made. Determination of the rental prices could create some problems for the bank but it is not a serious one that should keep the banks away from MMP.

Finally, the examples presented in the paper are the best proofs for viability of the MMP. If the various institutions all over the world, even in the west, managed to implement this model successfully then it should not be the problem for the rest of the Islamic banks to do the same. In overall, we can say that the MMP is better solution for the Islamic banks to serve the needs of the Muslim *Ummah*. It is *Shari'ah based* mode of finance accepted internationally.

CHAPTER FOUR

IJĀRAH SUKŪK

4.0 INTRODUCTION

The future growth of the Islamic banking and finance industry is incontestable. Islamic banking and finance is a fast-changing entity with new developments taking place constantly. It is said that the Islamic banking and finance annual growth is between 12% and 15%. According to estimation, there are US\$350,000 million in Islamic funds, with US\$500,000 million in assets and around US\$13,000 million invested in Islamic bonds (*sukūk*).¹⁹⁸ The development is evident in every aspect of the Islamic finance industry. The Islamic capital market is not an exception to this rule. Since the issue of the first Global *sukūk* in 2002, the Islamic capital market witnessed a huge expansion. There is a dire need to develop new products in order to meet an increasing demand from the customers all over the world. Previously non-Muslims were sceptical about the Islamic finance, but today more and more conventional entities are looking forward to take a share in the growing industry.

In this chapter, special attention is given to the development of Islamic *sukūk*, namely *sukūk ijārah* (Islamic leasing securities). These instruments can be used for various purposes as will be seen from the examples. Compared to the BBA and MMP that are used for short and medium-term financing, the *ijārah sukūk* could be used for long-term investments. The characteristics of Islamic *sukūk* are very much similar to the conventional bonds with a difference in that the Islamic *sukūk* are asset-backed securities. In this regard, the risk and return associated with the cash flow of a particular *sukūk*, during the defined period, belongs to holder of that particular *sukūk*.

The global *sukūk* market expanded enormously. Within only few years since the first *sukūk* was issued, this market is worth billions of dollars. It attracted the interests of many corporate and sovereign entities all over the world from Germany to Malaysia, and from the Philippines to the United States.¹⁹⁹ One important characteristic of Islamic *sukūk* in general and *ijārah sukūk* in particular is that they can offer all the good things of conventional derivatives without being speculative.

There are different types of *sukūk* such as *salām* securities, *ijārah* bonds, *istisnā'a* bonds, *mudārabah* (also known as *muqāradah*) bonds, and *mushārah* bonds. However, in this chapter we will focus our attention on *ijārah sukūk*, its relevance in today's Islamic banking and finance

¹⁹⁸ Victoria Robson, "Picking up the pace of conversion," *Middle East Economic Digest*, vol. 50, no. 37 (15 September, 2004): 51. Business Source Premier via IIUM, <<http://www.lib.iiu.edu.my>>.

¹⁹⁹ Nathif J. Adam and Abdulkader Thomas, *Islamic Bonds: Your Guide to Issuing, Structuring and Investing in Sukuk*, (London: Euromoney Books, 2004), xi.

industry and try to explain, in a meaningful way, its nature and advantages for long-term project financing.

4.1 LITERATURE REVIEW

Development of Islamic certificates or *sukūk*, in today's form, started some years ago even though the Muslim societies used *sukūk*, originating from trade and other commercial activities, as papers representing financial obligations during the Middle Ages. However, that type of *sukūk* is relatively different from the current one. This difference lies in the structure of the current *sukūk*, as they are akin to conventional process of securitization. Through this process the underlying asset is transferred to a number of investors through *sukūk* or certificates representing a proportionate ownership of the asset.²⁰⁰

One of the first writers on the topic was Monzer Kahf.²⁰¹ In his paper on assets-*ijārah*-bonds (AIBs), Kahf suggested the use of AIBs as an alternative for bridging the budget gap. He is of the opinion that the *ijārah* contract is very flexible and amendable to a large degree. In this way it can be easily suited for different purposes.²⁰² He further discusses different forms that AIBs can take depending on the nature of the asset and the method and procedure of issuance of the bonds. Since he is focused especially on AIBs, he briefly explains the characteristics and economics of these bonds. In his second paper on *Use of Usufruct Bonds in Financing Public Utilities*, he is further elaborating the use of *ijārah sukūk* for financing public facilities such as water, public transportation, electricity, education and so on. In this paper, he discusses the characteristics of usufruct bonds, *fiqhi* issues related to those bonds and compares them with conventional common shares and public debt bonds. He concludes that the most important characteristic of these bonds lies in the fact that they are negotiable while at the same time they adhere to the principles of *Sharī'ah* teachings.²⁰³ According to Kahf, *ijārah sukūk* instruments are “only one form of negotiable instruments of financing based on the sale principle.”²⁰⁴

²⁰⁰ Muhammad Ayub, "Securitization, *Sukūk* and Fund Management Potential to be Realized by Islamic Financial Institutions," paper presented at the International Conference on Islamic Economics and Finance, Jakarta, November 21-24, 2005, p. 349.

²⁰¹ Monzer Kahf, "The Use of *Assets Ijārah* Bonds for Bridging the Budget Gap" in *Islamic Financial Instruments for Public Sector Resource Mobilization*, edited by Ausaf Ahmad and Tariqullah Khan (Jeddah: Islamic Research and Training Institute (IRTI), 1997), Seminar Proceedings No. 39, 285-307. See also Monzer Kahf, "Use of Usufruct Bonds in Financing Public Utilities," <<http://www.kahf.net/papers/english/USE%20OF%20USUFRUCT%20BONDS%20IN%20.pdf>> (accessed 20 September, 2006).

²⁰² Kahf, "The Use of *Assets Ijārah* Bonds for Bridging the Budget Gap," 287.

²⁰³ Kahf, "Use of Usufruct Bonds in Financing Public Utilities," 50.

²⁰⁴ Kahf, *Instruments of meeting Budget Deficit in Islamic Economy*, 36. This citation should not be confusing. What is meant here is that *ijārah sukūk* instruments are based on sale principle when traded at the secondary market. It does not mean that the structure of the *ijārah sukūk* itself is based on sale principle. See Chapter Four for detailed discussion on *ijārah* contract.

Iqbal and Khan²⁰⁵ discussed various types of *sukūk* and their implementation for resource mobilization in various Muslim countries. They argued that the modern societies' expenditures may not be met through the "classical" Islamic sources of funds. Therefore, we need innovative approaches for mobilizing resources for meeting public expenditures. Since *sukūk* are asset-backed instruments, it is believed that they can enhance the stability of financial institutions and markets. Furthermore, the authors opine that Islamic *sukūk* are better alternative to the interest-based debt financing.²⁰⁶ However, as *sukūk* are new phenomenon there are several issues, such as legal framework, that have to be further discussed and reviewed.²⁰⁷

Development of the capital markets in general and Islamic *sukūk* in particular are the topics of the research done by Syed Ali.²⁰⁸ His work is very much indebted to the previously mentioned works by Monzer Kahf. However, he contributed to the literature with additional, updated data and more holistic elaboration of the topics related to the Islamic capital market. He surveyed four Islamic Development Bank (IDB) member countries, Bahrain, Malaysia, Pakistan and Sudan. According to Ali, *sukūk* has a great potential for being a financial and risk management tool for both corporate as well as government sectors.²⁰⁹ Primary market for *sukūk* is going to grow further, says Ali, but secondary market is yet to be developed. For secondary market to grow, the *sukūk* should target more diversified group of investors. Some *Sharī'ah* issues arising from *sukūk* have to be solved quickly for stability and investors' confidence in this sector.²¹⁰

The most comprehensive research on Islamic *sukūk* has been done by Nathif J. Adam and Abdulkader Thomas.²¹¹ In this work they cover various issues related to the *sukūk* in general; from theoretical overview of *sukūk*, their types and characteristics to issuing and structuring Islamic *sukūk* instruments. It is a holistic view of Islamic certificates. These fast-growing instruments are gaining more and more attention from all over the world. It is believed that *sukūk* will be among the main factors of development in Islamic finance industry in the coming future.²¹²

²⁰⁵ Munawar Iqbal and Tariqullah Khan, *Financing Public Expenditure: An Islamic Perspective*, (Jeddah: Islamic Research and Training Institute, 2004), Occasional Paper No. 7.

²⁰⁶ *Ibid.*, 2.

²⁰⁷ *Ibid.*, 73.

²⁰⁸ Salman Syed Ali, *Islamic Capital Market Products: Developments and Challenges*, (Jeddah: Islamic Research and Training Institute, 2005), Occasional Paper No. 9.

²⁰⁹ *Ibid.*, xv.

²¹⁰ *Ibid.*, xvi.

²¹¹ Nathif J. Adam and Abdulkader Thomas, *Islamic Bonds: Your Guide to Issuing, Structuring and Investing in Sukuk*, (London: Euromoney Books, 2004).

²¹² *Ibid.*, 16.

4.2 NATURE OF *IJĀRAH SUKŪK*

4.2.1 Definition of *Sukūk*

The word *Sukūk* comes from the Arabic verb *صَكَ* (*sakka*), which means to beat, strike, to shut, lock (the door). The word *صَكٌّ* (*sakkun*) pl. *صُكُوكٌ* (*sukūk*) or *صِكَالٌ* (*sikāk*) is derivative from that verb meaning (instrument of) contract, legal document, document, deed, check, cheque.²¹³

Generally speaking, *sukūk* can be defined as "asset-backed, stable income, tradable and *Sharī'ah* compatible trust certificates."²¹⁴ Simply put, Islamic *sukūks* are representation of proportionate ownership.²¹⁵ Islamic *sukūk* are referred as Islamic bond, but Rodney Wilson says that, due to their unique nature, it is better to describe them as Islamic investment certificates.²¹⁶

Ijārah sukūk can be defined as "securities representing the ownership of well-defined assets subject to a lease contract, they may be traded in a secondary market at the prevailing price determined by market forces."²¹⁷ The AAOIFI defines it as,

... certificates of equal value issued by the owner of a leased asset or a tangible asset to be leased by promise, or they are issued by a financial intermediary acting on behalf of the owner with the aim of selling the assets and recovering its value through subscription so that the holders of the certificates become owners of the assets.²¹⁸

4.2.2 Conditions for Issuance of *Sukūk*

There are some conditions related to the issuance of *sukūk*. One of the most important conditions is the existence of the assets.²¹⁹ This means that any institution, be it government, monetary agency, the corporation, the banking or financial institution, has to possess the assets on its balance sheet before issuing the *sukūk*. Apart from that, these assets should not be comprised solely from the debts created through Islamic financial instruments such as *murābahah* and *istisnā*.

Another important condition for validity of *ijārah* contract in general and *ijārah sukūk* in particular is that both leased asset and the rental payment are clearly known to both parties at the time of the contract.²²⁰ Finally, the issuer of the *sukūk* should be capable to fulfil his obligation

²¹³ Hans Wehr, *A Dictionary of Modern Written Arabic*, 520. See also Ruhi Ba'albani, *Al-Mawrid: A Modern Arabic-English Dictionary*, (Beirut: Dār al-'Ilm li al-Malāyīn, 8th edn., 1996), 298.

²¹⁴ Ali Arsalan Tariq, "Managing Financial Risks of Sukuk Structures," (M. Sc. Dissertation, Loughborough University UK, 2004), 20.

²¹⁵ Khaled A. Hussain, *Banking Efficiency in Bahrain: Islamic vs Conventional Banks*, (Jeddah: Islamic Research and Training Institute, 2004), Research Paper No. 68, 21.

²¹⁶ Rodney Wilson in Adam and Thomas, *Islamic Bonds*, 3.

²¹⁷ *Ibid.*, 8.

²¹⁸ AAOIFI, *Shari'a Standards*, Shari'a Standard No. 17, Investment *Sukūk*, 298.

²¹⁹ A.A. Tariq, 20.

²²⁰ Kahf, "The Use of *Assets Ijārah Bonds*", 288.

indicated on the *sukūk* certificates. This means that underlying usufructs/services should be available to the *sukūk* holders upon redemption.

4.2.3 Structure and Mechanism of *Ijārah Sukūk*

Structure of *ijārah sukūk* consists of three parties, namely: the originator (or beneficiary) *ijārah sukūk*; the Special Purpose Vehicle (SPV) the issuer of *ijārah sukūk*; and the investor (*ijārah sukūk* holder).²²¹

Broadly speaking, the procedure for issuance of *ijārah sukūk* in theory is relatively very simple. For the sake of issuance of *sukūk*, Special Purpose Vehicle will be created. The originator (it can be government, corporation or any other financial institution) sells the asset (property, land, etc) to the SPV. The SPV will then lease the asset back to the originator. The lessee (i.e. the originator) will pay periodical rental payments to the SPV for its use of the asset. Then the SPV will issue the *sukūk*. These *sukūk* represent an undivided proportionate ownership in the leased asset. Hence, the *sukūk* holders, by purchasing the *sukūk*, become legal co-owners of the asset. As owners of the leased asset, they are also the lessors to the originator. Therefore, they are entitled to receive the rental payments. At the same time they are responsible, as the owners of the leased asset, for the cost of maintenance of the asset leased to the originator. By issuing *sukūk* to the investors, the SPV will be able to pay the originator for the purchase of the asset. Once received, the rental payments will be transferred by the SPV to the *sukūk* holders. Finally, at the maturity, the originator will redeem the *sukūk* from the holders and take the asset back into position.

As we can see the SPV is very important ingredient of the *sukūk* issuance. The role of the SPV is as similar to the role of *mudārib* whereby it pools the revenue of the assets, issues certificates and shares the streams of income among the *sukūk* holders.²²²

According to Iqbal and Khan, there are six steps involved when it comes to the structure of *ijārah sukūk*. These steps are as follows:²²³

- i) Government (or any other entity) creates SPV.
- ii) Government sells the Land Parcel's Beneficial rights to SPV for fixed period.
- iii) SPV leases Land Parcels back to the Government for LIBOR plus government's credit spread-based floating rental under a Master *Ijārah* Agreement. The use of LIBOR as a benchmark deserves a special attention. We may ask questions such as: Is it really Islamic to use an interest-based benchmark such as LIBOR for Islamic products? Does it violate the contract or does it make it less Islamic? If the LIBOR is used for Islamic

²²¹ Ali, *Islamic Capital Market Products: Developments and Challenges*, 30.

²²² See Iqbal and Khan, *Financing Public Expenditure: An Islamic Perspective*, 57.

²²³ These steps are generated from the Figure 1 by Iqbal and Khan. See Iqbal and Khan, *Financing Public Expenditure: An Islamic Perspective*, 59.

financial instruments such as the *ijārah sukūk*, how different they are from the conventional interest-based instruments apart from being asset-backed?²²⁴

- iv) SPV keeps beneficial rights of Land Parcels in Trust and issues Trust certificates.
- v) SPV collects *sukūk* proceeds and makes semi-annual return payments to Certificate holders exactly in the amount received from government from government as rent. This practice of semi-annual payments is also similar (or rather same) as practiced in conventional financial system. This shows how Islamic financial industry is converging towards conventional system as already claimed in this study.
- vi) SPV pays *sukūk* proceeds to government as price for beneficial rights for Land Parcels.

The following figure (Figure 5.1) shows the structure of *ijārah sukūk* taking into account the steps above and particular case of the Malaysian Global *Sukūk*.

Figure 4.1: Malaysian Global *Sukūk*

4.2.4 Sale of the Leased Asset

The *sukūk* simply represents the right of the owner of that *sukūk* or certificate over a specific asset or property. Two questions may be raised here: Firstly, is it allowed for the owner of the asset

²²⁴ Some practical issues will be dealt in more detailed later on in this chapter.

(lessor) to sell the leased asset while the contract is still active? Secondly, may the *sukūk* be sold/bought by the *sukūk* holders/potential buyers at secondary market?

The answers to these questions are relatively simple and straight forward. There is no restriction when it comes to the sale of the leased asset. The lessor, as the owner of the asset, has full right of disposition of the asset as long as that sale does not hinder the original contract of leasing. This means that the new owner should honour the existing *ijārah* contract. According to the Hanbali school of jurisprudence, the new owner must honour the existing *ijārah* contract and as such he deserves to receive the remaining rental payment from the lessee.

On the other hand, the *ijārah sukūk* represents ownership of the usufructs or beneficial rights. Every owner of a share is independent of other shareholders. Hence, the owner is free to lease out or sell his/her share(s) independently or collectively. Some argue that the sale of the *sukūk* should be allowed by issuing body and that *ijārah* relationship between the lessor and lessee should not be affected.²²⁵ Usmani stated that, “[s]ince these *sukūk* represent the pro rata ownership of their holders in the tangible assets... they are fully negotiable and can be sold and purchased in the secondary market.”²²⁶ This characteristic of *ijārah* is important for securitization of leased asset. Furthermore, it increases the negotiability of the *sukūk* on the market.²²⁷

This sale of the *ijārah sukūk* will be carried out at the market value. This will reflect the market evaluation of the present rent value, expected future rent and the value at the end of the *ijārah* contract.

4.2.5 Characteristics of *Ijārah Sukūk*

The characteristics of *sukūk* are very much similar to those of a conventional bond with a major difference that *sukūk* are asset-backed securities. There are two important principles underlying the *ijārah sukūk*, namely: securitization and *ijārah* (leasing) contract. Having these two principles in mind we will now try to briefly explain main characteristics of *ijārah sukūk*.²²⁸ The characteristics are as follows:

- a) *Ijārah sukūk* represents the ownership of well-defined and clearly specified usufruct/service

It is worth noting that *ijārah sukūk* are result of underlying *ijārah* contract. This contract is between the asset owner or service provider and the *sukūk* holder(s). As such, *sukūk*

²²⁵ Kahf, *Instruments of meeting Budget Deficit in Islamic Economy*, 36.

²²⁶ Usmani, *An Introduction to Islamic Finance*, 98.

²²⁷ See Kahf, “The Use of Assets *Ijārah* Bonds”, 288-289.

²²⁸ For detailed discussion about some of the characteristics of the *ijārah sukūk* please see: Kahf, “Use of Usufruct Bonds in Financing Public Utilities,” <<http://www.kahf.net/papers/english/USE%20OF%20USFRUCT%20BONDS%20IN%20.pdf>> (accessed 20 September, 2006). 22-31.

represents the financial right bought by the purchaser of the certificate. In other words, a *sukūk* holder owns utility/service itself.

b) *Determination of the price of ijārah sukūk*

The price of *ijārah sukūk* is to be determined by the market (i.e. demand and supply forces). The most important issue here is that the rental price must be known to both parties at the time of the contract. As such this rent can be increasing, decreasing or constant from period to period as long as the formula for increments, or subtractions, is known at either the beginning of the leasing contract or at the time this contract is renewed.²²⁹

Initial price of *ijārah sukūk* will be determined by the market forces, i.e. supply and demand for that particular certificate. This is in line with *Sharī'ah* as long as it meets the basic conditions for valid contract. Once a *sukūk* is acquired by an individual or an institution it can be resold at any price agreed by the contractors (i.e. buyer and seller). In short, the owner of the certificate may either sell it at any price, depending on the market value of that certificate, or hold it until the maturity.

c) *Issuers of the ijārah sukūk*

The *ijārah sukūk* can be issued by the original owner of the usufructs/services underlying the certificates or by someone else as long as that person/institution can pledge to transfer the services from the original owners to the *sukūk* holders. The example of the former would be if Malaysia Airlines (MAS) issue air transport *sukūk*, while the latter would be if, let say, Bank Islam or any other institution, issue air transport certificates on behalf of MAS.

d) *Negotiability of the ijārah sukūk*

As we have already stated, the *ijārah sukūk* represent the well-defined and clearly specified asset or usufruct/service that is to be delivered at the maturity of these *sukūk*. Without this tangible asset or usufruct rights there can be no *sukūk*.²³⁰ Due to this characteristic of *ijārah sukūk*, the owners of these *sukūk* can sell them at any time. This implies that *ijārah sukūk* can be sold/bought at any time by any seller/buyer. In other words, the *ijārah sukūk* are fully negotiable certificated that can be traded freely at the market. The price of the *sukūk* will be determined by the two parties (i.e. buyer and

²²⁹ Kahf, "The Use of *Assets Ijārah* Bonds", 291.

²³⁰ Zohra Jabeen, "Significance of Sukuk Securitization for Banks: Structuring for Risk Regulation and Pricing," paper presented at IIUM International Conference on Islamic Banking and Finance (IICiBF 2007): *Research and Development: The Bridges between Ideals and Realities*, organized by IIUM Institute of Islamic Banking & Finance (IICiBF), 23-25 April, 2007, Crown Plaza Mutiara Hotel, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, 3.

seller) and will be affected by the market forces. This means that the sale of the *ijārah sukūk* could be at higher, lower or at par value, depending on supply and demand forces.

e) *The end of the ijārah sukūk*

The *ijārah sukūk* will be terminated by either two ways:²³¹ (1) through the actual use or consumption of the usufruct/service by the owner of the *sukūk* during the maturity period; and (2) it can also come to an end by revoking the contract through new agreement between the issuer and the *sukūk* holder.

f) *Amortization of the ijārah sukūk*

According to Kahf²³² the *ijārah sukūk* may be amortized when they are bought back by the issuer from the market. As such, the *ijārah sukūk* can be used for open market operation by the Central Bank, especially if the issuer is the Central Bank itself.

Some of these characteristics and other features of *ijārah sukūk* are also listed in the table below (see Table 4.1).

²³¹ Kahf, "Use of Usufruct Bonds in Financing Public Utilities," 30.

²³² *Ibid.*, 31.

Table 4.1
Features of *Ijārah Sukūk*

Feature	Brief Description
Flexibility of sale	There is nothing that restricts the sale of the leased asset by the lessor as long as the new owner of the asset honours the <i>ijārah</i> contract. When it comes to the sale of the <i>ijārah sukūk</i> , the sale is allowed with permission of the original owner/issuer of the <i>ijārah sukūk</i> certificates.
Independence of ownership	<i>Ijārah sukūk</i> holders own the share(s) of undivided asset(s). As such they are independent of each other and they can sell their shares independently from other <i>ijārah sukūk</i> holder or collectively.
Flexibility of the price	The price of <i>ijārah sukūk</i> will be determined by the market forces (i.e. supply and demand). Even though the rent has to be known at the time of the contract, there is nothing that restricts this determination of the rent to be based on any available means such as LIBOR. However, the use of interest-based indices should be avoided whenever possible.
Flexibility of the issuance	The issuer of <i>ijārah sukūk</i> can be any entity that is able to pledge the delivery of the underlying usufructs/services that are promised on <i>ijārah sukūk</i> certificates. Therefore, it is not only governments that can issue <i>ijārah sukūk</i> , rather it could be any corporation or financial institution that need to raise the funds.
Flexibility of the duration of the contract	The <i>ijārah sukūk</i> certificates can be of any length, as long as it can render the stipulated usufructs or services.
Tradability/Negotiable nature	Since the <i>ijārah sukūk</i> is securitized by real asset(s) it can be sold/bought at secondary market at any price determined by the supply and demand forces.
Easy entry and exit	With the development of the secondary market, the <i>ijārah sukūk</i> will be easy to sell/buy. As such they can be a tool for liquidity management.
Securitization	Securitization of <i>ijārah sukūk</i> certificates transforms these certificates from leased assets to financial assets that make them tradable at the secondary market.

4.2.6 Application of *Ijārah Sukūk*

As will be seen later on from the most current example, the *ijārah sukūk* instruments can be used for various purposes. It was also pointed out in the literature review that the *ijārah sukūk* could be applied by Muslim governments for bridging the budget gap or for funding public utilities. The *ijārah sukūk* could be used to finance most, if not all, public utility projects.²³³ Similarly, financial institutions and corporations can use these instruments to raise funds for new projects development or it can be used simply for resource mobilization from masses. In overall, the *ijārah sukūk* instruments could be seen as fund mobilization tools for both fixed and working capital.

In addition to the examples that will be discussed in the following section, we would like to highlight few projects that have been financed, either fully or partially, through the *ijārah sukūk* instruments. One such example is the financing of the Putra LRT II project in Kuala Lumpur,

²³³ Kahf, “The Use of *Assets Ijārah* Bonds for Bridging the Budget Gap,” 50.

Malaysia. During the construction the financing was provided by Islamic banks in the following manner. Firstly, the Islamic financiers purchased the original contract(s). Secondly, they will supply goods and services from the supplier(s) to the company undertaking the project. Finally, they will agree to sell the goods to the project company at a fixed mark-up.²³⁴ The other example where the *ijārah sukūk* were used is the case of Hub River Power Project in Pakistan.²³⁵ The best possible example would be the Zam Zam Tower project in Makkah, Saudi Arabia. The details of this project are explained below.

4.3 EVOLUTION OF *IJĀRAH SUKŪK*: A HISTORICAL OVERVIEW

According to Adam and Thomas,²³⁶ the first *sukūk* was issued by Albaraka Group's Al Tawfeek and Al Amin Companies back in 1980s. However, at that time these transactions were not termed as *sukūk*. Then, in 1990, Citibank and Kuwait Finance House (KFH) purchased tankers and leased them to Olsen Shipping, a leading Norwegian shipping company. This issue of *sukūk* was not marketable.²³⁷ Since then, various *sukūk* have been issued throughout the world. Among them were the *ijārah sukūk* issued in Bahrain, Malaysia, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, Dubai, etc. Here we will briefly elaborate some cases from Muslim countries that issued *ijārah sukūk* and elaborate the evolution that took place historically.

i) Bahrain²³⁸

The Bahrain Monetary Agency (BMA) started issuance of *ijārah sukūk* since 2001.²³⁹ In fact, the first issue, of US\$100 million, was made on 4th September, 2001, while the second, a US\$70 million issue, commenced on 27th February 2002. The third issue of *ijārah sukūk*, worth US\$80 million, was made on 29th August 2002, the fourth issue, of US\$50 million, was initiated on 19th November 2002. The third and the fourth issues were oversubscribed by 210% and 476% respectively. The fifth issue, of US\$80 million, was made by BMA on 25th February, 2003. This issue has been oversubscribed by more than three times. The *ijārah sukūk* are issued by the BMA on behalf of the Government of the Kingdom of Bahrain. The

²³⁴ Mentioned in Mohammed Obaidullah and Rodney Wilson, "Risk Sharing and Management in Infrastructure Financing: An Islamic Evaluation" in *Studies in Islamic Banking and Finance in the 21st Century: Theory and Practice*, edited by Muhammad Anwar and Mohamad Aslam Haneef (IIUM: Kulliyah of Economics and Management Sciences, 2005), 31.

²³⁵ See *ibid.*, 31-32.

²³⁶ Adam and Thomas, *Islamic Bonds*, 112.

²³⁷ *Ibid.*, 112-113.

²³⁸ Rashid Khalid Alkhan reserved full chapter (Chapter 4) of his book *Islamic Securitization* for case study of issuance of *sukūk* in the Kingdom of Bahrain.

²³⁹ This information is derived from the Central Bank of Bahrain's website: <<http://www.cbb.gov.bh>>.

total value of medium to long-term *ijārah sukūk*, issued by BMA as of 24th August, 2005, was US\$1.21 billion, of which US\$1.14 billion was outstanding.²⁴⁰

The BMA also launched a debut issue of short-term *ijārah sukūk* (six-month) in August 2005 and this was the first of its kind available to Islamic investors. This issue, of US\$59 million (BD22.2 million), was 222% oversubscribed and paid 4.06% over LIBOR.²⁴¹ Due to this pioneer issue of short-term *ijārah sukūk* BMA won a prestigious Deal of the Year award. This award has been conferred by Emerging markets newspaper.²⁴² Short-term *ijārah sukūk* are issued on monthly basis and have a six-month (182 days) maturity. On the other side, medium and long-term *ijārah sukūk* are issued on an ad hoc basis and have a maturity of 3 to 10 years.²⁴³

ii) *Malaysia*

Ijārah-based securitization in Malaysia started with the Segari Venture.²⁴⁴ They issued *ijārah sukūk* for financing its power generator project. The issue was relatively small and low-profiled, but it led to the development of leased-based securitization in Malaysia.

Malaysia is seen as having a more relaxed interpretation of the *Shari'ah* compared to other Muslim countries from the Middle East. Therefore, the investors from the Middle East region were not that much involved in investing in Malaysia. However, all that changed in June 2002, when the government of Malaysia issued the first international Islamic bond, Global *sukūk* or sovereign bond. This issue of US\$600 million with five-year maturity was led by HSBC and was *Shari'ah* compliant on the global scale. It is supposed to mature in this June. It has been listed in Luxemburg Stock Exchange and the Labuan International Financial Exchange.

Bank Negara Malaysia (BNM) is constantly exploring other alternatives to expand the range of the Islamic financial products. One of its latest initiatives was to formulate a floating mechanism based on the concept of *ijārah*. It is believed that this floating mechanism will help in managing the risks associated with asset and liability mismatches. It could also give financial institutions greater flexibility in improving their operational efficiency.²⁴⁵

²⁴⁰ Kathryn Wells, "BMA sells first short-dated sukuk," *Euromoney*, vol. 36, no. 7 (September, 2005): 70. Business Source Premier via IIUM, <<http://www.lib.iiu.edu.my>>.

²⁴¹ Ibid.

²⁴² See "BMA wins prestigious award for sukuk deal," *Middle East Company News Wire*, 3 October, 2005, Lexis-Nexis, via IIUM, <<http://www.lib.iiu.edu.my>>.

²⁴³ Extracted from the Central Bank of Bahrain's website: <<http://www.cbb.gov.bh>>.

²⁴⁴ See Engku Rabiah Adawiah, "Securitization in Islamic Contracts," paper presented at *Colloquium on Islamic Bonds*, jointly organized by the Securities Commission of Malaysia and International Islamic University Malaysia, 24 June, 2004, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, 42.

²⁴⁵ "A growing hub for Islamic banking," *Asiamoney*, vol. 14, no. 7 (September, 2003): 18-21. Business Source Premier via IIUM, <<http://www.lib.iiu.edu.my>>.

The Government of Malaysia is very much keen to become a hub of Islamic finance industry. Responding to the continuous growth of Islamic finance and greater demand for Islamic investment products, the Government amended the Government Investment Act 1983 in June 2005 with goal to allow the Government to issue a wider range of Islamic securities. This amended legislation, renamed as Government Funding Act 1983, gives more flexibility to the Government to source funds from capital market through the issuance of *ijārah*-based and asset-based Islamic financial instruments.²⁴⁶

Bank Negara Malaysia *Sukūk Ijārah* was introduced by the BNM as a tool for liquidity management. The issue of Bank Negara Malaysia *Sukūk Ijārah* took place in February, 2005. It was done through a special purpose vehicle, BNM Sukuk Berhad, and its size was RM400 million. The Bank Negara Malaysia *Sukūk Ijārah* will be issued on regular basis with subsequent size ranging from RM100 million to RM200 million. It is believed that this instrument would diversify the liquidity instruments used by BNM to tackle the liquidity problem within the Islamic money market. In addition to that, this will serve as a benchmark for other short and medium-term Islamic bonds.²⁴⁷

In addition to all of this, Malaysia plans to sell new US dollar-denominated sovereign Islamic bond this year and it is supposed to be based on either *ijārah* (leasing) or *mushārahah* (partnership) principles. This is a part of effort by Malaysia to remain competitive with Bahrain and now Singapore as a major Islamic finance centre.²⁴⁸

iii) Qatar

In 2003, the government of Qatar wanted to build the Hamad Medical City (HMC) in Doha, Qatar. Due to that the government of Qatar, Qatar International Islamic Bank and HSBC established a joint venture special purpose vehicle (SPV), Qatar Global *Sukūk* QSC. The SPV issued *sukūk-al-ijārah* worth US\$700 million that will be listed on the Labuan International Financial Exchange. The structure and the features of it are very similar to the Global *sukūk* issued by Malaysia. Initially it was supposed to be US\$500 million, but because of great interest in *sukūk*, the government of Qatar increased its size to US\$700 million. It is due by October 2010 with a rent of LIBOR plus 0.45%. The rating agency Standard & Poor's (S&P) rated this issuance of *sukūk* with "A+".²⁴⁹

²⁴⁶ Bank Negara Malaysia, *Annual Report 05*, (Kuala Lumpur: Bank Negara Malaysia, 2006), 162.

²⁴⁷ Bank Negara Malaysia, *Annual Report 05*, (Kuala Lumpur: Bank Negara Malaysia, 2006), 159. See also: Ministry of Finance, *Economic Report 2006/2007*, (Kuala Lumpur: Ministry of Finance, Government of Malaysia, 2006), 110.

²⁴⁸ "Malaysia: New Islamic Bonds Planned," *Emerging Markets Monitor*, vol. 12, no. 39 (22 January, 2007): 9. Business Source Premier via IIUM, <<http://www.lib.iiu.edu.my>>.

²⁴⁹ Documented on the published terms for the Qatar Global Sukuk, QSC, circular of 8 October 2003. Website: <<http://lfxsys.lfx.com.my/others/qatar/Offering%20Circular%208%20Oct%202003.pdf>> (accessed 23 May, 2007).

iv) *Saudi Arabia*

The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia decided to develop residential facilities located in proximity of the Holy Mosque Makkah al-Mukarramah, named Zam Zam Towers (ZZT). This project is to be carried out based on *sukūk al-intifāʿ*, which is a variant of *sukūk al-ijārah*. This *sukūk al-intifāʿ* is developed by Munshaat Real Estate Company (MREC) and is fully compatible with *Sharīʿah*.

The MREC sold its usufruct rights for 24 years under the *sukūk al-intifāʿ* contract transferring them into negotiable instruments. These shares will be sold to potential investors. By doing so MREC will be able to pay for the rent of the facilities (which are under a built-operate-transfer (BOT) concession allocated to Binladin Group of Companies (BGC)) and earn profit from the difference between what it pays to BGC and what it receives from *sukūk* holders. Upon the completion of BOT period, the ZZT will be return to the King Abdul Aziz Waqf.²⁵⁰

In addition to this, the Saudi Arabian Mining Company (Maaden) recently announced that it is going to raise US\$11,000 million for the development of its two projects in the Kingdom. It is planning to attract as many investors as possible. For that reason, it is going to use both conventional and Islamic bonds. Out of US\$11,000 million, US\$7,000 million will be allocated for aluminium project that involves development of alumina refinery and aluminium smelter. The remaining US\$4,000 million will be used for a phosphate project for fertiliser production. This mixture of conventional and Islamic bonds may not be the best solution from *Sharīʿah* point of view. However, as Islamic capital market is a niche this step is very important at this stage of development of Islamic instruments.²⁵¹

v) *United Arab Emirates (UAE)*

Dubai is also competing for the domination of Islamic capital market. The government of Dubai launched US\$750 million *sukūk al-ijārah* in October, 2004. This issue is a part of the US\$4.1 billion investment intended for the development of the Dubai International Airport (DIA). Another issue of *sukūk al-ijārah*, of US\$1 billion, was made by the Dubai Department of Civil Aviation on behalf of the Dubai Government in April, 2006. The proceedings of this issue are also to be used to fund the third terminal project at DIA. Apart from that, in December, 2006 Dubai-based developed Nakheel issued US\$3,520 million *sukūk*, the largest ever Islamic bond. This is another feat of Dubai on the financial market

²⁵⁰ For detailed discussion on the Zam Zam Towers project and *sukūk al-intifāʿ* refer to the website: <<http://www.zamzamtower.com/>>. See also Iqbal and Khan, *Fianncing Public Expenditure: An Islamic Perspective*, 63-64.

²⁵¹ "Diversification gains," *Middle East Economic Digest*, vol. 51, no. 12 (23 March, 2007): 59. Business Source Premier, via IJUM, <<http://www.lib.iiu.edu.my/>>.

scene. Initially the plan was to issue US\$2,500 million, but due to the huge demand and oversubscription it was raised to the US\$3,520. It is also worth noting that 40% of subscription came from Europe. This fact indicates that there is a huge interest for Islamic *sukūk* even in the West.²⁵²

vi) *The rest of the world*

Besides the above mentioned cases where the *ijārah sukūk* were issued, the rest of the world is also following the trend. The unique case was the issuance of US\$400 million five-year asset-backed *sukūk* by Islamic Development Bank (IDB) in 2003. The IDB did not base its *sukūk* on *ijārah* only. Rather it securitized a bundle of leases (*ijārah*), mark-up sale (*murābahah*) and conditional sale of items to be manufactured (*istisnāʿ*). This issuance of *sukūk* was rated “AAA” and “AA” by S&P and Fitch respectively.²⁵³ According to *Euroweek*, geographically speaking, 70% of the deal went to institutions in the Middle East, 17% to Asia and 13% to Europe. Out of this deal central banks bought 40%, Islamic institutions 30%, banks 15%, investment companies 8%-10%, and the remaining was bought by retail and other investors.²⁵⁴

We are also witnessing a huge interest for Islamic banking and finance in the West. The Government of UK is the leading example. They are trying to make UK a leading financial center and are ready to make amendments to the existing laws in order to facilitate the development of Islamic financial services and instruments. For instance, in a seminar on Islamic banking held in London in September 2002, Howard Davies, chairman of the Financial Services Authority (FSA), stated in his speech regarding the Islamic banking:

... [the FSA] would welcome a soundly financed and prudently managed Islamic financial institution in [the UK], which would be good for Muslim consumers, good for innovation and diversity in our markets, and good for London as an international financial centre. But [the FAS has] to treat applications from Islamic institutions in the way it does those from other, conventional firms, to ensure that they can compete effectively and, in the long run, on a level playing field with conventional finance providers.²⁵⁵

²⁵² “The rise of sharia bonds,” *Middle East Economic Digest*, vol. 50, no. 50 (15 December, 2006): 56-57. Business Source Premier, via IIUM, <<http://www.lib.iiu.edu.my>>.

²⁵³ “Islamic bond market leaps forward with IDB’s \$400m,” *Euroweek*, issue 814 (01 August, 2003): 1. Business Source Premier via IIUM, <<http://www.lib.iiu.edu.my>>.

²⁵⁴ *Ibid.*

²⁵⁵ Cited in Ayman H. Abdel-Khaleq, “Offering Islamic fund in the US and Europe,” *International Financial Law Review*, vol. 23, no. 5 (May, 2004): 56. Business Source Premier via IIUM, <<http://www.lib.iiu.edu.my>>.

Since Islamic *sukūk* can be hit with stamp duty land tax several times in the UK, the UK's authorities are taking steps to overcome this obstacle faced by Islamic finance industry. They proposed the changes to the Finance Act in 2006 with the effect to take place by the middle of 2007. The proposed changes are supposed to give the same tax treatment for Islamic instruments as ordinary conventional bonds.²⁵⁶ This and similar moves initiated by the UK Government put it ahead of many Muslim countries (e.g. Turkey, Pakistan, Indonesia, etc.) with regard to the legal framework for Islamic banking and finance industry.²⁵⁷

It is clear from the above that the future of Islamic capital market is bright. The launch of the Dow Jones Citigroup Sukuk Index (DJCSI)²⁵⁸ in 2006 is a promising sign of further development of the Islamic capital market. The DJCSI is “the first index that seeks to measure the performance of global funds complying with Islamic investment guidelines.”²⁵⁹

However, the Islamic capital market is not free from problems. The challenges facing the further development of the Islamic capital market will be dealt later on in this chapter. In the following table (Table 4.2) you can see the ratings history of some *ijārah sukūk* issues rated by S&P.

²⁵⁶ “UK plans law to foster Islamic bonds by clearing tax hurdles,” *Euroweek*, issue 978 (03 November, 2006): 14. Business Source Premier via IIUM, <<http://www.lib.iiu.edu.my>>.

²⁵⁷ Turkey, Pakistan, Indonesia and some other countries are still imposing double stamp duty. Malaysia has already dealt with that issue and it made necessary amendments to the existing laws. To promote the tax neutrality the BNM amended the Stamp Act 1949, which took effect in October 2005. See Bank Negara Malaysia, *Annual Report 05*, 162. On the other hand, Turkey is really struggling with developing the Islamic banking and finance industry. Even though its population consists of 98% Muslims, still the chains of secularism do not allow for the sector to develop further. The Islamic banking and finance industry is reported to worth about US\$300 billion worldwide. Out of that sum, it represents only 3% of Turkey's banking sector, while in case of Malaysia and Kuwait it represents 10% to 12% and 22% respectively. For the details about case of Turkey see: Nicholas Birch, “Islamic banking struggles to find market,” *The Washington Times (DC)*, 10 July, 2006, A13. Regional Business News via IIUM, <<http://www.lib.iiu.edu.my>>.

²⁵⁸ Chris Wright, “Building a benchmark,” *Asiamoney*, vol. 17, no. 3 (April, 2006): 6. Business Source Premier via IIUM, <<http://www.lib.iiu.edu.my>>.

²⁵⁹ Quoted in *ibid*.

Table 4.2
Ijārah Sukūk Ratings History

Originator	Date of first rating	Issue amount	S&P rating
Malaysia Global Sukuk Inc.	June 10, 2002	US\$600 million	A-
Kingdom of Bahrain	Sept. 04, 2002	US\$80 million	A-
Kingdom of Bahrain	Nov. 11, 2002	US\$50 million	A-
Solidarity Trust Services Ltr. (Guarantor: Islamic Development Bank)	Aug. 11, 2003	US\$400 million	AAA
Qatar Global <i>Sukūk</i> QSC	Sept. 10, 2003	US\$700 million	A+
Bahrain Monetary Agency International <i>Sukūk</i> Co.	Feb, 18, 2004	US\$250 million	A-
Stichting Sachsen-Anhalt Trust	July 9, 2004	€100 million	AA-
Loehmann's Holdings Inc.	Sept. 22, 2004	US\$ ¹¹⁰ million	CCC+
Sarawak Corporate <i>Sukūk</i> Co.	Dec. 23, 2004	US\$350 million	A-
Pakistan International <i>Sukūk</i> Co.	Dec. 23, 2004	US\$600 million	B+
Islamic Development Bank	May 20, 2005	US\$1 billion	AAA
Tabreed 06 Financing Corp.	June 15, 2006	US\$200 million	BBB-
East Cameron Gas Co. <i>Sukūk</i>	July 31, 2006	US\$166 million	CCC+
Sharjah Islamic Bank <i>Sukūk</i>	Sept. 12, 2006	US\$225 million	BBB

Source: Standard & Poor's (S&P) website: <http://www.standardandpoors.com>

4.4 SECURITIZATION

Securitization is a quite young phenomenon. It is considered as the most important innovation of recent history. In plain English terms, securitization is “a process of transforming an otherwise illiquid asset into a liquid one.”²⁶⁰ Monzer Kahf defined it as, “putting certain income generating physical assets as a base of, or a guarantee for, the issuance of securities that are financial assets.”²⁶¹ Securitization can be done with regard to two categories, namely: securitization in equities and securitization in debts. Here, we will focus on the former category. Securitization, according to Rashid Khalid Alkhan, is a name for a technique that is used by the banks to transform a pool of

²⁶⁰ Engku Rabiah Adawiah, “Securitization in Islamic Contracts,” paper presented at *Colloquium on Islamic Bonds*, jointly organized by the Securities Commission of Malaysia and International Islamic University Malaysia, 24 June, 2004, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, 3.

²⁶¹ Kahf, “The Use of *Assets Ijāra* Bonds”, 293.

assets on its balance sheet into certificates that are negotiable at the capital market.²⁶²

Documentation of the contracts is encouraged by the *Shari'ah*. The Holy Qur'an says:

يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا إِذَا تَدَايَنْتُمْ بِدَيْنٍ إِلَىٰ أَجَلٍ مُّسَمًّى فَاكْتُبُوهُ وَلْيَكْتُب بَيْنَكُمْ كَاتِبٌ بِالْعَدْلِ وَلَا يَأْبَ كَاتِبٌ أَنْ يَكْتُبَ كَمَا عَلَّمَهُ اللَّهُ فَلْيَكْتُبْ وَلْيُمْلِلِ الَّذِي عَلَيْهِ الْحَقُّ وَلْيَتَّقِ اللَّهَ رَبَّهُ وَلَا بِيُخْسٍ مِّنْهُ شَيْئًا فَإِن كَانَ الَّذِي عَلَيْهِ الْحَقُّ سَفِيهًا أَوْ ضَعِيفًا أَوْ لَا يَسْتَطِيعُ أَنْ يُمِلَّ هُوَ فَلْيُمْلِلْ وَلِيُّهُ بِالْعَدْلِ وَاسْتَشْهِدُوا شَهِيدَيْنِ مِّن رِّجَالِكُمْ فَإِن لَّمْ يَكُونَا رَجُلَيْنِ فَرَجُلٌ وَامْرَأَتَانِ مِمَّن تَرْضَوْنَ مِنَ الشُّهَدَاءِ أَن تَضِلَّ إِحْدَاهُمَا فَتُذَكَّرَ إِحْدَاهُمَا الْأُخْرَىٰ وَلَا يَأْبَ الشُّهَدَاءُ إِذَا مَا دُعُوا وَلَا تَسْأَمُوا أَن تَكْتُبُوهُ صَغِيرًا أَوْ كَبِيرًا إِلَىٰ أَجَلِهِ ذَلِكُمْ أَفْضَلُ عِنْدَ اللَّهِ وَأَقْوَمُ لِلشَّهَادَةِ وَأَدْنَىٰ أَلَّا تَرْتَابُوا إِلَّا أَن تَكُونَ تِجَارَةً حَاضِرَةً تُدِيرُونَهَا بَيْنَكُمْ فَلَيْسَ عَلَيْكُمْ جُنَاحٌ أَلَّا تَكْتُبُوهَا وَأَشْهِدُوا إِذَا تَبَايَعْتُمْ وَلَا يُضَارَ كَاتِبٌ وَلَا شَهِيدٌ وَإِن تَعَلَّوْا فَإِنَّهُ فَسُوقٌ بِكُمْ وَاتَّقُوا اللَّهَ وَيُعَلِّمُكُمُ اللَّهُ وَاللَّهُ بِكُلِّ شَيْءٍ عَلِيمٌ (البقرة, 282)

O ye who believe! When ye deal with each other, in transactions involving future obligations in a fixed period of time, reduce them to writing Let a scribe write down faithfully as between the parties: let not the scribe refuse to write: as Allah Has taught him, so let him write. Let him who incurs the liability dictate, but let him fear His Lord Allah, and not diminish aught of what he owes. If they party liable is mentally deficient, or weak, or unable Himself to dictate, Let his guardian dictate faithfully, and get two witnesses, out of your own men, and if there are not two men, then a man and two women, such as ye choose, for witnesses, so that if one of them errs, the other can remind her. The witnesses should not refuse when they are called on (For evidence). Disdain not to reduce to writing (your contract) for a future period, whether it be small or big: it is juster in the sight of Allah, More suitable as evidence, and more convenient to prevent doubts among yourselves but if it be a transaction which ye carry out on the spot among yourselves, there is no blame on you if ye reduce it not to writing. But take witness whenever ye make a commercial contract; and let neither scribe nor witness suffer harm. If ye do (such harm), it would be wickedness in you. So fear Allah. For it is God that teaches you. And Allah is well acquainted with all things. (Al-Baqarah, 2:282)

Even though, this verse is dealing with the documentation (securitization) of debt only, the documentation of other financial rights, contracts and activities is encouraged as well, based on

²⁶² Alkhan, *Islamic Securitization: A Revolution in the Banking Industry*, 3.

analogy.²⁶³ Decision No.5 of the 4th Annual Plenary Session of the OIC *Fiqh* Academy,²⁶⁴ held in Jeddah 18-23/6/1408H (6-11/2/1988), asserts that any combination of the following four types of assets can be grouped together for the purpose of securitization:

- i) physical assets,
- ii) financial rights (such as the usufruct in *ijarah*),
- iii) interpersonal debts, and
- iv) money.

This resolution pays special attention to the share of each of these four assets in the pool used for securitization. It requires that if the money or the debts are dominating the pool, then the trading of these instruments should follow the rules regarding the sale of money and debts. It means that they can be traded only at par value. On the other hand, if the pooled assets are predominantly asset-backed then these instruments can be traded at any price prevailing at the market as result of the supply and demand forces. This raises some important issues. First and foremost, is it allowed to mix something that is allowed and something that is not (in this case a tradable assets and non-tradable or debts) and make it tradable based on the ratio? What should be the ration for such formula? Is merely 51 percent enough to make it tradable? Or, is this yet another way to get away with *ribā*? These and similar issues should be discussed in more details.

One may ask: What are the benefits of Islamic securitization (if any)? There are several benefits/advantages that can be derived from the Islamic securitization. Firstly, it enables the bank to change the structure of its asset by liquidating some portfolio of loans. Secondly, it helps the bank to mitigate, avoid or shift the risk and exposure to another entity (e.g. SPV). Thirdly, this represents the new source of funds. Finally, financial institutions have a comparative advantage in originating loans, hence securitization allows them to earn fees through lending and this lending does not expend its balance sheet.²⁶⁵ According to Adawiah, the securitization of *ijārah sukūk* begins with the identification of suitable asset that can be both sold and leased.²⁶⁶ Based on the above discussed structure of the *ijārah sukūk*, she concludes the following:

- a) The *ijārah sukūk* do not represent debts, but the undivided proportionate ownership of the leased (tangible) asset(s).
- b) Since the *ijārah sukūk* represent neither debts nor money, they can be traded at discount price, as opposed to money and debts.

²⁶³ Monzer Kahf, "Use of Usufruct Bonds in Financing Public Utilities," 22.

²⁶⁴ See: The OIC Islamic *Fiqh* Academy, *Resolutions and Recommendations of the Council of the Islamic Fiqh Academy: 1985-2000 – Jeddah*, (Jeddah: Islamic Economics Research Center, 2000), 61-66.

²⁶⁵ Derived from: Alkhan, *Islamic Securitization: A Revolution in the Banking Industry*, 18.

²⁶⁶ See: Adawiah, "Securitization in Islamic Contracts," 43-44.

- c) Because the *ijārah sukūk* represent the (real) leased assets/property it is tradable at any price prevailing at the market and mutually agreed between the parties.
- d) Due to all of the above, the *ijārah sukūk* are globally acceptable and considered as *Sharī'ah*-compliant securities.²⁶⁷

4.5 ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF *IJĀRAH SUKŪK*

4.5.1 Advantages of *Ijārah Sukūk*²⁶⁸

As everything else, *ijārah sukūk* has its own advantages as well as disadvantages. The followings are some of the advantages of *ijārah sukūk*:

- a) It increases the liquidity of originator and investor while reducing liquidity premium in other products of capital market resulting in lower cost of funding for entrepreneurs.
- b) The flow of funds to securitized asset market will increase as well.
- c) One of the main advantages of *ijārah sukūk* is their negotiability while still adhering to the *Sharī'ah* norms and principles.
- d) Through the capital market it can tap new and diversified sources of funds which will be seen as more attractive by institutional and passive investors.
- e) It can help development of capital market by allowing small players, who are specialized in securitization and issuance, to enter the market.
- f) Through the development of *sukūk* and specialized issuers the cost of funding will become lower again.
- g) It is seen as parking avenue for excess liquidity faced by Islamic banks currently.
- h) The *ijārah* contract, and therefore *ijārah sukūk*, can be contracted for any period of time and it can be renewed for as long as the asset exists.²⁶⁹
- i) Investing in *ijārah sukūk* is relatively less risky than investing in equities. At the same time, the income stream is fixed, at regular basis, while any dividends from the equity financing can fluctuate and is subject to variation.²⁷⁰
- j) An option of exit can be executed easily with well established secondary market (which is currently lacking).

4.5.2 Disadvantages of *Ijārah Sukūk*

The *ijārah sukūk* instruments are far from being perfect instruments in the market. There are several disadvantages of these instruments such as:

²⁶⁷ Extracted from *ibid.*, 44.

²⁶⁸ Some of these advantages are explained in Syed Ali, 47-48.

²⁶⁹ Kahf, "The Use of *Assets Ijārah* Bonds", 288.

²⁷⁰ Adam and Thomas, *Islamic Bonds*, 8.

- a) The use of the interest rate as a benchmark (i.e. LIBOR). Even though some would argue that there is no problem in using LIBOR as a benchmark, we believe that this practice mimics the conventional capital market. This way Islamic financial market is related to the interest rate which should be avoided at the first place. Islamic financial system should be free from *ribā* (this is the claim by Islamic economists and scholars, at least in the literature), yet we are using an interest-based benchmark for our financial instruments.
- b) The *ijārah sukūk* instruments are limited liquidity management instruments. This would be avoided by fully developing secondary market for these instruments and by having relatively large supply of these instruments on regular basis.
- c) Due to non-existence of a well-developed secondary market, the entry and the exit may not be that easy (if possible at all presently) as already mentioned above.
- d) Since the cost of issuance of *ijārah sukūk* is initially very high they can be used only by large corporations. However, as new issues are coming up and there are, more or less, similar to the previous issuance, the process is becoming more familiar to the potential issuer and therefore the cost is going to decrease in future.

4.6 CHALLENGES RELATED TO *IJĀRAH SUKŪK*

Since Islamic capital market is relatively a new niche and *ijārah sukūk* represents a quite new instrument available to the Muslim as well as non-Muslim investors there are several challenges faced in the development of this product. Simply said, the infrastructure for the development of Islamic capital market in general and *ijārah sukūk* in particular is yet to achieve its efficiency. The most prominent areas that need to be addressed are briefly explained in the following lines.

One of the challenges faced by the Islamic institutions that are trying to develop the capital market further is the lack of globally recognized standards. Bahrain and Malaysia established regulatory boards and institutions (such as Islamic Financial Services Board, International Islamic Financial Markets, and International Islamic Rating Agency) as a step to deal with this and similar issues.²⁷¹ In order to facilitate further development of Islamic capital market there should be more open dialogue between the Muslim regions in order to standardize the procedures and make it more accessible to the potential issuers of *ijārah sukūk*. This is the most relevant for the legal issues. Since there is difference of opinion among the regions, in order to make these instruments globally acceptable we have to implement the most commonly acceptable interpretation and make it as a

²⁷¹ “Islamic bond market leaps forward with IDB’s \$400m,” *Euroweek*, issue 814 (01August, 2003): 1. Business Source Premier via IIUM, <<http://www.lib.iiu.edu.my>>.

benchmark or standard. This is already taking place when it comes to the Global *ijārah sukūk*, but yet it has to be extended more widely.

Another problem faced by Islamic capital market is the lack of well-developed secondary market where the trading of the *ijārah sukūk* could take place. Non-availability of well-established secondary market is one of the major problems in Islamic capital market.²⁷² This issue is constantly raised by the Muslim scholars discussing on the topic. Without the second market the trading of these instruments will not take place and the optimum results will not be achieved. Furthermore, this will slow the growth of Islamic banking industry while at the same time reducing the volume of long-term investments.²⁷³ So far, there is no evidence of second market trading of the *ijārah sukūk*. This shows that the supply of these instruments is well shorter than the demand. It looks like there is indefinite demand for *ijārah sukūk* instruments at the current offered rates.²⁷⁴ As result we are experiencing, what Salman Syed Ali named, “*sukūk* trap”²⁷⁵ whereby the additional supply of the *ijārah sukūk* instruments does not push the prices down. The reason for such phenomenon lies in the fact that the *sukūk* holders tend to hold these certificates until the maturity. In other words, secondary market trading is not taking place at all. Ali recommends two solutions to promote development of secondary market trading:

- (i) Targeting more diversified group of investors. The issuers of *ijārah sukūk* should focus more on smaller investors. This way it will lead to more secondary market trading of these certificates; and
- (ii) The other solution would be to lower the return of the existing *sukūk* instruments. This would also increase the trading on the secondary market.²⁷⁶

Liquidity is yet another challenge of Islamic capital market. The question of liquidity is very important in economics and finance. This issue can be addressed through the securitization process. Due to its negotiable feature, Adawiah said, “securitization can create and re-create liquidity.”²⁷⁷ Both sellers and producers benefit from the liquidity. Furthermore, it improves their abilities to invest and expand their transactions. However, the liquidity is interlinked with the development of secondary market. Hence, to solve the problem of liquidity we have to improve the secondary market infrastructure.

²⁷² Hussain, *Banking Efficiency in Bahrain: Islamic vs Conventional Banks*, 23.

²⁷³ *Ibid.*

²⁷⁴ Ali, *Islamic Capital Market Products: Developments and Challenges*, 36.

²⁷⁵ The term coined by Salman Syed Ali. See *Ibid.*, 36.

²⁷⁶ *Ibid.*, 87.

²⁷⁷ Adawiah, “Securitization in Islamic Contracts,” 2.

4.7 PRACTICAL ISSUES

We have already raised several issues with regard to the current *ijārah sukūk* practices. Here we would like to highlight these practical issues that are of great importance for the validity of the true nature of *ijārah sukūk*.

First and foremost, the Islamic economics and therefore Islamic banking and finance are supposed to be interest-free system. Theoretically the models and modus operandi of the Islamic banks are discussed in such a way that there is no room for interest. However, in most cases we witness that it is actually conventional interest rate that is determining the destiny of Islamic economics. This is the case with any product developed by Islamic banks in general, and *ijārah sukūk* in particular. The use of LIBOR to determine the rental for *ijārah sukūk* or to determine the future price of the certificates undermines Islamicity of mode of finance. In order to make it really Islamic in theory and practice then we should base it not on LIBOR but rather on an index that is interest-free. As we already stated earlier, this practice of using LIBOR as benchmark mimics the conventional financial practices and leads to the convergence of Islamic financial system towards the conventional one.

In addition to that, the issue of the liability is crucial in this mode of finance as it makes profit lawful. This means that without liability of *ijārah sukūk* holders the profits that they are receiving are not lawful. As *ijārah sukūk* holders are owners of the leased asset(s) they are supposed to bear the risk and the cost of maintenance of that asset(s). If anyone tries to evade these liabilities by the owner, then the profit becomes unlawful from *Shari'ah* perspective.

Furthermore, according to Decision No.5 of the OIC *Fiqh* Academy,²⁷⁸ as mentioned earlier, any combination of the four types of assets can be grouped together for the purpose of securitization. The only condition put forward by them is that more than 51% should consist of assets. Money and debts can be included in this pool as long as they are representing smaller share of the pool. If this criterion is satisfied then the certificates created from this pool can be traded freely at the market. This practice of mixing tradable and non-tradable assets into one pool and making them altogether tradable based on the share of each is of suspicious validity from an Islamic point of view and needs to be re-examined.

4.8 COMPARISON BETWEEN BBA, MMP AND IJĀRAH SUKŪK

In the table bellow (Table 4.3), the attempt is made to compare the contracts that are main objective of this paper. In the table, the BBA, MMP and *ijārah sukūk* modus operandi are compared with regard to their features. This table is very much self-explanatory and needs no extra explanation.

²⁷⁸ See: The OIC Islamic *Fiqh* Academy, *Resolutions and Recommendations of the Council of the Islamic Fiqh Academy: 1985-2000 – Jeddah*, (Jeddah: Islamic Economics Research Center, 2000), 61-66.

Table 4.3
Comparison between BBA, MMP and *Ijārah Sukūk* contract arrangements

Feature	Brief Description		
	<i>BBA</i>	<i>MMP</i>	<i>Ijārah Sukūk</i>
<i>Nature of Contract</i>	Deferred payment, sale based contract. However, the underlying structure is based on <i>bay' al-'inah</i> .	Profit & Loss Sharing arrangement based on <i>mushārah mutanāqisah</i> and <i>ijārah</i> contracts.	Asset backed certificates that represent a proportionate ownership.
<i>Acceptance</i>	This practice is accepted in Malaysia. Since it is based on <i>bay' al-'inah</i> , it is considered as unlawful by the Middle Eastern Muslim.	This mechanism is internationally acceptable and considered as <i>Shari'ah</i> -compliant transaction.	The structure of the <i>ijārah sukūk</i> is seen as <i>Shari'ah</i> -compliant certificates and as such they are globally acceptable.
<i>Price determination</i>	The price is determined in the contract upfront and cannot be changed or altered at any time, i.e. it is fixed and more often than not it is priced above the market value.	The rental price is determined at the market value, as result of the forces of supply and demand. In other words, the price is flexible.	The price will be determined by the market forces (i.e. supply and demand) and the price is flexible.
<i>The length of the contract</i>	Fixed by the contract.	Flexible. It can decrease or increase depending on the redemption of the shares by the lessee.	The certificates can be of any length, as long as it can render the stipulated usufructs or services.
<i>Tradability/Negotiable</i>	The asset under the BBA cannot be traded as the bank did not secure the ownership of the asset fully.	The shares in the partnership can be transferred/traded to the third party as long as they do not invalidate the original partnership contract	Due to the asset backed securitization the <i>sukūk</i> are negotiable at the secondary market at any price determined by the supply and demand forces.
<i>Easy entry and exit</i>	The client is still obliged to repay the debt even if he defaulted.	Any side of the contract can easily cancel the contract (as long as it does not hurt the other party) by selling off his/her shares.	With the development of the secondary market, the <i>ijārah sukūk</i> will be easy to sell/buy.

Table 4.3 - Continued

Feature	Brief Description		
	<i>BBA</i>	<i>MMP</i>	<i>Ijārah Sukūk</i>
<i>Seigniorage</i>	It results in creation of money from nothing as Islamic banks operate under fractional reserve system.	If implemented through co-operatives then there will be no creation of money at all. Otherwise it can be present to some extent, but less than in case of BBA.	Since <i>sukūk</i> are fully asset-backed securities, there is no creation of money at all.
<i>Practical issues</i>	Interest rate is used for the determination of the future price for the BBA product. It mimics the conventional loan the best.	LIBOR is used for the determination of the rental price that undermines its Islamicity as well.	Using LIBOR as benchmark, mixing tradable and non-tradable goods into one pool and the liability of the <i>sukūk</i> holders are some of the issues.
<i>Effect on economy</i>	It is inflationary in nature, as the result of creation of money.	Being non-inflationary, if implemented through co-operatives or mutual funds, this model can have a positive impact on economy.	Since <i>sukūk</i> are based on real asset, it is believed that these arrangements will enhance the stability of financial institutions and market in particular and economy in general.
<i>Vulnerability^a</i>	In both inflationary and deflationary environment or in the case of rise/fall of interest rate the BBA transactions are severely affected.	Since the price of the rent and shares is determined according to the market, the negative effects of the inflation/deflation can be addressed more efficiently.	<i>Sukūk</i> are priced at the market value that can incorporate any changes happening in the economy such as inflation, deflation or rise/fall of the interest rate.

^a Vulnerability in terms of the effects that inflation, deflation or rise/fall of interest rate have on these contract.

4.9 CONCLUSION

In this chapter we have elaborated the *ijārah sukūk* as possible tools for investment purposes. The main conclusions arising from this chapter can be summarized in the following way. The *ijārah sukūk* are applicable to almost all financing purposes while adhering to the *Sharī'ah* rulings as they are asset-backed instruments. Since these instruments are asset-backed, they can be traded freely at the secondary market as they are negotiable instruments. This is one of the most important characteristics, among many, of the *ijārah sukūk*. These instruments can be used to address the liquidity problem faced by the Islamic banks.

Securitization is another area covered in this chapter with special attention given to the *ijārah sukūk* securitization. Securitization transforms otherwise illiquid assets into liquid ones, making them tradable. The importance of securitization of the *ijārah sukūk* instruments is seen from the fact that without securitization there would be no *ijārah sukūk*. Consequently, the trade of the *ijārah sukūk* certificates would not take place.

However, as with any new developing product, the *ijārah sukūk* are not free from problems. Islamic capital market, even though having great potential, is far from being efficient and several issues are highlighted. Among them, the most prominent ones are lack of the well-defined, well-structured secondary market and lack of standards. Some suggestions for these problems are rightly indicated.

The practical issues discussed still remain to be addressed efficiently by Muslim scholars. In order to differentiate the *ijārah sukūk* from the conventional bonds we have to make it unique by using special Islamic benchmark. This issue is partially addressed by the introduction of Dow Jones Citigroup Sukuk Index (DJCSI). Furthermore, without bearing the risk and liability the *sukūk* holder is not liable to receive any profit. Therefore the due attention has to be given to this matter in the future issuance of the *ijārah sukūk* certificates.

Finally, the comparison is made between the BBA, MMP and the *ijārah sukūk* modus operandi. From the tabular presentation (Table 4.3), which is derived from the paper, it can be seen that MMP and the *ijārah sukūk* instruments are far more in line with *maqāsid al-Sharī'ah*. Hence, these contracts should prevail over the contentious BBA financing technique. However, even within these two instruments (MMP and the *ijārah sukūk*) the problems still remain unsolved. The most prominent one is the problem of benchmarking where the LIBOR is used instead of Islamic benchmark.

CHAPTER FIVE

RESEARCH FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

5.0 INTRODUCTION

In the previous chapters we have elaborated issues related to the BBA, MMP and *Ijārah Sukūk*. These financial techniques are theoretically explained and issues about them have been raised. Throughout the paper we have promoted MMP and *Ijārah Sukūk* as substitutes and/or compliments to the BBA mode of financing. In this chapter we will try to investigate the perception of the banking officers, academicians and students towards BBA, MMP and *Ijārah Sukūk*. To evaluate this perception we used primary data collected using a questionnaire sample.

This chapter provides descriptive statistics based on responses obtained from a questionnaire sample. We would like to find out how much these groups are aware of these products offered by Islamic banks. We would also like to justify whether our claims that MMP and *Ijārah Sukūk* are better alternatives are true. In addition to that, respondents' views and perception of Islamic financial products are evaluated.

5.1 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is based on a sample survey and it is mainly descriptive. This survey consisted of 39 questions divided into five (5) parts (See Appendix B for a sample of questionnaire). First section consisted of 6 questions covering respondent's personal information. Section two had 12 questions regarding BBA mode of finance. Section three consisted of one question on respondent's familiarity about MMP mode of finance and 8 sub-questions related to the MMP. These 8 sub-questions were not applicable to those respondents who answered 'No' on the first question in the section three. Section four covered BBA, MMP and *Ijārah Sukūk*. Finally, in the section five we left empty space for participants to write down their own comments and suggestions regarding the issues raised by the survey.

The questions were mainly close-ended questions addressing the issues related to BBA, MMP and *Ijārah Sukūk*. Before the questionnaire has been sent to respondents several individuals within International Islamic University Malaysia (IIUM), who are well versed in the survey creation, have been consulted. After their approval and after receiving the official letter from the IIUM's official for conducting a survey, we approached Islamic banks in Malaysia for the purpose of collecting data from their employees. From the ten Islamic banks listed on Bank Negara's (Central Bank of Malaysia) website eight of them participated in this research plus Bank Negara

itself.¹ In this questionnaire we mainly used Likert-type scale ranging from ‘strongly disagree’, ‘disagree’, ‘no comment’ (‘neutral’), ‘agree’ to ‘strongly agree’ and the respondents were asked to give their opinions on various issues and claims regarding BBA, MMP and *Ijārah Sukūk*.

We adopted two strategies for conducting survey and getting the answers. First one is the self-administered questionnaire approach using the drop-off survey methodology that was implemented in case of Islamic bank operating in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia. The self-administered approach was implemented due to these two reasons: (i) we believe that this way we would show to the banks the seriousness of this research; (ii) this way the researcher would avoid obstacles such as time constraint and financial problems. The target population for this survey was banking officers working in Islamic banks. We narrow it down to the bank officers because we would like to find out their views regarding the products that are the main topic of this study.

The other methodology was an online questionnaire. This methodology was introduced in order to get response from the academicians, students and other Islamic banks that may not be necessary operating in Malaysia. For this methodology a specially structured survey was created in order to facilitate the online completion of the questionnaire. We intended to have two sample populations: one consisting mainly of bank officers working in Islamic banks in Malaysia and another consisting of academicians, student and bank officers from banks not operating in Malaysia.

5.2 DATA COLLECTION

The data collection was carried on from July 20 to August 3, 2007. As we already mentioned, for Islamic banks operating in Malaysia we used drop-off methodology. We approached each bank separately and handed over the sample questionnaires to be filled up by the employees of that particular bank. Out 90 questionnaires that were given out to the eight banks, 50 were returned. Out of these 50 questionnaires, 45 were completed correctly and therefore deemed to be usable for this study, yielding a response rate of 50 percent. This response was considered large enough and sufficient for statistical reliability and generalization.

With regard to the online questionnaire during the same period the researcher sent 70 e-mails to the academicians, students and bank officers outside Malaysia. Out of these 70 questionnaires the researcher received 34 with one incomplete questionnaire. As result, 33 questionnaires were

¹ Fully fledged Islamic banks that are offering Islamic products in Malaysia are: Al Rajhi Banking & Investment Corporation (Malaysia) Berhad, Affin Islamic Bank Berhad, AmIslamic Bank Berhad, Bank Islam Malaysia Berhad, Bank Muamalat Malaysia Berhad, CIMB Islamic Bank Berhad, EONCAP Islamic Bank Berhad, Hong Leong Islamic Bank Berhad, Kuwait Finance House (Malaysia) Berhad, and RHB ISLAMIC Bank Berhad. Source Bank Negara’s website: www.bnm.gov.my. The following eight banks participated in the research: Al Rajhi Banking & Investment Corporation (Malaysia) Berhad, Bank Islam Malaysia Berhad, Bank Muamalat Malaysia Berhad, CIMB Islamic Bank Berhad, EONCAP Islamic Bank Berhad, Hong Leong Islamic Bank Berhad, Kuwait Finance House (Malaysia) Berhad, and RHB ISLAMIC Bank Berhad plus Central Bank of Malaysia.

complete and used for this research. The response rate for the online questionnaire was 47.1 percent. Therefore, total number of questionnaires that were complete and usable for this research is 78, out of 160 questionnaires distributed (90 drop-off and 70 online questionnaires respectively). The combined response rate is therefore 48.75 percent, which is relatively high and sufficient for analysis (see Table 5.1 below).

Table 5.1
Distribution of Questionnaires and Response Rate

Respondents	No. Issued	No. Returned	No. of Usable	% Usable
Islamic Bank in Malaysia	90	50	45	50
Online Survey	70	34	33	47.1
Total	160	84	78	48.75

5.3 FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

5.3.1 Profile Analysis

As mentioned earlier, a total of 78 responses were collected from a total of 160 distributed questionnaires. The respondents were classified by gender, age, marital status, education level, occupation and knowledge of Islamic financial products.

According to Table 5.2 below, we can see that out of 78 respondents, 67.9% were male, and 32.1% were female. Of those 78 respondents, 6.4% were below 25 years old, 88.5% between 25 and 50 years old, while remaining 5.1% were above 50 years old. It is also obvious from the table that married respondents were majority in this survey representing 66.7% of the total. Remaining 33.3% were single. Consequently, we can conclude that the opinions expressed in this survey reflect the views and perceptions of married, middle-aged male.

Table 5.2
Distribution of Respondents by Gender, Age, and Marital Status

		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	53	67.9
	Female	25	32.1
Age	Below 25	5	6.4
	25 - 50	69	88.5
	Above 50	4	5.1
Marital status	Single	26	33.3
	Married	52	66.7

Table 5.3 (see below) shows distributions of respondents by level of education, occupation and knowledge of Islamic products. The table clearly shows that 34.6% of respondents had degree and master degree respectively, 17.9% were with Ph.D., while 12.8% were respondents with diploma or other certificates. When it comes to the occupation criteria, it can be seen that in this survey 7.7% were students, 21.8% were academicians, 56.4% were bank officers, and 14.1% were others. Hence, the majority of our respondents are bank officers with either degree or master degree and good knowledge of Islamic products.

Table 5.3
Distribution of Respondents by Education, Occupation and Knowledge about Islamic Products

		Frequency	Percentage
Education	Degree	27	34.6
	Master	27	34.6
	Ph.D.	14	17.6
	Other	10	12.8
Occupation	Student	6	7.7
	Academicians	17	21.8
	Bank Officer	44	56.4
	Other	11	14.1
Knowledge about Islamic products	Poor	2	2.6
	Average	21	26.9
	Good	30	38.5
	Very Good	13	16.7
	Excellent	12	15.4

Form the two tables above it can be concluded that majority of our respondents were married, middle-aged male who had either degree or master degree, working in Islamic bank and had good knowledge of Islamic products. This results show that the participants of this research were qualified and suitable for analysis of this study.

5.3.2 BBA Analysis

Section B of the questionnaire dealt with issues related to the BBA. This part consisted of 12 statements, each dealing with some aspect of BBA as a mode of finance. According to Table 5.4 below, the estimated Chi-Square statistics are significant except statement number nine. It means that variables do not have a uniform distribution. So the null hypothesis that the values have the same frequency can be rejected. The table shows that 89.7% and 9% of participants ‘strongly agree’ and ‘agree’ respectively with the first statement that says: “*The products of Islamic banks should be*

in line with *Shari'ah*". Only 1.3% of participants were neutral. It should be noted that there was no participant who disagrees with this statement.

Table 5.4
Respondents' Perception of BBA

Statement	SD %	D %	NC %	A %	SA %	Chi ²	df	Sig
1. The products of Islamic banks should be in line with <i>Shari'ah</i>	-	-	1.3	9	89.7	112.3	2	.000
2. Profit and Loss Sharing (PLS) modes of finance are true representative of Islamic financial system	2.6	9	10.3	35.9	42.3	49.56	4	.000
3. Interest is not <i>ribā</i> . Therefore conventional banking is acceptable	80.8	7.7	1.3	6.4	3.8	180.9	4	.000
4. BBA as practiced in Malaysia is in accordance to the <i>Shari'ah</i>	5.1	23.1	39.7	23.1	9	29.30	4	.000
5. BBA is a 'back-door' to the interest	12.8	23.1	35.9	21.8	6.4	19.56	4	.001
6. BBA promotes the Objectives of <i>Shari'ah</i> (<i>maqāsid al-Shari'ah</i>) including the welfare of the society	6.4	21.8	33.3	26.9	11.5	18.92	4	.001
7. Using interest rate (<i>ribā</i>) as a benchmark for BBA financing should be avoided	9	14.1	16	26.9	33.3	15.33	4	.004
8. Using interest rate as a benchmark for BBA financing brings a lot of doubts about Islamicity of BBA	6.4	17.9	15.4	32.1	28.2	16.48	4	.002
9. BBA financing indirectly involves interest rate (<i>ribā</i>)	19.2	19.2	28.2	23.1	10.3	6.74	4	.150
10. Current practices of Islamic banks will lead to a convergence of Islamic banks towards conventional counterparts	10.3	10.3	35.9	30.8	12.8	23.79	4	.000
11. Due to its fixed nature, BBA is relatively more expensive than conventional loan	9	21.8	21.8	32.1	15.4	11.48	4	.022
12. BBA seems unjust in cases of early settlement	7.7	28.2	29.5	23.1	11.5	15.2	4	.004

Note. SD (Strongly Disagree), D (Disagree), NC (No Comment), A (Agree), and SA (Strongly Agree), Chi² (Chi Square), df (Degree of Freedom), Sig (Significance).

Majority of writers on Islamic economics and finance argue that Islamic banking and finance are to be based on profit and loss sharing (PLS) mechanism. As result the second statement was presented to the participants in order to get their views on the topic. The statement reads: "*Profit and Loss Sharing (PLS) modes of finance are true representative of Islamic financial system*". From the Table 5.4 we see that only 11.6% disagree with this statement; 9% disagree and 2.6% strongly disagree with the statement. On the other hand, 35.9% and 42.3% (total 78.2%) of participants agree and strongly agree respectively with the statement two. Only 10.3% are those who did not comment or were neutral on the issue. As result shown from evaluating this statement, the support for PLS modes of finance is very strong. However, the reality is quite opposite. The debt-based modes of financing are dominating Islamic banks' portfolios, as shown in the previous chapters (see chapter two for that matter). The results collected from this statement only support what has been already

discussed by Muslim scholars 30 or 40 years ago. This result should be transformed into reality so that Islamic banking and finance can distinguish itself from conventional counterparts and develop further.

Some quarters argue that contemporary interest is not *ribā* and therefore conventional loan is not *harām*. In order to find out what is the opinion of our correspondents, we stated following statement: “*Interest is not ribā. Therefore conventional banking is acceptable*”. As can be seen from the Table, 80.8% of participants ‘strongly disagree’ and 7.7% of them ‘disagree’ with this statement; 1.3% had ‘no comment’ on the statement. Only 6.4% are those who ‘agree’ and 3.8% those who ‘strongly disagree’ with the statement. Therefore, we can conclude that our respondents consider interest as *ribā*. Hence conventional banking is not acceptable.

When it comes to *Shari‘ah*-compliance of BBA as a mode of finance, we have raised several issues. Many authors are consistently arguing that BBA, as practiced in Malaysia (i.e. modus of operandi of BBA in Malaysia) is not in line with *Shari‘ah*. Some advocates of this view have been mentioned throughout chapter two. The fourth statement referred to this issue. It states: “*BBA as practiced in Malaysia is in accordance to the Shari‘ah*”. The results were mixed. The majority of participants, 39.7%, were neutral, 23.1% of participants ‘disagree’ and the same percentage ‘agree’ with the statement, while 5.1% ‘strongly disagree’, and 9% ‘strongly agree’ with the statement.

Statement five says: “*BBA is a ‘back-door’ to the interest*”. The results are also mixed as is the case for the previous statement. Majority of the respondents, 35.9%, had ‘no comment’ for answer, 12.8% ‘strongly disagree’, 23.1% ‘disagree’ with this statement. On the other hand, 21.8% ‘agree’ and 6.4% ‘strongly agree’ with the statement that BBA is a ‘back-door’ to the interest.

The Objectives of *Shari‘ah* (*maqāsid al- Shari‘ah*) received a huge attention in this study. Lately, *maqāsid al- Shari‘ah* has become the major concern of those writing on Islamic banking and finance. How does BBA financing fit into that picture was our concern. In that regard the sixth statement was raised. It says: “*BBA promotes the Objectives of Shari‘ah (maqāsid al- Shari‘ah) including the welfare of the society*”. ‘No comment’ for an answer had 33.3% of the respondents, 26.9% ‘agree’ and 11.5% ‘strongly agree’ with this statement (38.4% combined ‘agree’ and ‘strongly agree’). The respondents that ‘strongly disagree’ and ‘disagree’ with this statement were 6.4% and 21.8% respectively.

Throughout this research we have questioned the use of interest rate (IR) as a benchmark for Islamic financial modes. We acknowledged that using interest rate as a benchmark does not invalidate a contract as such, but it should be avoided. This is an opinion of Muhammad Taqi Usmani that was cited earlier in this paper. The respondents generally agree with this view. The statement seven reads: “*Using interest rate (ribā) as a benchmark for BBA financing should be avoided*”. From the table we can see that over 60% generally agree with the statement, 33.3%

‘strongly agree’ and 26.9% ‘agree’. Those who ‘strongly disagree’ with the statement represent 9% of total, ‘disagree’ represent 14.1%, while 16.7% are those with ‘no comment’. It is obvious that IR as benchmark should be avoided.

Even though bankers do not mention it directly in the contract, when deciding on the “profit rate” for BBA financing they use all available information including interest rate as argued by Saiful Azhar Rosly.² This practice, according to him, brings a lot of doubts about Islamicity of BBA as mode of finance. “*Using interest rate as a benchmark for BBA financing brings a lot of doubts about Islamicity of BBA*” was the statement number eight. Out of 78 respondents, 6.4% ‘strongly disagree’, 17.9% ‘disagree’, 15.4% ‘no comment’, while 32.1% ‘agree’, and 28.2% ‘strongly agree’ with this statement. Obviously that using IR as benchmark for BBA financing brings a lot of doubts about Islamicity of BBA. Therefore, this practice should be avoided in order to make it fully Islamic.

In our study and throughout the literature it has been argued that the BBA as practiced in Malaysia indirectly involves IR. On the statement that: “*BBA financing indirectly involves interest rate (ribā)*” our respondents were slightly against this statement. From the table we see that 19.2% of the participants ‘strongly disagree’ with the statement and the same percentage of them ‘disagree’, while 28.2% had ‘no comment’ on the statement. At the same time, 23.1% ‘agree’ and 10.3% ‘strongly agree’ with the statement.

One of distinguished feature of this research is the claim that states that current practices of Islamic banking and finance leads to the convergence of Islamic banks towards conventional counterparts. This was the topic of the statement number ten that reads: “*Current practices of Islamic banks will lead to a convergence of Islamic banks towards conventional counterparts*”. Going through the table, we find that 12.8% of participants ‘strongly agree’, 30.8% ‘agree’, while 35.9% were neutral, 10.3% ‘disagree’ and 10.3% of them ‘strongly disagree’ with this statement. Generally speaking, the respondents share our view about the convergence. Almost half of them either ‘agree’ or ‘strongly agree’ with statement ten. Therefore, we propose that the current practices have to be changed and this is in line with our research.

Using an example we showed that BBA financing is relatively more expensive than either conventional loan or MMP. This has been also shown by other scholars such as Meera and Dzuljastri.³ Statement eleven in the table states: “*Due to its fixed nature, BBA is relatively more expensive than conventional loan*”. Again, majority of the participants of the survey agreed with the statement with 15.4% who ‘strongly agree’ and 32.1% who ‘agree’, 21.8% who were neutral,

² See Saiful Azhar Rosly, *Critical Issues on Islamic Banking and Financial Markets*, (Kuala Lumpur: Dinamas, 2005).

³ See Meera and Dzuljastri, “Islamic Home Financing.”

21.8% who ‘disagree’ and 9% who ‘strongly disagree’ with this statement. It shows that the claims of this and many other studies are in line with the perceptions of the participants of this survey.

In addition to the statement number eleven, the statement number twelve is a continuation. Due to its fixed price, we argued throughout this study that BBA is unjust mode of finance in case of early settlement. This statement says: “*BBA seems unjust in cases of early settlement*”. In this case the results are mixed and there is no clear cut. The table shows that 7.7% of people involved in this questionnaire ‘strongly disagree’, 28.2% ‘disagree’, 29.5% are neutral, while 23.1% ‘agree’ and 11.5% ‘strongly agree’ with this statement.

5.3.3 MMP Analysis

Our next step in the survey was to find out how much people involved in this survey are aware of the MMP as a mode of finance. Prior to undertaking of this survey we believed that local (i.e. Malaysian) people have little knowledge of this mode of finance. The *section C* of the survey asked the questions regarding MMP. Firstly we asked participants whether they are familiar with MMP or not. If the answer was “Yes” then they were asked 8 additional questions related to MMP. If the answer was “No” then they were asked to proceed to the next section, which is *section D*.

Table 5.5
Familiarity with MMP

		Frequency	%	Chi Square	df	Asymp. Sig.
Are you familiar with MMP?	Yes	61	78.2	24.82	1	.000
	No	17	21.8			
Total		78	100			

As can be seen from the Table 5.5 above, out of 78 participants 61 of them were familiar with MMP mode of financing. It represents 78.2% of the total. The remaining 21.8% or 17 participants were not familiar with this mode of finance. As result, remaining 8 questions of section C were only answered by 61 participants. The answer to this question is also statistically significant at 99% level as can be seen from the table above. In this case we used a six-point Likert-type scale to assess the views of the respondents. For those who answered ‘No’ on this question we will use label ‘not applicable’. The remaining will be ranked in the same manner as BBA in the previous section.⁴

⁴ Please note here that analysis will include all participants, even those who answered ‘No’ on the question on familiarity with MMP. Those 17 people who answered ‘No’, represent 21.8% of total 78 participants. Therefore, remaining 78.2% will be shared between 61 participants who answered ‘Yes’.

In this research we tried to promote new modes of financing, including MMP. We believe that this mode is better alternative, if not substitution, to the overwhelmingly used BBA financing technique. To check this claim we presented to the participants of the survey with the following statement: “MMP is better mode of finance than BBA”. Their obvious preference of MMP to BBA is obvious from the Table 5.6.

Table 5.6
Respondents’ Perception of MMP

Statement	SD %	D %	NC %	A %	SA %	Chi ²	df	Sig
1. MMP is better mode of finance than BBA	-	3.3	9.8	37.7	49.2	35.32	3	.000
2. MMP promotes Profit and Loss Sharing (PLS) mechanism	-	1.6	1.6	57.4	39.3	57.23	3	.000
3. MMP reflects the true spirit of Islam through sharing of the risk and the gain between the partners	-	4.9	4.9	49.2	41	40.18	3	.000
4. MMP promotes the Objectives of <i>Shari’ah</i> (<i>maqāsid al-Shari’ah</i>) including the welfare of the society	-	3.3	9.8	52.5	34.4	37.68	3	.000
5. Using interest rate (<i>ribā</i>) as a benchmark for MMP financing should be avoided	6.6	11.5	6.6	37.7	37.7	32.36	4	.000
6. Due to its flexible pricing MMP is relatively cheaper than both BBA and conventional loan	3.3	16.4	34.4	34.4	11.5	23.83	4	.000
7. MMP contributes positively to equitable distribution of wealth and income	-	1.6	23	59	16.4	43.45	3	.000
8. MMP may be difficult to implement	6.6	23	9.8	49.2	11.5	37.11	4	.000

Note. SD (Strongly Disagree), D (Disagree), NC (No Comment), A (Agree), and SA (Strongly Agree), Chi² (Chi Square), df (Degree of Freedom), Sig (Significance).

The Table 5.6 shows statistical significance at 99% level for all the statements. This means that respondents are generally agreeing to the statements. It shows that out of 61 participants, 49.2% ‘strongly agree’, 37.7% ‘agree’, 9.8% were neutral, while only 3.3% disagree with the statement number one and no participant that ‘strongly disagrees’. These results fully support our claims that MMP should be implemented as it is better mode of finance than BBA. This strong preference shown by our respondents inevitably shows that MMP would be well accepted by the customers if implemented in the banks.

As MMP is based primarily on *mushārah* contract it promotes profit and loss sharing mechanism. Both *mushārah* and *mudhārah* are considered to be a corner stone of Islamic banking and finance. Yet, they are not that much present in current Islamic banks. Second statement in *section C* states: “MMP promotes Profit and Loss Sharing (PLS) mechanism”. Here, only 1.6% of the participants both ‘disagree’ and were neutral on this statement. At the same time, 57.4% of them ‘agree’ and 39.3% ‘strongly agree’ with third statement.

True spirit of Islamic financial system is based on the principles of cooperation, brotherhood and justice between the parties. As such, the risk and the gain are to be shared equally between the parties. The third statement says: “*MMP reflects the true spirit of Islam through sharing of the risk and the gain between the partners*”. Again we see that our participants are overwhelmingly in support of this statement. Over 90% of them generally agree with the statement; 41% ‘strongly agree’ and 49.2% ‘agree’. Again we see that there is no participant who ‘strongly disagree’ with the statement. Only 4.9% of participants ‘disagree’ and also 4.9% had ‘no comment’ on the statement.

As already mentioned, in this study we tried to promote those products that are *Shari’ah-based* and in line with *maqāsid al- Shari’ah*. We believe that MMP is one of those products. Therefore we presented this statement (statement four) to our respondents: “*MMP promotes the Objectives of Shari’ah (maqāsid al- Shari’ah) including the welfare of the society*”. In this case, as with the previous one, majority of participants agreed with the statement. Among them 34.4% ‘strongly agree’, 52.5% ‘agree’, and 9.8% had ‘no comment’ regarding the statement. Two participants, 3.3% of total 61 participants ‘disagree’ while there is no one strongly disagreeing with the statement.

Statement number five raises the question of IR as benchmark for MMP financing. It reads: “*Using interest rate (ribā) as a benchmark for MMP financing should be avoided*”. Out of our 61 participants, 37.7% ‘strongly agree’ and same percentage of them ‘agree’ with the statement, 6.6% were neutral, while 11.5% ‘disagree’ and 6.6% ‘strongly disagree’ with the statement five. These results show strong disapproval of survey participants towards the use of IR as benchmark for MMP financing.

Using hypothetical example we showed in previous chapter that MMP is relatively cheaper mode of financing compared to both BBA and conventional loan. We asked respondents to consider following statement: “*Due to its flexible pricing MMP is relatively cheaper than both BBA and conventional loan*”. Compared to previous statement, in this case there is no clear preference shown. As shown in the table, 11.5% of our respondents ‘strongly agree’ and 34.4% ‘agree’ with the statement, with 34.4% of those who did not comment. The reason for this high rate of those who were neutral could be because they either are not fully familiar with MMP modus operandi or they were not sure. Very low number of participants disagrees with the statement. Among them 16.4% ‘disagree’ and 3.3% ‘strongly disagree’. Even though the results are mixed, still we can see that the majority are those who support the statement. Therefore, we can conclude that MMP is relatively cheaper mode of finance compared to both BBA and conventional loan.

Implementing equity based financial products will promote equitable distribution of income and wealth. Current system exploits wealth and income of the people. The statement seven says: “*MMP contributes positively to equitable distribution of wealth and income*”. There was no

participant who ‘strongly disagree’ with the statement. Only one of them, 1.6%, ‘disagrees’ with 23% of them being neutral. Again majority of participant generally agreed with the statement; 59% of them ‘agree’ and 16.4% ‘strongly agree’.

Lastly we asked our participant whether or not the implementation of the MMP would be difficult. The last statement, statement eight, of *section C* was: “MMP may be difficult to implement”. There was 6.6% of those who ‘strongly disagree’ and 23% of those who ‘disagree’ with the statement, while 9.8% were neutral. Majority of our participants are in favor of the statement; 49.2% ‘agree’ and 11.5% ‘strongly agree’ with the statement. It is obvious that from their point of view, implementing MMP into Islamic financial system may be difficult to implement.

5.3.4 Comparative Analysis between BBA and MMP

First part of the *section D* of the survey is dealing with general questions regarding BBA and MMP. Second part consisted of the questions regarding *Ijārah Sukūk*. Five questions were included in the first part of *section D*. The first question is: “If given a choice, which mode of financing would you select?” From the Table 5.7 we can see that there is huge preference of MMP over both BBA and conventional loan.

Table 5.7
Preference: BBA, MMP and Conventional Loan

Question	BBA %	MMP %	Loan %	Chi-Square	df	Asymp Sig.
If given a choice, which mode of financing would you select?	23.1	74.4	2.6	64	2	.000

Out of our 78 participants, 23.1% would choose BBA as their mode of finance. Two of them, representing 2.6% would go for conventional loan. The remaining 74.4% are those who prefer MMP to BBA and conventional loan. It should be also noted here that majority of those who are not familiar with MMP selected BBA as their favorite mode of finance. This means that if the mechanism of MMP is introduced to them, then they may have selected MMP as well. This would increase the percentage of those who are in favor of MMP. However, even without their support the percentage of those who choose MMP is very high. This shows the perspective of MMP if implemented in the Islamic banks. The response is also statistically significant at 99% significance level.

When asked “Which mode of finance is a better representative of the true Islamic financial system?” the response was as follows: 9% of the respondents said that BBA is better representative of Islamic financial system (IFS); majority of them, 70.5% said claimed the better representative of

IFS is MMP; finally 20.5% of them said that both of them, BBA and MMP, are true representative of IFS (see Table 5.8). Again, the dominance of the MMP product is obvious and the answer is statistically significant.

Table 5.8
True Representative of IFS

Question	BBA %	MMP %	Both %	Chi-Square	df	Asymp. Sig.
Which mode of finance is a better representative of the true Islamic financial system?	9	70.5	20.5	50.077	2	.000

Table 5.9
Development of IFS

Question	YES %	NO %	NS %	Chi-Square	df	Asymp. Sig.
1. Do you think that Islamic banks are currently lacking products to meet the needs of the Muslim customers?	75.6	20.5	3.8	66.07	2	.000
2. Implementation of MMP will help further development of Islamic financial system?	79.5	1.3	19.2	78.53	2	.000
3. Interest rate should be completely avoided in Islamic banking and finance?	74.4	11.5	14.1	59.15	2	.000

The above table, Table 5.9, shows the response of the participants on the following three questions: (i) *Do you think that Islamic banks are currently lacking products to meet the needs of the Muslim customers?*; (ii) *Implementation of MMP will help further development of Islamic financial system?*; and (iii) *Interest rate should be completely avoided in Islamic banking and finance?* Again the answers are statistically significant at 99% level. For all of these questions, on average two-third of respondents answered ‘Yes’. More precisely, 75.6% said that Islamic banks are lacking products to meet the needs of Muslim customers, compared to 20.5% and 3.8% of those who said ‘No’ or ‘Not Sure’ about the question. That MMP will help development of IFS said 79.5% of participants, with 1.3% saying ‘No’ and 19.2% being neutral. Regarding the use of interest rate in IFS, the answers are in accordance with the previous, similar, statements. Majority of them, 74.4% said that IR should be completely avoided. That IR should not be completely avoided said 11.5%. With no definite choice made were 14.1% of the participants.

5.3.5 *Ijārah Sukūk* Analysis

As already mentioned, second part of *section D* is dealing with *Ijārah Sukūk*. The first question was about participants' familiarity with *Ijārah Sukūk*. On the question: “*Are you familiar with Ijārah Sukūk (Islamic leasing bonds)?*” 66.7% or 52 out of 78 answered with ‘Yes’, while 33.3% of the participants were unfamiliar with *Ijārah Sukūk* (see Table 5.10 below). Again the null hypothesis, that the value of this statement has the same frequency, can be rejected at 99% significance level as shown in the Table 5.10 below.

Table 5.10
Familiarity with *Ijārah Sukūk*

		Frequency	%	Chi-Square	df	Asymp. Sig.
Are you familiar with <i>Ijārah Sukūk</i> ?	Yes	52	66.7	8.667	1	.003
	No	26	33.3			
Total		78	100			

The table below shows statistical significance for all the statements at 99% level with statement number two being statistically significant at 90% significance level. Out of 52 participants who said that are familiar with *Ijārah Sukūk*, 45 said that would like to invest in *Ijārah Sukūk* if given chance. This represents 86.5%, which is very high (see Table 5.11). Two of them, 3.8% said ‘No’ to the investment in *Ijārah Sukūk*, while 9.6%, or five participants, were ‘not sure’ about investing in *Ijārah Sukūk*.

Table 5.11
Participants' perception on *Ijārah Sukūk*

Question	Yes %	No %	NS %	Chi-Square	df	Asymp Sig.
1. If given a chance would you invest in <i>Ijārah Sukūk</i> ?	86.5	3.8	9.6	66.5	2	.000
2. Using interest rate as a benchmark is ok. <i>Ijārah Sukūk</i> holders should be kept liable	40.4	40.4	19.2	4.65	2	.098
3. for delivering of the services/usufructs as the owners of the asset(s)?	73.1	11.5	15.4	37.07	2	.000
4. For development of <i>Ijārah Sukūk</i> a well-developed secondary market is necessary?	88.5	1.9	9.6	71.57	2	.000
5. Do you agree that <i>Ijārah Sukūk</i> should be more popularized?	88.5	5.8	5.8	71.11	2	.000

Interesting answer was given by our respondents when asked whether or not “*using interest rate as benchmark is ok*”. Equal number of participants, 21 out of 52 (40.4%), said it is both ok and not ok to use IR as benchmark. Only 10 of them were undecided about this issue. When asked in the previous sections of the survey whether or not using of IR as benchmark for both BBA and MMP

should be avoided they answered positively (i.e. that IR should be avoided). However in this case there are somehow undecided. One of the comments received from one of the participants was that so far there is no other benchmark to be used for *Ijārah Sukūk*. This could be one of the possible reasons why so many of them answered ‘Yes’ on this question.

The question of liability is very important and we highlighted it throughout our research. According to *Shari‘ah* principles in order for us to receive reward or payment (i.e. profit) we have to bear risk and be liable for the services. In this regard, the *Ijārah Sukūk* holders, in order for their profit to be *halāl* (permissible), they should be liable for the period holding the *sukūk*. Therefore the third question was: “*Ijārah Sukūk* holders should be kept liable for delivering of the services/usufructs as the owners of the asset(s)?” From the table above, it can be seen that 73.1% of the respondents are of the view that they should be liable, 11.5% said they should not be liable, while 15.4% was ‘not sure’. Obviously their response is in favor of our already claimed and supported view that *Ijārah Sukūk* holders should be kept liable for delivering of the services/usufructs as the owners of the asset(s).

As shown in the table, the secondary market is definitely necessary. We see that 88.5% of participants said that it is necessary to have a well-developed secondary market, only one participant or 1.9% of total said that secondary market is not necessary. The remaining 9.6% were not sure. We have also raised in our study the problem of non-existence of a well-developed secondary market as an obstacle to fully efficient Islamic capital market. From research we indicated that a well-developed secondary market is ‘a must’ for Islamic capital market to develop.

Whether or not *Ijārah Sukūk* should be more popularized was the last question in *section D*. As indicated in table above, 88.5% believes that *Ijārah Sukūk* should be more popularized, while 5.8% of the participants think that *Ijārah Sukūk* need not to be more popularized and 5.8% also is not sure about the question. The obvious proof that *Ijārah Sukūk* should be more popularized is the fact that 26 out of 78 initial participants, representing 33.3% of total, were not familiar with *Ijārah Sukūk*. This is undisputable fact that the introduction of *Ijārah Sukūk* to the general masses and even bank officers is necessary.

5.3.6 General Comments by the Participants

Last section of the survey, *section E*, was left for participants to make their own comment with regarding the issues raised in this questionnaires. As this was voluntary contribution from the side of the participants not everyone gave a comment. To be more precise, only few of them responded by writing their own views and comments.

One of them wrote that he was confused when filling this questionnaire. This confusion was not result of the questionnaire itself, but rather, as he said: “there are differences between the

theory/concept of each contract and the application. For example, based on the theory, BBA is a permissible contract. However, in Malaysia, they actually use *bay' al-inah* mechanism for BBA which is not permissible.” This have been fully elaborated throughout our study and these comments are in lie with our findings and claims.

Another comment was that any new product should be completely in line with *Shari'ah* principles and interest rate must be avoided. Someone else argue that implementation of Islamic banking, a *Shari'ah-based* model, is not possible under the paper money based system, i.e. modern world. Monetary system based on gold dinar is inevitable for implementation of Islamic banking products in their true sense.

In addition to that the following lines are interesting. One of the participants wrote the following:

... the mentality of the bankers as well as the customers has to be changed first in order for the profit and loss sharing-based financial products to be effectively introduced in the market. ... If there is no serious effort done to differentiate between conventional and Islamic banking practices ... products would be designed and altered no less different from the conventional products and only small adjustment will be made to suit *Shari'ah* requirements. Therefore, the product will be named after the *Shari'ah* compliant concept, yet the mechanics would be similar to the conventional product. Hence, the net effect on the economic and society would be similar.

It is also believed that the implementation of new products should be supported with strong consumer education. This is definitely true, but before this is done we need to educate our bankers and people dealing with these products. From the survey conducted I have found that majority of those who were not familiar with MMP and *Ijarah Sukuk* were bank officers who worked in Islamic banks. This indicates that even those who are supposed to know these products, as they are involved in this industry, are not aware of these mechanisms. Now, if this is the case, then how can we expect ordinary citizens to know these products? Table 5.11 shows cross-reference between the occupation of the participants and their unfamiliarity with MMP. As can be seen from the table below, 12 out of 17 participants who are not familiar with MMP are bank officers.

Table 5.12
Occupation vs. Familiar with MMP

		Familiar with MMP?		Total
		Yes	No	
Occupation	Student	5	1	6
	Academics	16	1	17
	Bank Officer	32	12	44
	Other	8	3	11
Total		61	17	78

Table 5.13
Occupation vs. *Ijārah Sukūk*

		Are you familiar with <i>Ijārah Sukūk</i> ?		Total
		Yes	No	
Occupation	Student	5	1	6
	Academics	13	4	17
	Bank Officer	26	18	44
	Other	8	3	11
Total		52	26	78

Table 5.12 shows the comparison between the occupation of the participants and their familiarity with *Ijārah Sukūk*. As already stated, 33.3% of 78 participants are not familiar with *Ijārah Sukūk*. There are 26 participants that are unaware of *Ijārah Sukūk*, of which 18 are bank officers.

5.4 CONCLUSION

Going through this survey we have seen the perception of bank officers working in Islamic banks (majority of them being from local, Malaysian banks), academicians doing research in Islamic banking and finance, as well as the perception of few students. Majority of results are very much in line with main claims of this research. We see that throughout the survey, the respondents are of view that IR as benchmark should be avoided when it comes to the BBA and MMP financing. However, they are not really sure when it comes to the *Ijārah Sukūk*. As already stated, the non-existence of possible alternative may be a reason for such results.

A claim that current practices of Islamic banking and finance will lead to the convergence of Islamic banks towards conventional counterparts is supported by total 43.6%.⁵ As expected, there are number of participants who are not aware of MMP and *Ijārah Sukūk* products. In case of MMP over 20% of the participants are unfamiliar with its mechanism, while 33.3% are unfamiliar with

⁵ Found by summing up 30.8% and 12.8% of those who ‘agree’ and ‘strongly agree’ with the statement number 10. See Table 5.4 above.

Ijārah Sukūk. This shows that this research will be of great help to those who are looking for more information about these products.

In overall, the MMP is seen by our participants as superior over the BBA. As result, the future of MMP, if implemented widely in Malaysia and other places, is bright. A huge majority of the participants are in favor of MMP and chose it over BBA and conventional loan. However, some difficulties can be there while implementing these new products. This was pointed out by the participants. The possible difficulties in implementation of new products have been discussed in previous chapters. Therefore, some necessary reforms may be needed in order to facilitate their development as shown in this study.

Finally it can be concluded from the data collected using the questionnaire that Islamic banks are in need of new products and that implementation of MMP will further develop IFS. As for *Ijārah Sukūk*, a well-developed secondary market is 'a must'. In addition to that, education of the employees of the banks, as shown in Table 5.11 and 5.12, as well as general masses is needed for further development of both *Ijārah Sukūk* and MMP.

CHAPTER SIX

CONCLUSION

6.0 INTRODUCTION

This paper represents an attempt to revive the true nature of Islamic banking and finance industry that is being promoted by its pioneer scholars in last forty years or so. The scholars are repeatedly speaking of profit and loss sharing (PLS) mechanism as inseparable or integral part of Islamic banking and finance. In fact, all of them consider the PLS as the true spirit of Islamic financial system or the *raison d'être*. They argued, and still do, from the very beginning that Islamic banking and finance should be carried out based on PLS, promoting the brotherhood and cooperation.

Unfortunately, the practices that we are witnessing today are not in support of the above statements and vision shared by Islamic economists who pioneered the idea of Islamic banking and finance. Islamic banks follow the path of least resistance avoiding to explore the true nature of Islamic banking and finance. They developed such environment that is very much similar to that one of their conventional counterparts. They minimized the risks (if any) involved in their daily activities while working under the name of 'Islamic bank'. The use of PLS instruments is marginalized and almost insignificant. Hence, the vision of fairness, efficiency, stability and growth through sharing in finance was diluted by the increasing confluence of debt financing and a monetary system built around debt.⁶

This scenario is obvious from the example of Islamic banks operating in Malaysia. As we saw in this paper, their primary mode of finance was BBA and *murābahah*. Unfortunately, even these modus operandi are not carried out in the proper way as they should be in order to be considered as *Shari'ah*-compliant. Quite contrary, these modes were modified in such a way to fit the 'bottom line' (i.e. the capitalist market economy based on interest) environment in which they are operating. This modification, alienation and overdependence of Islamic banks on mark-up sale (i.e. BBA and *murābahah*) led to the resemblance with and the convergence of Islamic banks towards the conventional counterparts.

Therefore this paper tried to stress, once again, the importance of PLS modes of finance and proposed the use of these modes in everyday transactions. By applying more PLS modes of finance such as MMP, *ijārah*, and *ijārah sukūk*, Islamic banks will be able to distinct themselves from their

⁶ Mohammad Nejatullah Siddiqi, "40 Years of Islamic Banking: The Lessons for the Future," paper presented at One Day Seminar on Islamic Banking and Finance: *Islamic Banking after 40 Years*, jointly organized by IIUM Institute of Islamic Banking and Finance (IIBF) and Kulliyah of Economics and Management Sciences (KENMS), International Islamic University Malaysia, Renaissance Hotel, Kuala Lumpur, August 30, 2006.

conventional counterparts and make the real contribution to the development of Islamic banking and finance.

6.1 FINDINGS AND CONTRIBUTIONS

In the following paragraphs we will try to sum up the main findings of the paper, starting with Chapter Two, since the Chapter One is the introductory chapter and needs no explanation. Once again, we would like to stress that the second chapter was informative in nature. Its purpose was to introduce the BBA mode of finance to the readers and critically elaborate the mechanism practiced in Malaysia currently. From the discussion on the BBA as a mode of finance, we can conclude that the BBA as such is very much in line with the *Shari'ah*. The problem with BBA, at least in case of Malaysia, lies in the *modus operandi* that is implemented by Islamic banks in Malaysia. After thorough analysis of BBA and *murabahah* structures, the way they are implemented in Malaysia, it is clear to us that these structures reflect “buy-back” mechanism, also known as *bay' al-'inah*.⁷

This practice is used in Malaysia since Shafi'i school of *fiqh* legalized and validated *bay' al-'inah* transactions. The other classical and medieval *fuqahā* did not legalize this practice. Malikīs and Hanbalīs categorically rejected *bay' al-'inah*, considering it as a legal trick (*hilah*) opening back-door for *ribā*. On the other hand, the Hanafīs and majority of *fuqahā* allowed *bay' al-'inah* if it involves three parties and this practice is known as *tawarruq*. However, if *bay' al-'inah* is carried out between the same two persons, then even the Hanafīs disallowed its practice.⁸

It is clear from the discussion that the BBA financing should be minimized and avoided if possible due to its misleading features. Its fixed nature makes it quite vulnerable to the economic turbulences such as inflation/deflation and rise/fall of interest rate, among others. The danger of opening back door for interest is very good reason why we should avoid this financing technique. Its worth citing Chapra again, when he said, “[t]he danger will, however, always remain that the *mu'ajjal* and *murabahah* forms of sales may deteriorate into purely financing arrangements with the agreed profit margin being no more than a camouflage for interest.”⁹

After the reviewing of the BBA *modus operandi* and finding all the above mentioned deficiencies, we proposed the use of MMP financing technique as alternative and solution to these problems. The MMP mechanism, as is clear from the Chapter Three discussion, can address

⁷ This assertion is very known fact that has been discussed widely among Islamic *fiqhī* scholars and economists. For example see: Adawiah, “Securitization in Islamic Contracts,” 8 and 12. See also: Saiful Azhar Rosly, *Critical Issues on Islamic Banking and Financial Markets*, (Kuala Lumpur: Dinamas, 2005).

⁸ The *bay' al-'inah* transactions are allowed only by the Shafi'īs and Zahirīs scholars. For detailed discussion about the *bay' al-'inah* transactions and its legal rulings among Muslim scholars, see: Adawiah, “Securitization in Islamic Contracts,” 11-16.

⁹ M. Umer Chapra, *Towards a Just Monetary system*, 171.

problems faced by BBA efficiently. It is not only PLS-based mode of finance, but it is also promoting the *maqāsid al-Sharī'ah*.

The advantages of the MMP mechanism over the BBA are enormous. This mechanism promotes the risk-sharing and cooperation between the contractual parties. It brings more harmony to the economy, especially if implemented through co-operatives or mutual funds. It promotes fairness due to the fact that this mode of finance is always priced at the market value, as opposite to the BBA pricing. Its structure is flexible, being able to respond to the market fluctuations and disturbances. Most importantly, this mechanism is internationally acceptable and can easily become the standard throughout the Islamic banking industry.

Chapter two and three, covering the BBA and MMP respectively, are dealing with short to medium-term financing. These mechanisms are mostly used for meeting customers' personal needs. This includes the financing of home purchase, car purchase and such. In order to complete the picture, we included a chapter on the *ijārah sukūk* investment certificates (i.e. Chapter Four).

These certificates represent the latest development in the Islamic capital market. The purpose of *ijārah sukūk* is to help government, Islamic banks and financial institutions to mobilize funds for financing new projects. Being built on the *ijārah* and securitized by the pool of assets there is no objection to its permissibility from the *Sharī'ah* point of view. As already stated in chapter four, the OIC Fiqh Academy ruled out that as long as the real assets, either physical or usufructs, are dominating the pool of assets represented by the *sukūk* certificates, these *sukūk* can be traded at the market value free from *ribā*. Otherwise, if these assets are dominated by debts or cash money, then these certificates can be traded only at face value.¹⁰

Islamic banks are in dire need of these instruments for addressing the problem of liquidity. Because they represent the proportionate ownership in the leased asset, these *ijārah sukūk* certificates can be traded at the secondary market. This trade will bring about more liquidity into the Islamic banking and finance industry.

The future of *ijārah sukūk* is looking bright as demand for *sukūk* is almost indefinite. It attracted international attention both from the Muslim and the Western world, as they are based on a unique underlying structure. However, for these instruments to attain the efficiency the well-organized secondary market is a must. So far, this market is almost non-existent, as there is no trade of *ijārah sukūk* certificates taking place until now.

Everything that has been said, in the first four chapters, about BBA, MMP and *ijārah sukūk* was the topic of a survey conducted to test the claims. The goal was to check out the perception of the people (especially bank officers) regarding the new products we are proposing. It is alarming

¹⁰ The OIC Islamic Fiqh Academy, *Resolutions and Recommendations of the Council of the Islamic Fiqh Academy: 1985-2000 – Jeddah*, 61-66.

fact how big percentage of respondents did not know about MMP and *ijārah sukūk*. More than 20% are not familiar with MMP while around 33% are not familiar with *ijārah sukūk* (Table 5.5 and Table 5.10 respectively). This shows that even bank officers are not familiar of new products. As such this study could help them get familiar with the proposed modes of finance. This will be obvious contribution of this research.

It is also worth noting that majority of those who responded to the questions in the survey agreed that MMP is better than BBA, more *Sharī'ah* compliant, and promotes *maqāsid al- Sharī'ah*. A person may ask a question: *How can you say that a MMP is better than BBA and more Sharī'ah compliant based on the views of laymen people?* This question is a good question, but we have not based our opinion on the views of these laymen people. Rather we have indicated in the study that Islamic scholars are of opinion that MMP is better than BBA and that it is more *Sharī'ah* compliant while promoting *maqāsid al- Sharī'ah*. The perceptions and views of our respondents are just in line with those already stated opinion of Muslim *fuqahā*.

The importance of this study lies in its holistic approach to Islamic banking and finance from small and medium modes of finance to the long-term financing mechanism. Its main objective was to promote PLS financial techniques as in line with the vision of Islamic banking and finance. The paper elaborated theoretically the most viable and sound solutions for the problems faces by the Islamic banks. It is done in systematic way contributing to the existing literature on the topics. Furthermore, all the claims are more or less supported by the survey findings.

Furthermore, the great amount of this paper is focused on *Sharī'ah*-related issues as it is lacking in the current literature. As rightly noted by Muhammad Ayub¹¹ despite the good performance and enormous growth of Islamic financial institutions, the due attention to the *Sharī'ah* aspect and the compliance of the product to the *Sharī'ah* is lacking. He goes by saying:

Notwithstanding visibly good performance as a whole in terms of growth rate and the penetration levels in global finance, a relatively weaker area is the aspect of *Sharī'ah* compliance which is not being taken care of properly by many IFIs. Credibility of Islamic banks is the most important aspects and the key to success and development. Islamic banks must give special care to this aspect otherwise they would be facing systemic risk for the whole industry. It has been seen in many cases that the *Sharī'ah* Advisors are there simply to endorse the formats of documents and the bankers are free to conduct business in response to market signals without any effective follow up by *Sharī'ah* people. Such relaxed environment results in non *Sharī'ah* compliance of

¹¹ Muhammad Ayub, "Securitization, *Sukūk* and Fund Management Potential to be Realized by Islamic Financial Institutions," p. 349.

transactions undertaken by bankers who may or may not be sufficiently trained in *Shari'ah* matters.¹²

Having in mind the citation above, we can see the relevance of this study that pays special attention to *Shari'ah* by raising several practical issues throughout the paper. The intention of this practice is to highlight the weakness of the current Islamic financial products and its negative effect on the future development of the industry. Unless we address the issues such as the usage of LIBOR as a benchmark, mixing of tradable and non-tradable assets in a pool, and liability issues underlying this modes of finance we will not be able to distance Islamic finance from the conventional counterpart. If we continue this road we are going, it will lead to the convergence of Islamic banking and finance towards the conventional counterparts.

Therefore, in order to make Islamic banks more distinct from their interest-based counterparts we proposed the use of the MMP mechanism instead of BBA. As solution to the problem of the liquidity faced by Islamic banks the further development of *ijarah sukuk* and improving their trading at the secondary market are suggested. However, these modus operandi have to be reviewed and the above-mentioned practical issues should be addressed in order to make them completely free from interest. As such they will uphold the true spirit of *Shari'ah* as they will be following *maqāsid al-Shari'ah*'s guidance.

One of the major contributions of the study would be the comparison between the BBA, MMP and *ijarah sukuk* that was presented at the end of chapter four. In general, this study contributed to the existing literature by its holistic approach combining different models and comparing them theoretically and empirically.

6.2 LIMITATION AND FUTURE RESEARCH

As with any research, and this research is not an exception, there are limitations to the study conducted. The first limitation of this study lies in fact that it covered only one side of the story. Despite its extensive theoretical elaboration and empirical results from the survey conducted, this research has to be tested in practice. It claims that the MMP and the *ijarah sukuk* are superior modes of financing, as opposed to the BBA mechanism. From the theoretical point of view, the study shows this fact clearly but it lacks more empirical evidences to support it. The data collected so far show the people's preference of MMP over BBA. When it comes to the *ijarah sukuk*, we cannot draw the line as one third of respondents were not aware of Islamic certificates. Therefore, further, more extensive empirical researches should be carried out with more countries involved and not only Malaysia.

¹² Ibid., p. 349. The *italics* are ours.

Secondly, due to the time and space limit for this research, accompanied with enormity of the topic, the study may be lacking some important aspects of the topics that otherwise should be included and discussed thoroughly. After doing this research it is believed that each mode of finance involved in this study could be not only a Master Thesis, but a Ph.D. Dissertation, as each and every mode of finance in itself is spacious. Consequently, the focus of the paper was given to the main elements of the topic only. Therefore, some areas within the research may be overlooked for the sake of overall focus on very specific issues.

Having said this, the possible recommendations for future studies would be as follows:

1. This study would be of greater value if complemented by wider empirical studies (i.e. including more countries internationally). It would give it more relevancy and credibility. There is a huge need to conduct an empirical study that will elaborate the claims raised by this research. It can include some econometrical models that will analyze the relevance of this study and its claims. Econometric model can be applied to each mode of finance separately, but the cross-model would be more desirable for this study.
2. So far one research was carried on to compare MMP and BBA. This research was done on by Umar Ahmed¹³ and it covered the academicians and students of International Islamic University Malaysia (IIUM). Our research focused on bankers covering MMP, BBA and *ijārah sukūk*. Further questionnaires and surveys may be carried out in order to get the customers' views on the topic. Since the customers are directly affected by these modes of finance, their views would be very useful for this study.
3. Further studies are needed to address the problems raised in the chapter five with regard to liquidity management and secondary market trading. Well researches on these topics can help Islamic banks and financial institutions to better deal with these issues.

Despite its limitations, this study has established sound foundations for further development and enhancement of the MMP, the *ijārah* and the *ijārah sukūk* investment techniques to be used within the Islamic banking and finance industry. Furthermore, it gives a great starting point for future research on the topic.

This is from me and Allah (swt) knows the best!

¹³ Umar Ahmed, "Customers views on IIUM asset financing: a comparative study of Al-Musharakah Al-Mutanaqisah and Al-Bay' Bithamanin Ajil," (Master thesis, International Islamic University Malaysia, 2006).

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APPENDIX A

A MATHEMATICAL DERIVATION MODEL

In order for us to calculate necessary instalment and rental fees for *mushārah mutanāqisah* partnership we need a mathematical model. Here we will use mathematical derivation provided by Kameel and Dzuljastri.¹⁴ The model is as follows:¹⁵

P = Price of asset, e.g. a home, car

B_0 = Financier's contribution into the partnership

C_0 = Customer's contribution into the partnership

Therefore the price would be, $P = B_0 + C_0$

R = Periodic rental, eg. monthly

A = Additional periodic payment by customer to redeem the financier's equity faster

$M = R + A$, is therefore, the total periodic payment

Let C_i = the customer's equity (ownership) of the asset in period i

Let the proportion of customer's equity in period i , $r_i = \frac{C_i}{P}$

Therefore,

$$C_0 = C_0$$

$$C_1 = C_0 + r_0R + A$$

$$C_2 = C_1 + r_1R + A$$

$$C_3 = C_2 + r_2R + A$$

.

.

.

$$C_n = C_{n-1} + r_{n-1}R + A$$

¹⁴ Meera and Dzuljastri, "Islamic Home Financing," 26-30.

¹⁵ Note: This is the reproduced mathematical derivation note provided by Meera and Dzuljastri in their paper on "Islamic Home Financing through *Mushārah Mutanāqisah* and *al-Bay' Bithaman Ajil* Contracts: A Comparative Analysis", *Review of Islamic Economics*, vol. 9, no. 2 (2005): 26-30. The author acknowledges his full indebtedness to this paper.

Therefore,

$$C_0 = C_0$$

$$C_1 = C_0 + r_0R + A$$

$$C_2 = C_0 + r_0R + A + r_1R + A = C_0 + R(r_0 + r_1) + 2A$$

$$C_3 = C_0 + r_0R + A + r_1R + A + r_2R + A = C_0 + R(r_0 + r_1 + r_2) + 3A$$

.

$$C_n = C_0 + R(r_0 + r_1 + r_2 + \dots + r_{n-1}) + nA$$

$$C_n = C_0 + \frac{R}{P}(C_0 + C_1 + C_2 + \dots + C_{n-1}) + nA \quad \text{Since } r_i = \frac{C_i}{P}$$

Let $x = \frac{R}{P}$, then

$$C_1 = C_0 + xC_0 + A = (1 + x)C_0 + A$$

$$C_2 = C_0 + x(C_0 + C_0 + xC_0 + A) + 2A = (1 + 2x + x^2)C_0 + (x + 2)A$$

$$\begin{aligned} C_3 &= C_0 + x(C_0 + C_0 + xC_0 + A + C_0 + (C_0 + C_0 + xC_0 + A) + 2A) + 3A \\ &= (1 + 3x + 3x^2 + x^3)C_0 + (x^2 + 3x + 3)A \end{aligned}$$

.

Therefore,

$$C_1 = (1 + x)C_0 + A$$

$$C_2 = (1 + x)^2 C_0 + (x + 2)A$$

$$C_3 = (1 + x)^3 C_0 + (x^2 + 3x + 3)A$$

$$C_4 = (1 + x)^4 C_0 + (x^3 + 4x^2 + 6x + 4)A$$

.

$$C_n = (1 + x)^n C_0 + \left[\frac{(1 + x)^n - 1}{x} \right] A \quad (1)$$

and, of course, the proportion of the customer's equity in the n^{th} period is $r_n = \frac{C_n}{P}$

Rewriting equation (1), the number of periods taken by the customer to fully own the house is given by, where $C_n = P$,

$$\begin{aligned}
P &= (1+x)^n C_0 + \frac{(1+x)^n}{x} A - \frac{1}{x} A \\
&= (1+x)^n \left[C_0 + \frac{A}{x} \right] - \frac{1}{x} A \\
(1+x)^n &= \frac{P + \frac{A}{x}}{C_0 + \frac{A}{x}} \\
\Rightarrow n &= \frac{\ln\left(P + \frac{A}{x}\right) - \ln\left(C_0 + \frac{A}{x}\right)}{\ln(1+x)} \quad (2)
\end{aligned}$$

Once the rental, R , has been determined and the customer has decided on the period of partnership, i.e. the n , then the periodic amount the customer has to top up additionally is given by

$$A = \frac{x[P - (1+x)^n C_0]}{(1+x)^n - 1} \quad (3)$$

and, the formula for determining the periodic payment is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
M &= R + A \\
&= \frac{R[(1+x)^n - 1] + x[P - (1+x)^n C_0]}{(1+x)^n - 1} \\
&= \frac{R(1+x)^n - R + xP - x(1+x)^n C_0}{(1+x)^n - 1} \\
&= \frac{x(1+x)^n P - R + R - x(1+x)^n C_0}{(1+x)^n - 1} \quad \text{Since } xP = R \\
&= \frac{x(1+x)^n [P - C_0]}{(1+x)^n - 1} \\
&= \frac{x(1+x)^n B_0}{(1+x)^n - 1}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow M = \frac{x(1+x)^n B_0}{(1+x)^n - 1} \quad (4)$$

which, interestingly, is similar to the normal annuity formula used for computing the payment in conventional loan calculations¹⁶. Hence, mathematically, the normal annuity formula can also be used for *Mushārahah Mutanāqisah* calculations, but the periodic interest rate is replaced by the rental rate, $x = \frac{R}{P}$. Indeed then, the periodic rate of return for *Mushārahah Mutanāqisah* Partnership is solely

determined by the rental rate, $x = \frac{R}{P}$. Therefore, the

$$\text{Internal Rate of Return (IRR) to bank} = \frac{R}{P} \quad (5)$$

Also,

$$\text{Total payment made to financier} = Mn \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Total profit to financier} = Mn - B_0 \quad (7)$$

Note: Since the rate of return (IRR) for the financier is solely determined by the rental rate, $x = \frac{R}{P}$, **irrespective** of the initial capital provided by the financier (B_0) and/or the duration of the partnership (n), the financier may be tempt **to finance only homes with high rental values**; while it is in the interest of the customers to negotiate for low rentals. At the extreme, if the rental is nil, then the *Mushārahah Mutanāqisah* financing will become similar to *Qard al-Hassan*.

¹⁶ Computed using the standard formula for present value of annuities, i.e. $PV = \frac{Pmt}{i} \left[1 - \frac{1}{(1+i)^n} \right]$ which

gives $Pmt = \frac{i(1+i)^n PV}{(1+i)^n - 1}$.

APPENDIX B

Department of Economics
International Islamic University Malaysia

A Survey of A Theoretical Comparison between *Al-Bay' Bithaman Ājil* (BBA), *Mushārahah Mutanāqisah Partnership* (MMP) and *Ijārah Sukūk*

Explanation of the concepts:

Al-Bay' Bithaman Ājil (BBA) is a sale contract on the basis of deferred payment of the price and present delivery of the good sold.

Mushārahah Mutanāqisah Partnership (MMP) or *Diminishing Mushārahah* is a *Mushārahah* in which the Islamic bank agrees to transfer gradually to the other partner its (the Islamic bank's) share in the *Mushārahah*, so that the Islamic bank's share declines and the other partner's share increases until the latter becomes the sole proprietor of the venture.

Ijārah sukūk are securities representing the ownership of well-defined assets subject to a lease contract, they may be traded in a secondary market at the prevailing price determined by market forces.

General Instructions and Information

1. All individual responses to this questionnaire will be kept **STRICTLY CONFIDENTIAL**.
2. If you do not have the exact answer to a question, please provide your best judgment by selecting any available answer provided in the question. Your answers are very important for the accuracy of the study. Please do not leave any question unanswered.
3. If you have any additional comments or suggestions, please feel free to use the space provided at the end of this questionnaire.

SAMPLE QUESTIONNAIRE

This questionnaire comprises of five (5) parts. Please answer all items on this answer sheet.

PART A: PERSONAL INFORMATION

Please tick (✓) in the appropriate space for your response.

1. Gender () Male () Female
2. Age () Below 25 () 25 – 50 () Above 50
3. Marital Satus () Single () Married
4. Education () Degree () Masters
 () Ph.D. () Other
5. Occupation () Student () Academicians
 () Bank Officer () Other
6. Knowledge about () Poor () Average
 the Islamic products () Good () Very Good
 () Excellent

PART B - BBA

Please **circle** the numerical indicator on how you feel about the following statements.

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	No Comment	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5

1. The products of Islamic banks should be in line with *Shari'ah* 1 2 3 4 5
2. Profit and Loss Sharing (PLS) modes of finance are true 1 2 3 4 5
representative of Islamic financial system
3. Interest is not *ribā*. Therefore conventional banking is 1 2 3 4 5
acceptable
4. BBA as practiced in Malaysia is in accordance to the *Shari'ah* 1 2 3 4 5
5. BBA is a 'back-door' to the interest 1 2 3 4 5
6. BBA promotes the Objectives of *Shari'ah* (*maqāsid al-* 1 2 3 4 5
Shari'ah) including the welfare of the society
7. Using interest rate (*ribā*) as a benchmark for BBA financing 1 2 3 4 5
should be avoided

8. Using interest rate as a benchmark for BBA financing brings a lot of doubts about Islamicity of BBA 1 2 3 4 5
9. BBA financing indirectly involves interest rate (*ribā*) 1 2 3 4 5
10. Current practices of Islamic banks will lead to a convergence of Islamic banks towards conventional counterparts 1 2 3 4 5
11. Due to its fixed nature, BBA is relatively more expensive than conventional loan 1 2 3 4 5
12. BBA seems unjust in cases of early settlement 1 2 3 4 5

PART C - MMP

I. Are you familiar with *Mushārah Mutanāqisah Partnership* (MMP) mechanism?

() Yes () No

If your answer is **No** for the above question, please go to **PART D** below.

Please **circle** the numerical indicator on how you feel about the following statements.

Strongly Disagree 1	Disagree 2	No Comment 3	Agree 4	Strongly Agree 5
------------------------	---------------	-----------------	------------	---------------------

1. MMP is better mode of finance than BBA 1 2 3 4 5
2. MMP promotes Profit and Loss Sharing (PLS) mechanism 1 2 3 4 5
3. MMP reflects the true spirit of Islam through sharing of the risk and the gain between the partners 1 2 3 4 5
4. MMP promotes the Objectives of *Sharī'ah* (*maqāsid al-Sharī'ah*) including the welfare of the society 1 2 3 4 5
5. Using interest rate (*ribā*) as a benchmark for MMP financing should be avoided 1 2 3 4 5
6. Due to its flexible pricing MMP is relatively cheaper than both BBA and conventional loan 1 2 3 4 5
7. MMP contributes positively to equitable distribution of wealth and income 1 2 3 4 5
8. MMP may be difficult to implement 1 2 3 4 5

PART D: INTERVIEW

Please tick (✓) in the appropriate space for your response.

1. If given a choice, which mode of financing would you select?
 BBA MMP Conventional loan
2. Which mode of finance is a better representative of the true Islamic financial system?
 BBA MMP Both
3. Do you think that Islamic banks are currently lacking products to meet the needs of the Muslim customers?
 Yes No Not sure
4. Implementation of MMP will help further development of Islamic financial system?
 Yes No Not sure
5. Interest rate should be completely avoided in Islamic banking and finance?
 Yes No Not sure
6. Are you familiar with *Ijārah Sukūk* (Islamic leasing bonds)?
 Yes No

If your answer is **No** for the above question, please go to **PART E** below.

7. If given a chance would you invest in *Ijārah Sukūk*?
 Yes No Not sure
8. Using interest rate as a benchmark is ok.
 Yes No Not sure
9. *Ijārah Sukūk* holders should be kept liable for delivering of the services/usufructs as the owners of the asset(s)?
 Yes No Not sure
10. For development of *Ijārah Sukūk* a well-developed secondary market is necessary?
 Yes No Not sure
11. Do you agree that *Ijārah Sukūk* should be more popularized?
 Yes No Not sure

PART E:

If you have any suggestions with regard to the implementation of MMP and other Islamic products please use the space below.

.....
.....
.....
.....
.....
.....
.....

Thank you very much

APPENDIX C

Frequency Tables

Section A

Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	53	67.9	67.9	67.9
	Female	25	32.1	32.1	100.0
	Total	78	100.0	100.0	

Age

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Below 25	5	6.4	6.4	6.4
	25 - 50	69	88.5	88.5	94.9
	Above 50	4	5.1	5.1	100.0
	Total	78	100.0	100.0	

Marital Status

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Single	26	33.3	33.3	33.3
	Married	52	66.7	66.7	100.0
	Total	78	100.0	100.0	

Education

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Degree	27	34.6	34.6	34.6
	Master	27	34.6	34.6	69.2
	Ph.D.	14	17.9	17.9	87.2
	Other	10	12.8	12.8	100.0
	Total	78	100.0	100.0	

Occupation

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Student	6	7.7	7.7	7.7
	Academicians	17	21.8	21.8	29.5
	Bank Officer	44	56.4	56.4	85.9
	Other	11	14.1	14.1	100.0
	Total	78	100.0	100.0	

Knowledge of Isl. Products

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Poor	2	2.6	2.6	2.6
	Average	21	26.9	26.9	29.5
	Good	30	38.5	38.5	67.9
	Very Good	13	16.7	16.7	84.6
	Excellent	12	15.4	15.4	100.0
	Total	78	100.0	100.0	

Crosstabs

Occupation vs. Familiarity with MMP

		Familiar with MMP?		Total
		Yes	No	
Occupation	Student	5	1	6
	Academicians	16	1	17
	Bank Officer	32	12	44
	Other	8	3	11
Total		61	17	78

Occupation vs. Ijārah Sukūk

		Are you familiar with Ijārah Sukūk?		Total
		Yes	No	
Occupation	Student	5	1	6
	Academicians	13	4	17
	Bank Officer	26	18	44
	Other	8	3	11
Total		52	26	78

Frequency Table for Section B

Should be in line with Shari'ah

Q1B		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No Comment	1	1.3	1.3	1.3
	Agree	7	9.0	9.0	10.3
	Strongly Agree	70	89.7	89.7	100.0
	Total	78	100.0	100.0	

PLS are true representative

Q2B		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	2	2.6	2.6	2.6
	Disagree	7	9.0	9.0	11.5
	No Comment	8	10.3	10.3	21.8
	Agree	28	35.9	35.9	57.7
	Strongly Agree	33	42.3	42.3	100.0
	Total	78	100.0	100.0	

Interest is not Riba

Q3B		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	63	80.8	80.8	80.8
	Disagree	6	7.7	7.7	88.5
	No Comment	1	1.3	1.3	89.7
	Agree	5	6.4	6.4	96.2
	Strongly Agree	3	3.8	3.8	100.0
	Total	78	100.0	100.0	

BBA in M'sia is Shari'ah-Compliant

Q4B		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	4	5.1	5.1	5.1
	Disagree	18	23.1	23.1	28.2
	No Comment	31	39.7	39.7	67.9
	Agree	18	23.1	23.1	91.0
	Strongly Agree	7	9.0	9.0	100.0
	Total	78	100.0	100.0	

BBA is a Back-door to interest

Q5B		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	10	12.8	12.8	12.8
	Disagree	18	23.1	23.1	35.9
	No Comment	28	35.9	35.9	71.8
	Agree	17	21.8	21.8	93.6
	Strongly Agree	5	6.4	6.4	100.0
	Total	78	100.0	100.0	

BBA promotes *Maqāsid al-Shari'ah*

Q6B		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	5	6.4	6.4	6.4
	Disagree	17	21.8	21.8	28.2
	No Comment	26	33.3	33.3	61.5
	Agree	21	26.9	26.9	88.5
	Strongly Agree	9	11.5	11.5	100.0
	Total	78	100.0	100.0	

IR as benchmark for BBA should be avoided

Q7B		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	7	9.0	9.0	9.0
	Disagree	11	14.1	14.1	23.1
	No Comment	13	16.7	16.7	39.7
	Agree	21	26.9	26.9	66.7
	Strongly Agree	26	33.3	33.3	100.0
	Total	78	100.0	100.0	

Using IR brings doubts

Q8B		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	5	6.4	6.4	6.4
	Disagree	14	17.9	17.9	24.4
	No Comment	12	15.4	15.4	39.7
	Agree	25	32.1	32.1	71.8
	Strongly Agree	22	28.2	28.2	100.0
	Total	78	100.0	100.0	

BBA indirectly involves IR

Q9B		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	15	19.2	19.2	19.2
	Disagree	15	19.2	19.2	38.5
	No Comment	22	28.2	28.2	66.7
	Agree	18	23.1	23.1	89.7
	Strongly Agree	8	10.3	10.3	100.0
	Total	78	100.0	100.0	

Convergence towards conv. Banks

Q10B		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	8	10.3	10.3	10.3
	Disagree	8	10.3	10.3	20.5
	No Comment	28	35.9	35.9	56.4
	Agree	24	30.8	30.8	87.2
	Strongly Agree	10	12.8	12.8	100.0
	Total	78	100.0	100.0	

BBA is relatively more expensive

Q11B		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	7	9.0	9.0	9.0
	Disagree	17	21.8	21.8	30.8
	No Comment	17	21.8	21.8	52.6
	Agree	25	32.1	32.1	84.6
	Strongly Agree	12	15.4	15.4	100.0
	Total	78	100.0	100.0	

BBA unjust in case of early settlement

Q12B		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	6	7.7	7.7	7.7
	Disagree	22	28.2	28.2	35.9
	No Comment	23	29.5	29.5	65.4
	Agree	18	23.1	23.1	88.5
	Strongly Agree	9	11.5	11.5	100.0
	Total	78	100.0	100.0	

Frequency Table for Section C

Familiar with MMP?

Q-I		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	61	78.2	78.2	78.2
	No	17	21.8	21.8	100.0
Total		78	100.0	100.0	

MMP is better than BBA

Q1C		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree	2	3.3	3.3	3.3
	No Comment	6	9.8	9.8	13.1
	Agree	23	37.7	37.7	50.8
	Strongly Agree	30	49.2	49.2	100.0
	Total	61	100.0	100.0	

MMP promotes PLS mode of finance

Q2C		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree	1	1.6	1.6	1.6
	No Comment	1	1.6	1.6	3.3
	Agree	35	57.4	57.4	60.7
	Strongly Agree	24	39.3	39.3	100.0
	Total	61	100.0	100.0	

MMP reflects true spirit of Islam

Q3C		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree	3	4.9	4.9	4.9
	No Comment	3	4.9	4.9	9.8
	Agree	30	49.2	49.2	59.0
	Strongly Agree	25	41.0	41.0	100.0
	Total	61	100.0	100.0	

MMP Promotes *Maqāsid al-Shari'ah*

Q4C		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree	2	3.3	3.3	3.3
	No Comment	6	9.8	9.8	13.1
	Agree	32	52.5	52.5	65.6
	Strongly Agree	21	34.4	34.4	100.0
	Total	61	100.0	100.0	

IR as benchmark for MMP should be avoided

Q5C		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	4	6.6	6.6	6.6
	Disagree	7	11.5	11.5	18.0
	No Comment	4	6.6	6.6	24.6
	Agree	23	37.7	37.7	62.3
	Strongly Agree	23	37.7	37.7	100.0
	Total	61	100.0	100.0	

MMP cheaper than BBA and loan

Q6C		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	2	3.3	3.3	3.3
	Disagree	10	16.4	16.4	19.7
	No Comment	21	34.4	34.4	54.1
	Agree	21	34.4	34.4	88.5
	Strongly Agree	7	11.5	11.5	100.0
	Total	61	100.0	100.0	

MMP contributes to equitable distribution

Q7C		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree	1	1.6	1.6	1.6
	No Comment	14	23.0	23.0	24.6
	Agree	36	59.0	59.0	83.6
	Strongly Agree	10	16.4	16.4	100.0
	Total	61	100.0	100.0	

MMP may be difficult to implement

Q8C		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	4	6.6	6.6	6.6
	Disagree	14	23.0	23.0	29.5
	No Comment	6	9.8	9.8	39.3
	Agree	30	49.2	49.2	88.5
	Strongly Agree	7	11.5	11.5	100.0
	Total	61	100.0	100.0	

Frequency Table for Section D

Which mode would you select?

Q1D		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	BBA	18	23.1	23.1	23.1
	MMP	58	74.4	74.4	97.4
	Conventional Loan	2	2.6	2.6	100.0
	Total	78	100.0	100.0	

Which mode is better representative of IFS

Q2D		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	BBA	7	9.0	9.0	9.0
	MMP	55	70.5	70.5	79.5
	Both	16	20.5	20.5	100.0
	Total	78	100.0	100.0	

Islamic Banks lack products

Q3D		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	59	75.6	75.6	75.6
	No	16	20.5	20.5	96.2
	Not Sure	3	3.8	3.8	100.0
	Total	78	100.0	100.0	

MMP will help development of IFS

Q4D		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	62	79.5	79.5	79.5
	No	1	1.3	1.3	80.8
	Not Sure	15	19.2	19.2	100.0
	Total	78	100.0	100.0	

IR should be completely avoided

Q5D		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	58	74.4	74.4	74.4
	No	9	11.5	11.5	85.9
	Not Sure	11	14.1	14.1	100.0
	Total	78	100.0	100.0	

Are you familiar with Ijarah Sukuk?

Q6D		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	52	66.7	66.7	66.7
	No	26	33.3	33.3	100.0
	Total	78	100.0	100.0	

Would you invest in *Ijārah Sukūk*?

Q7D		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	45	86.5	86.5	86.5
	No	2	3.8	3.8	90.4
	Not Sure	5	9.6	9.6	100.0
	Total	52	100.0	100.0	

Using IR as benchmark is OK?

Q8D		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	21	40.4	40.4	40.4
	No	21	40.4	40.4	80.8
	Not Sure	10	19.2	19.2	100.0
	Total	52	100.0	100.0	

***Sukūk* holders should be liable?**

Q9D		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	38	73.1	73.1	73.1
	No	6	11.5	11.5	84.6
	Not Sure	8	15.4	15.4	100.0
	Total	52	100.0	100.0	

Secondary Market is necessary

Q10D		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	46	88.5	88.5	88.5
	No	1	1.9	1.9	90.4
	Not Sure	5	9.6	9.6	100.0
	Total	52	100.0	100.0	

***Sukūk* should be more popularized**

Q11D		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	46	88.5	88.5	88.5
	No	3	5.8	5.8	94.2
	Not Sure	3	5.8	5.8	100.0
	Total	52	100.0	100.0	

Chi-Square Test

Which mode would you select?

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
BBA	18	26.0	-8.0
MMP	58	26.0	32.0
Conventional Loan	2	26.0	-24.0
Total	78		

Test Statistics

	Which mode would you select?
Chi-Square	64.000
df	2
Asymp. Sig.	.000

Perception of BBA

	Should be in line with Shari'ah	PLS are true representative	Interest is not Riba	BBA in M'sia is Shari'ah-Compliant	BBA is a Back-door to interest	BBA promotes Maqasid al-Shari'ah	IR as benchmark for BBA should be avoided
Chi-Square ^(a, b)	112.385	49.564	180.974	29.308	19.564	18.923	15.333
df	2	4	4	4	4	4	4
Asymp. Sig.	.000	.000	.000	.000	.001	.001	.004

^a 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 26.0.

^b 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 15.6.

	Using IR brings doubts	BBA indirectly involves IR	Convergence towards conv. Banks	BBA is relatively more expensive	BBA unjust in case of early settlement
Chi-Square ^(a, b)	16.487	6.744	23.795	11.487	15.205
df	4	4	4	4	4
Asymp. Sig.	.002	.150	.000	.022	.004

Perception of MMP

	MMP is better than BBA	MMP promotes PLS mode of finance	MMP reflects true spirit of Islam	MMP Promotes Maqasid al-Shari'ah	IR as benchmark for MMP should be avoided	MMP cheaper than BBA and loan	MMP contributes to equitable distribution	MMP may be difficult to implement
Chi-Square	35.328	57.230	40.180	37.689	32.361	23.836	43.459	37.115
df	3	3	3	3	4	4	3	4
Asymp. Sig.	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

General Overview

	Which mode would you select?	Which mode is better representative of IFS	Isl. Banks lack products	MMP will help development of IFS	IR should be completely avoided
Chi-Square	64.000	50.077	66.077	78.538	59.154
df	2	2	2	2	2
Asymp. Sig.	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

Perception of Ijārah Sukūk

	Would you invest in I. Sukuk?	Using IR as benchmark is OK?	Sukuk holders should be liable?	Sec. Mkt. Is necessary	Sukuk should be popularized
Chi-Square	66.500	4.654	37.077	71.577	71.115
df	2	2	2	2	2
Asymp. Sig.	.000	.098	.000	.000	.000